

Linking Research & Innovation for Gender Equality

D5.4 Sustainability and Expansion Plan

WP5 - Engagement, change
management and sustainability

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Executive Summary

The present deliverable aimed at developing a robust individual sustainability strategy for ensuring the continuity of the inclusive Gender Equality Plan (GEP)'s measures by the RPOs and RFOs involved in CALIPER. This document built upon the key policy insights on gender equality work at European level, the existing literature on the main success and hindering factors for sustaining the GE momentum within the institution and the institutionalisation of organisational changes, the *D5.1 Internal engagement and change management strategy guidelines*, the internal monitoring and evaluation reports of the partners' GEP measures (D4.2 and D4.3) and the workshops with internal and external stakeholders conducted by each CALIPER partners.

The present deliverable includes 9 individual sustainability strategies developed for each CALIPER partner ensuring the continuation of the gender equality work beyond the project lifecycle.

It should be noted that in most of the CALIPER partners the gender equality effort is sustained since:

- 2 inclusive GEPs (UNILE and UZG FER) continue their implementation because their overall duration exceeded the CALIPER project life cycle.
- 2 inclusive GEPs (by YU and IRB) have been updated after the 2nd iteration of the GEP implementation. Both GEPs are approved by their internal administration (for IRB it was not necessary for the updated GEP to undergo a new approval process).
- 4 new inclusive GEPs have been elaborated undergoing an internal approval process (ECE NTUA, SNRFSFG, UEFISCDI, STU BA) since their duration ended within the project implementation. Three out of four GEPs have been approved. The last one is under the approval process (ECE NTUA).
- Parts of 1 inclusive GEP (ULB) that has been elaborated within the project implementation phase will be incorporated in the institutional overall Gender and Diversity Plan. The plan is under consultation.

This document is primarily addressed to the RPOs/RFOs involved in CALIPER to support the implementation and sustainability of the GEPs. It can also be used by other higher education and research institutions that desire to foster/sustain structural change for gender equality.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

This deliverable is part of WP5: Engagement, change management and sustainability. This WP aims at creating the appropriate conditions and strategies for ensuring the acceptance and sustainability of the inclusive Gender Equality Plan (GEP)'s measures by the RPOs and RFOs involved in CALIPER. The objective of the T5.4 is twofold: on one side it aims at supporting partner RFOs and RPOs in ensuring that the internal change process will be sustained after the end of the project on the other side to influence and offer the opportunity to interested RPOs and RFOs to adopt gender balance measures, ensuring the maximum impact of the project's outcomes (see D5.5 CALIPER Charter).

The objective of this document is to help the RPOs and RFOs involved in CALIPER to develop a tailored internal sustainability strategy of the gender equality changes achieved throughout the two iteration phases of the GEP implementation during the CALIPER project.

The document presents, on the one hand, some insights to understand the current policy context on gender equality work at European level as well as the main success and hindering factors for sustaining the GE momentum within the institution. This document builds upon the existing literature, the *D5.1 Internal engagement and change management strategy guidelines*, the internal monitoring and evaluation reports of the partners' GEP measures and the consultations with internal and external stakeholders conducted by each CALIPER partners leading the ground for the development of a tailored sustainability and expansion plan for each CALIPER partners.

The present document can be considered as a tool to be used by each RPOs/RFOs for sustaining the momentum on the promotion of inclusive gender equality within their institutions. The promotion of gender equality requires a careful analysis of the internal and external context of each organisation. Gender equality legislation, institutional procedures, starting points, internal support, existing gender equality structures and many other factors may differ between organisations. Therefore, a 'one size fits all' approach would not be fruitful. Following this reasoning, the partners' individual sustainability strategy has been developed within the context of the present deliverable.

Finally, the present document is complemented at the concluding remarks by the relevant activities to be carried out in the upcoming years ensuring the overall sustainability of the project outputs, as foreseen in the project's grant agreement.

1.2 Intended audience

This document is primarily addressed to the RPOs/RFOs involved in CALIPER to support the sustainability of their inclusive GEPs. It can also be used by other higher education and research institutions that desire to foster/sustain structural change for gender equality.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

Chapter 2 outlines the current policy landscape and respective evidence from the literature on GEPs facilitating and hindering factors as well as CALIPER approach towards sustainability. Chapter 3 presents for each CALIPER partner their individual sustainability strategy securing the continuation of the respective gender equality measures. Chapter 5 includes the concluding remarks of the present report. Lastly, Annex II presents the sustainability plan template that partners used to develop their own sustainability strategy and Annex III presents the detailed reports from the sustainability workshops that partners performed with internal and external stakeholders in order to develop their individual strategy.

1.4 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

The present report on sustainability supports the whole project process. It is connected to WP3 (Implementation of GEPs) and WP4 (Monitoring and evaluation) given that the plan is essential to ensuring support to the different actions and measures included in the GEP are sustained beyond the project implementation acting as a guarantee to the sustainability of the GE measures. Finally, this deliverable is part of the last task of WP5 (Engagement, change management and sustainability) and thus its knowledge and output has been built on the knowledge incurred under the tasks T5.1, T5.2 and T5.3 (engaging with the innovation ecosystems and raising awareness and engagement activities, respectively).

2 Sustaining institutional change towards inclusive Gender Equality

2.1 Inclusive Gender Equality Plans as a policy instrument to achieve institutional change

Over the last two decades, the European Union (EU) has been extensively addressing gender inequalities in higher education and scientific research, which has been systematically documented through the SHE Figures reports. Gender equality is now a fundamental priority of EU research and innovation policy.

A key pillar of European policy is the integration of a gender perspective into all programmes and funding instruments aimed at shaping the European Research Area (ERA). Specifically, ERA Priority 4 focuses on gender equality and gender mainstreaming in R&I^{1,2} and Horizon Europe sets gender equality as a crosscutting principle aiming to eliminate gender and intersecting socioeconomic inequalities throughout Research and Innovation (R&I) systems. Additionally, the 27 Member States are invited to adopt policies and measures to combat gender inequalities in these areas.

In this vein, since 2015, EU actively promotes and supports, the implementation of GEPs in research institutions as a tool to mainstream gender for structural change ([Clavero & Galligan, 2021](#)). According to [Ljubljana Declaration \(2021\)](#), considered a transformative tool “to achieve long-term and sustainable advancement towards Gender equality in R&I”, GEPs have been made an eligibility criterion for accessing Horizon Europe funding. This foresees that GEPs have specific mandatory content (specific areas of intervention) and process related requirements³.

Specifically, in the context of Horizon Europe, GEPs seek to integrate the gender dimension into the internal functioning of universities and research organisations (both those that fund and those that carry out research). The five proposed areas of intervention are: (a) work-life balance; (b) enhancing the presence of women in leadership and decision-making positions; (c) gender equality in recruitment and promotion; (d) integrating the gender dimension into teaching and research content; and (e) addressing sexual harassment and gender-based violence. GEPs should be a public document posted on the institution's website and approved by its administration. Each institution should allocate resources and qualified staff (on gender equality issues) to implement it over time, systematically collect gender-disaggregated data, and develop training and awareness-raising activities on gender equality and gender bias for staff.

The abovementioned Horizon Europe GEP eligibility criterion exerted noticeable impact on the national gender equality activities in R&I, which is demonstrated particularly by the increase in approved GEPs in R&I institutions ([Knapińska & Chrobak-Tatara, 2023](#)). **The requirement for institutions to have a GEP, in order to receive research funding from Horizon Europe was a catalyst and a game changer.** By 2022-23 most of Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) and research centres in EU had established GEPs within their own institutions. Thus, GEPs have emerged as the dominant policy instrument for advancing gender equality in R&I institutions.

¹ [European research area \(ERA\) | European Commission \(europa.eu\)](#)

² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en#gender-equality-in-the-european-research-area-era

³wp-11-widening-participation-and-strengthening-the-european-research-area_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf (europa.eu)

This policy change has also created a more favorable environment for CALIPER's partners with regards to the implementation of the gender equality measures foreseen in their GEPs and in some cases facilitated the approval process of the new GEPs developed by some of the partners, during the final period of the project implementation. Overall, all partners, have reported that this was a positive change facilitating the gender equality work within their institutions, contributing/ensuring also the sustainability of their inclusive GEP measures.

In any case, Gender Equality work remains a long-term process and often encounters steep challenges even in this favourable environment, resulting sometimes in setbacks of achievements of an organisation. The following section is focused on the current evidence from literature that can facilitate or hinder GEPs implementation and sustainability.

2.2 Current evidence: GEPs success and hindering factors

Universities and research institutions remain both gendered and gendering organizations ([Acker, 1990](#); [Rosa, Drew & Canavan, 2020](#)). Both academia and labour market are still horizontally and vertically segregated, there is significant absence of the gender dimension in teaching and research and there are still persistent phenomena of sexual harassment affecting the quality of the produced work and research, which in turn has a negative social and economic impact in the wider society.

Thus, the fact that an institution has initiated gender equality work, for example a GEP, does not guarantee that gender inequalities are being tackled in a sustainable manner ([O'Connor, 2020](#)). Furthermore, the potential of GEPs to generate institutional and cultural change in universities is still a contested matter ([Rosa & Clavero, 2022](#)). On one hand, GEPs are being implemented in complex contexts which are characterized by uncertainty ([Glouberman & Zimmerman, 2002](#)). For example, the emergence of new far right movement and the marketization and liberalisation of the academia testify the increased complexity of environments in which GEPs are being designed and implemented. On the other hand, GEPs have been criticized for being technocratic tools focusing on hard data incorporating also conservative frameworks for understanding gender equality and the respective actions designed to achieve that goal ([Lätti, 2017](#)). However [Clavero and Galligan \(2021\)](#) argue that *"while a GEP may be initiated by a managerialist logic where the goal is to formulate a reasonable technocratic document and to follow it through the different phases, it can also provide opportunities for transforming gender–power relationships in the organization"*.

During the past decade several EU projects funded by the FP7, Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe programmes worked on developing and implementing GEPs in research institutions across Europe. Thus several scholars investigated the potential of GEPs to bring sustainable structural change towards gender equality by performing (comparative) studies among the GEP implementing partners of these projects investigating among others the effects of a GEP and the potential facilitating and hindering factors for implementing a GEP ([Clavero & Galligan, 2021](#), [Anagnostou, 2022](#); [Bencivenga & Drew, 2021](#); [Palmén & Kalpazidou Schmidt, 2019](#)).

For example, [Clavero and Galligan \(2021\)](#) analysing 7 GEPs, developed and implemented through the "Sage" project, found persistent gender gaps in levels of participation and engagement in GEP design and implementation, lack of gender disaggregated data, insufficient recognition of the Gender Equality issue and important challenges for changing the formal criteria by which academic merit and scientific excellence is evaluated in recruitment and promotion processes. Overall, they mention that the change process should be sensitive to the existing internal gender power relations, and the multiple and interrelated axis through which these power dynamics are manifested. In addition, they recognize as a prerequisite having an institutional

consensus on the value of having gender justice both in the formal and informal procedures of the institution which can be enhanced from university leaders' commitment on the topic.

Also, an earlier study conducted by [Timmers, Willemsen and Tijdens \(2010\)](#) analysing the impact of gender equality policies implemented from 2000 to 2007 in Dutch HE institutions, found that these policies reducing the existing glass ceiling. However, [Benschop and Verloo \(2011\)](#) claimed that progress was hindered by many impediments to change such as the managerialist tendency of planned change, the need for simultaneous short and long-term agendas for change, the issue of resistance, the need to address gender-related emotions and attitudes, the intersectionality of multiple inequalities, and the inclusion and voice of all stakeholders, not only particular categories of women. [Anagnostou \(2022\)](#) analysing the factors that hinder the implementation of GEPs in research and HE institutions based on 5 GEPs in Greece, Cyprus, Romania, Italy and Serbia which have been developed and implemented by the Horizon 2020 project "TARGET, argues that "the lack of a coherent GE discourse in R&I policies that sheds light on structural barriers and implicit bias is a central impediment limiting the potential of GEPs".

[Bencivenga and Drew, 2021](#) comparing GEPs implemented in Italy and Ireland highlight the importance of receiving support of the top management in the change process and the difficulties in changing the ways in which excellence and merit is evaluated as indicated also in as [Clavero and Galligan \(2021\)](#). They mention two main strategies to accelerate the achievement of gender equality, minimize resistance to change and promote the HEI's internationalization: 1. The use of qualitative and quantitative key performance indicators and 2. the use of existing tools, protocols, non-formal initiatives, laws, to ensure that the GEP proposals integrate and build upon existing knowledge and experience.

Other scholars mention as a challenge to achieve gender equality in academia, the simplified notion of 'the woman' propounded by liberal and neoliberal feminism ([Tzanakou & Pearce 2019](#)) and the lack of attention to the dynamics of change ([Schmidt & Cacace 2019](#)). [Ikävalko & Kantola \(2017\)](#) mention that discursive strategies in resisting feminism include "gender equality having gone too far", "constructing an opposition between women's and men's interests", constructing an opposition between "good gender equality and too radical feminism" or simply arguing that "gender equality has already been achieved".

Lastly, the GEAR tool⁴ developed by EIGE, on the hindering factors risking the entire GEP process including the sustainability of the gender equality actions, mention ([EIGE, 2022](#)):

1. Resistance to the implementation of a GEP
2. Low engagement and mobilisation of stakeholders including a lack of understanding of the need for, and importance of gender equality may be encountered.
3. An absence of dedicated, adequate, and sustained resources, both human and financial, for gender equality work and for developing, implementing, and monitoring a GEP can be an obstacle.
4. A lack of availability of, or access to, sex-disaggregated human resources data.
5. A lack of institutional or organisational authority of staff responsible for GEP implementation including minimum autonomy to implement changes.

The same tool mentions the below action as facilitating factors of the GEP process

⁴ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear>

1. Involve stakeholders within and outside the organisation
2. Establish a well-equipped and well-positioned gender equality body (e.g. a dedicated unit, working group, team or office)
3. Have available of sex-disaggregated data and data on intersectional dimensions such as age, nationality, and disability:
4. Find the balance between clear objectives and flexible implementation.

Thus, it seems that there several facilitating as well as hindering factors affecting the GEP process and the respective sustainability of the gender equality work. **Taking into consideration that different contexts, such as institutional gendered practices and norms, shape the forms of resistance (Ahmed, 2012) and that gender equality interventions taking place in complex contexts are characterized by uncertainty (Glouberman & Zimmerman, 2002), it is of utmost importance when thinking about sustainability not to consider a strategy “one-size-fits-all”.**

The following section is focused on processes/actions for institutionalising the changes that can back up the GEPs implementation and sustainability at the CALIPER’s GEPs implementing partners.

2.3 Institutionalising Gender Equality measures in Higher Education and research institutions

In complex and uncertain environments some changes are only part of a long journey of organizational adaptation.

When it comes to institutionalisation of gender equality measures, according to EIGE⁵

“The strategic goal of the process is to integrate gender equality into the regular rules, procedures and practices of an institution. A successful gender mainstreaming implementation will lead to the transformation of an institution, thus also impacting on the organisational culture.”

[Wroblewski & Palmén](#) (2022) suggest that RPOs are embedded in two conflicting institutional logics – the academic and the organisational logic which can be one of the main reasons for the ineffective implementation of gender equality policies. Successful GEPs have to address both these logics.

According to the same authors a theory of change approach enables individual and institutional reflexivity to be integrated into the GEP process. This has to be tailored to the context and needs of the specific institution and may focus on the development of the GEP itself or on specific interventions or measures within the GEP. Thus, institutionalisation is not an all-or-nothing concept but reflects degrees of persistence in a change. Based on the organisational change theory and according to the institutionalisation framework proposed by Cummings & Worley (2015), there are five institutionalisation processes that can directly affect the degree to which interventions are institutionalised:

1. Socialisation: This concerns the transmission of information about beliefs, preferences, norms and values with respect to the intervention. A continual process of socialization is necessary to promote persistence of the change program. New information should be communicated to other employees and especially new members of the organisation. Transmission of information about the interventions helps bring new members onboard and allows participants to reaffirm the beliefs and norms and values underlying the intervention.

2. Commitment: This binds people to behaviours associated with the intervention. It includes initial commitment to the program as well as recommitment over time. Opportunities for commitment should allow people to select the necessary behaviours freely, explicitly, and publicly. Commitment should derive

⁵ <https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gender-institutional-transformation/gender-mainstreaming-and-institutional-transformation>

from several organisational levels including employees directly involved and the middle and upper managers who can support or thwart the intervention.

3. Reward allocation: This involves linking rewards to the new behaviours required by an intervention. Organisational rewards can enhance the persistence of changes. A combination of intrinsic and extrinsic rewards can reinforce new behaviours. Intrinsic rewards are internal and derive from the opportunities for challenge development and accomplishment found in the work. Extrinsic rewards include money for example for increased contributions.

4. Diffusion: This refers to the process of transferring changes from one unit/department to another. Diffusion facilitates institutionalization by providing a wider organisation base to support new behaviours.

5. Sensing and calibration: This involves detecting deviations from desired interventions and behaviours and taking corrective action. This knowledge can be undertaken from the establishment of effective monitoring and evaluation systems for interpreting if the change actions are being implemented according to the planned objectives and timeline. In case there is any deviation, this knowledge can then initiate corrective actions to ensure that behaviours are more in line with the intervention.

In addition, according to the model proposed by [EIGE \(2016\)](#) on institutional transformation gender mainstreaming is conceived as a strategy that is pursued as a systematic and planned process for organisational learning. The strategic goal of the process is to integrate gender equality into the regular rules, procedures and practices of an institution. Gender mainstreaming is therefore understood both as a process as well as a state.

At the model they identify three phases of mainstreaming gender in an organisation:

1. The initial phase in which the process of the change is planned and some first steps are made by the stakeholders in order to anchor gender equality as a guiding principle in all procedures and practices in an organisational setting

2. The implementation phase in which the relevant planned actions are becoming a reality. Meaning that now the planned regulations and procedures are in place adopting a gender dimension.

3. The consolidation phase in which gender equality is part of all regular procedures and thus gender equality is sustainably anchored within an organisation's culture.

In addition, according to [Sangiuliano & Cortesi, 2019](#), when it comes to the development of a GEP within an EU funded project, the gender equality work and GEPs implemented might pose higher dismissal risks. Therefore, and focusing on the EQUAL-IST project, another H2020 project, with regards to the sustainability of the respective gender equality actions/GEPs developed, they mention 5 key Dimensions (ibid p165):

1. Rules and procedures: Meaning to integrate the relevant actions into existing management policies and regulations.

2. Structures: Corresponding to the assignment of existing structure the responsibility to carry out the activities.

3. Resources: Safeguarding the allocation of the needed resources, both financial and human, for each activity. Balance internal and external funding sources

4. Knowledge and expertise: Making sure that the necessary (internal or external) Gender Knowledge in place internally to sustain this activity.

5. Consensus: Ensuring support from internal and external stakeholders from the regional national Research and Innovation ecosystem.

Withing the CALIPER project they have established relevant gender equality bodies for being accountable of the Gender Equality activities, they have developed internal gender equality knowledge and collaborated with external stakeholders etc. However, after the end of an EU funded project resources are not always ensured. Most of the CALIPER partners are at the transition phase between phase 2 and 3 of the EIGE's model.

Thus, a strategy facilitating the consolidation of the measures is necessary. Key aspect of step three is in principle, monitoring the process of organisational change. This means checking at regular intervals whether, or to what degree, the activities outlined in the working plan have been implemented and whether predefined milestones have been reached [EIGE \(2016\)](#). This also coincide with the last part of the Cummings & Worley (2015) model referred to "sensing and calibration".

Overall, research has identified how gender equality initiatives and policies in R&I often fail during the implementation phase ([Palmén & Kalpazidou Schmidt, 2019](#)), resulting in an absence of deep-seated change and the failure to effectively challenge gender norms.

In addition, institutionalising changes achieved by GEP processes can be critical as it is estimated that more than 70% of efforts aimed at changing existing processes and structures within institutions fail to sustain ([Todnem By, 2005](#)). In particular, resistance in the implementation phase has been identified as one of the main reasons why gender equality initiatives in R&I may fail to create and sustain effective change ([Wroblewski & Palmen, 2022](#)).

[Lombardo and Mergaert \(2013, p. 229\)](#) define resistance as "a phenomenon that emerges during processes of change, such as when gender equalities policies are implemented, and that is aimed at maintaining the status quo and opposing change". *D5.1 Internal engagement and change management strategy* has identified, based on the FESTA Project's results ([2016](#)), the following dimensions of resistances showing that they can take multiple forms:

- **Active/passive resistance.** Active resistance refers to subversive action, to take action to prevent the implementation of gender equality (being critical, blocking, finding objections, ridiculing); whereas passive resistance related to the act of being silent and not doing anything (agreeing verbally but not following through, withholding information).
- **Explicit/implicit resistance.** This refers to the visibility of the resistance, the extent upon which resistance is overt or covert. In the first case, the person shows an apparent and open opposition to gender equality work. In the second case, the person does not want to openly show resistance and finds more discrete or obscure ways to express it. The second type of resistance is, of course, more difficult to identify and address.
- **Gender specific/non gender specific resistance.** Resistance can be directly directed to gender issues or not. For instance, it can be linked to a general resistance to change in the organisation. This renders gender equality work difficult to perform, but it does not focus explicitly on it so there may be ways to overcome it.
- **Individual/group resistance.** This dimension refers to the number of people involved in resistance. It can be an individual, a few or a group.
- **Personal/institutional resistance.** The first one is related to someone's motives, traits, feelings, etc., whereas the second one is associated with the institutional culture or its legal and administrative procedures. It is however important to note that people can change institutional culture and the other way around.

Respective activities on tackling those resistances have been identified in the relevant literature and have been included in D5.1.

The following section drawing from the abovementioned evidence from the literature presents the CALIPER's approach towards sustainability.

2.4 CALIPER's approach towards sustainability

The concept of sustainability has been embedded in the CALIPER project directly from its conception phase. Objective 5 of the project's Grant Agreement is about "Ensuring the sustainability and expansion of the GEPs at a national and international level targeting key stakeholders".

This ambitious objective is being achieved by a set of processes which include:

- the continuous formative monitoring and evaluation process of GEPs implementation (T4.2), that has thoroughly taken stock of achieved results in terms of outputs and outcome indicators, mapped achievements, obstacles and resistances. Its focus on institutionalization processes and thus sustainability has allowed supporting internal discussions on needed adjustments and GEPs refinements during the two implementation phases.
- the development of an internal engagement and communication strategy and the organisation of Online raising awareness sessions and internal workshops in each RPO/ RFO working as a blueprint to reach several university departments (T5.3);
- the development of a sustainability plan at each RPO/RFO partner (T5.4);
- the organization of GE webinars targeting external RPOs and RFOs promoting institutional change for gender equality (T5.4);
- the involvement of policy makers in the Research and Innovation Hub in the participating countries creating strong synergies between RPOs/ RFOs and the policy level actors and, hence, promote, sustain and further expand to other relevant RPOs/ RFOs, the CALIPER results and GEPs developed (T2.2). the establishment of strong links with innovation ecosystem stakeholders and the promotion of these newly established relationships to external RPOs/RFOs as good practices for designing gender equality measures (T5.2);
- the creation of a Charter on Institutional Change for Gender Equal Research and Innovation Hubs promoting the adoption of gender balance measures (T5.4);
- production of policy briefings supporting and promoting the expansion of gender equality measures in academic institutions (T6.4);

Based on [EIGE \(2016\)](#) within the context of this deliverable, which focuses on the sustainability of the gender equality measures at each CALIPER partner, institutionalisation/gender mainstreaming is conceived as a strategy that is pursued as a systematic and planned process for organisational learning within an institution in order to achieve gender equality internally. The goal is to integrate gender equality into the regular rules, procedures and practices of the CALIPER participating institution.

In addition, at this stage few key elements should be noted in advance. Following up on CALIPER's inclusive GEPs implementation process during 2-iterations phases within the past 4 years, at this final stage of the project, CALIPER partners based on the individual inclusive GEP implementation and sustainability process, can be divided into two main groups:

1. Partners whose GEP continues beyond the project duration: (UNILE, IRB, UZG FER, YU),
2. Partners whose GEP ends within the project duration: STU BA, ECE NTUA, SNRFSFG, UEFISCDI and ULB. This group can be further divided into two sub groups:
 - 2.1. The partners that developed a new GEP at the concluding stage of the project which is under approval subject to internal rules and procedures: STU BA, ECE NTUA, SNRFSFG, UEFISCDI;
 - 2.2 ULB that will integrate part of its CALIPER GEP⁶ key objectives, into their new central Gender and Diversity Plan that is under development.

Thus, at this stage of the project implementation, the continuation of the change effort implemented via respective GEP measures is already ensured in the majority of the institutions. Therefore, the aim of the present document is to provide an individual sustainability strategy that will back up this continuous effort for change towards gender equality for achieving the institutionalisation of measures. This strategy draws from the abovementioned literature and based on the project's contractual obligations mentioned in the Grant Agreement.

Thus, the main pillars on which the individual sustainability plans developed and presented in the next chapter are:

- 1. Develop a gender equality vision, post CALIPER's implementation period:** It can be noted that sustainability of gender equality policies and GEPs implemented within an EU funded project might pose higher dismissal risks after the project conclusion due to lack of funding or engagement of relevant stakeholders (Sangiuliano & Cortesi, 2019). Therefore, a medium- to long-term vision statement, especially as part of a broader institutional vision, can convey the institution's goal and commitment for a gender-equal institutional environment. The vision can set new expectations for the attitudes and behaviour of all people and be used as a benchmark for measuring progress.
- 2. Draft an individual institutionalisation/sustainability strategy of GEP activities:** Benchmark the Gender Equality actions based on the five indicators proposed by Cummings & Worley (2015) and EIGE's (2016) model on consolidation of the gender equality measures.
- 3. Foresee potential resistances and ways to tackle them.**

To facilitate this process, a template was created by VIL and shared with the partners to be completed ensuring the consistency among the project partners. The template can be found on Annex II of the present deliverable.

Lastly, all of the CALIPER partners implemented sustainability workshops with internal and external stakeholders within the last year of the project implementation (2023) in order to co-create their institution's gender equality roadmap after the project's end. These workshops have been critical in shaping the below mentioned individual sustainability plans. All the reports can be found at the annex of the present deliverable.

⁶ ULB had linked and developed their CALIPER GEP in alignment with, and in the frame of, its institutional Gender & Diversity policy at the start of the project

3 CALIPER individual sustainability strategies

The present section presents the sustainability of the CALIPER gender equality actions after the project's completion. The consortium consists of 9 GEP implementing partners. In particular, the composition of the consortium is as follows:

- a. RPOs: UNILE, IRB, UZG FER, YU, STU BA, ECE NTUA, STU BA, ULB
- b. RFOs: SNRFSFG, UEFISCDI

This section presents the individual sustainability plan for every organisation based on the institutionalisation principles mentioned in the previous section.

Each plan presents:

1. Partners vision for Gender Equality for the upcoming two years
2. Partners sustainability strategy ensuring sustainability of the GEP measures
3. Partners individual strategy for tackling resistances

3.1 University of Zagreb – Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (RPO) Error! Bookmark not defined.

- Institutional vision for Gender Equality for the upcoming two years:

The strategic goal of the faculty is to provide equal opportunities for employees and students in achieving personal and professional development, unhindered by prejudices and stereotypes (Strategy of Development of UNIZG-FER 2024 - 2028). In our Gender Equality Plan for the period 2021 – 2025 FER UZG had set three overarching goals: equality in scientific careers, balance of representation in decision-making, and integration of the gender dimension in the content of research and innovation. FER UZG will plan, implement and evaluate activities in teaching and scientific activities, and in cooperation with the community, which will contribute, as far as possible, to the fulfilment of the stated general goals.

To be more specific, in the upcoming two years UZG FER plans to implement the following actions.

- Attracting and retaining female researchers

This measure provides for the systematic collection of data and its analysis to better understand why people choose to leave higher education and science. The new insights will be the basis for the introduction of new measures to ensure, to the extent possible, the attraction and retention of talented female researchers.

- Reporting on the status of gender equality

Each two years, FER UZG collects data and analyse the impact of the implemented activities on institutional change. In 2024 FER UZG will prepare and promote the second report.

- Gender-sensitive language in legal documents

FER UZG will continue the revision of language practices in all legal documents of the faculty. FER UZG aims to revise all documents concerning students and employees and have them using the appropriate gender.

Sustainability strategy

Socialisation:

The faculty has set up a public website specially dedicated to gender equality and equal opportunities: https://www.fer.unizg.hr/jednake_mogucnosti. FER UZG publishes news and information regularly.

The Faculty has set up Equal Opportunities Committee which consists of 10 professors, students and heads of relevant administrative offices. The Committee is the permanent advisory body of the Faculty Council, the highest decision-making body of the Faculty, which consists of all professors of the Faculty. The Committee meets once a month to discuss relevant issues and reports regularly to the Faculty Council. It is the responsibility of the Committee to implement the GEP and also maintain the level of engagement of the internal and external stakeholders.

Every year the Faculty organises a workshop for newly hired assistant professors. FER UZG will include the relevant information on the gender equality measures in the training to be received by them.

Commitment:

As mentioned, UZG-FER established a permanent Equal Opportunities Committee which itself represents institutional commitment to gender equality. Also, providing equal opportunities to employees has been included in the new Strategy of Development of UNIZG-FER 2024 – 2028 to strengthen the commitment. It is the duty of the Equal Opportunities Committee to implement this area of the strategic plan, and to permanently induce institutional change toward more equal institution which includes engagement of all employees, and middle and high management.

First of all, the commitment is visible through strategic documents which have been accepted by the Faculty Council, the highest decision-making body of the institution. The Faculty Council consist of all the professors, and representatives of research associates, in total around 250 members. On more practical basis, the Equal Opportunities Committee which is a permanent body meets each month to plan activities and to report on conducted activities. The report of the meeting is then communicated to the members of the Faculty Council in regular monthly meetings.

Reward allocation:

The members of the Equal Opportunities Committee do not receive any reward, since it is a duty of every employee to take part in some committees. In addition, the researchers having Horizon Europe projects also implement activities promoting gender equality within their projects, the only reward being the project itself.

Diffusion:

All the professors from all the departments are members of the Faculty Council. In the regular monthly meetings of the Council, all the relevant information from the monthly meeting of the Equal Opportunities Committee are disseminated.

Sensing and calibration/Monitoring and evaluation:

At the moment, based on the CALIPER project methodology, UZG FER will perform formative self-evaluation every two years and publish a report. The monitoring and evaluation activities are responsibility of the Equal Opportunities Committee.

Resistances

Main issue: Potential gender fatigue

After 4 years of the CALIPER project and 2 years of GEP implementation, the internal stakeholders might feel gender fatigue. The GEP was very ambitious, and FER UZG implemented many actions, which resulted in more women being included in decision-making and setting up the first permanent Equal Opportunities

Committee. Internal stakeholders might conclude that the work in GE is completed and might not be open to participate in the new activities driving institutional change.

Strategy: The main tool is the GEP that the institution is obliged to have and then obliged to fulfil. In addition, the new Equal Opportunity Committee will necessarily drive the institutional change since it is a permanent body of the Faculty Council with clear task to improve the gender equality. It is necessary to continue the engagement of the high management supporting the actions of GEP, and administrative management helping in the implementation.

3.2 Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (RFO)

- Institutional vision for Gender Equality for the upcoming two years:

One of the main objectives is to continue the implementation of GEP activities for the area of human resources, research funding, transfer to market and institutional communication. Besides that, it is planned to continue to support the female researchers and announce new calls on gender research.

- Sustainability strategy

Socialisation:

The continuing meeting with the internal and external stakeholders towards the implementation of new activities are planned. Besides that, various joint events can contribute to the transmission of different information. This year also reorganization of the WIN event and conference in the frame of "Science Fest" is planned.

Since some actions were implemented on a structural basis, the collection and updateing of different information will be done on systematic basis despite any changes in human resources.

Commitment:

No separate department or body for gender equality issues has been appointed at the foundation, however, due to changes in job descriptions the collection of various data now represents the obligatory job part of some employees.

Reward allocation:

There are no additional incentives or rewards applied to changes in job description.

Diffusion:

Raising awareness and constant communication at the managerial level in this regard is important for future developments. Besides that, the organization of various meetings and events can be also very beneficial.

Different types of information can be shared during the organized internal meetings. Besides that, the communication strategy was elaborated in the previous iteration phases and it will be systematically updated.

Sensing and calibration/Monitoring and evaluation:

None of monitoring and evaluation processes are established by now, however the GEP implementation can be monitored and evaluated in the similar way in the future.

Resistances

Main issue: In the future one obstacle could be a lack of resources (financial, human resources). Lack of resources can represent an obstacle for the continuation of the implementation of particular activities.

Besides that, different resistances on individual level regarding the understanding of necessities and significance of gender equality issues and activities related to this topic can take place.

Strategy: Involvement of top management, additional consultations with Administration Department (HR), communication and dissemination tools will be useful in this regard.

The main strategy will be strong communications on various issues, raising awareness and allocation of additional resources.

3.3 Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (RPO)

- Institutional vision for Gender Equality for the upcoming two years:

The Faculty (MTF) as an autonomous organizational part of STU implemented the GEP for the first time through the realization of the CALIPER project. It is the first concrete enforceable document that has been put into practice, with many activities aimed mainly at raising awareness about gender equality. STU BA started from a neutral risk scenario. The legal basis for us is the Labor Code, which has zero tolerance for any forms of discrimination. In our environment, the gender equality plan is understood as a tool for increasing the quality and efficiency of the internal and external process and material content of the communication strategy. This also results in the sustainability plan, which forms the framework of the new GEP for the period 2024 to 2026.

- Sustainability strategy

Socialisation:

As mentioned in the introduction, the most important element of sustainability is the communication strategy. In this case, STU BA wants to continue to focus on addressing internal stakeholders by organizing regular seminars and workshops. STU BA still perceives resistance to the topic of gender equality, which is essentially confused with another aspect of perception. These seminars will focus on various aspects of gender equality with the aim of raising awareness about its correct understanding. Due to the fact that R&I HUB members have different areas of expertise (academia, business, NGOs), STU BA will focus on their beneficial aspects of best practices with an emphasis on due diligence. STU BA will also try to expand the members of the R&I HUB. However, STU BA do not exclude the use of best practices by other entities operating on the national territory, or abroad. Emphasis will be placed on the benefits of raising awareness, using best practices, due diligence and an effective approach.

As previously stated in the Monitoring Report on the GEP's implementation success, STU BA transformed the Working Group into the Council for Gender Equality, which serves as an executive body for the sustainability of GEP implementation. One way to ensure gender equality within the faculty is by implementing it in the internal documentation, which is legally binding. The documentation impacts all aspects of faculty, student, and stakeholder life, both internally and externally. As part of our communication strategy, STU BA added a "Gender Equality Strategy" tab to the faculty website. This tab contains information about current events, the GEP, and useful resources. STU BA plans to expand this communication tool by adding new features and

contributions, such as interviews with successful female students, female researchers, and female entrepreneurs as role models. The website is the official measurable tool in relation to the number of visitors. It is supplemented by social networks, through which STU BA also communicate in this area.

Commitment:

A two-way flow of information is required between the Council, faculty management, and internal stakeholders. The Council for Gender Equality is a body subordinated to the Dean of the Faculty. The Council ensures the coordinated implementation of the GEP. It submits proposals for modification of the GEP in the form of amendments to the management of the MTF STU for approval and creates documents related to its implementation. It is responsible for monitoring and evaluating the GEP. It ensures communication and sustainability of the GEP, ensures communication and counselling with other faculties, or the rectorate of STU, communicates and integrates the policy of diversity, inclusion and gender equality across the entire faculty in the field of teaching, research and employment. The Council communicates and integrates the policy of diversity, inclusion and gender equality towards the external environment, identifies and removes barriers to fulfilling the principles of equal opportunities and gender equality. The Council operates in accordance with its statute, which outlines its organizational and procedural structure. The chairman is appointed by the dean of MTF STU for a term of office of 3 years. The activities of the Council are financed from the faculty budget.

Diffusion:

The Council for Gender Equality maintains a list of representatives of all institutions and departments, through which it communicates the conclusions reached and, conversely, accepts suggestions and ideas from individual organizational parts of the faculty. Collection of information is continuous. The sharing of information and its transfer to organizational parts of the faculty is operational. The council meets once every 2 months.

Sensing and calibration/Monitoring and evaluation:

The evaluation process will take place once a year, and its analysis and conclusions are part of the overall report presented by the council once a year. The evaluation process consists of a written questionnaire distributed to all employees of the faculty.

Resistances

Main issue: Relevant resources are sought to finance the implementation of the GEP ensuring its sustainability. The source of financing is one of the most important concerns for STU BA. Funding consists in covering direct expenses associated with GEP activities such as the seminars mentioned and, other activities in relation to the organization of various undertakings such as attracting female students. Indirect costs in case there are enough resources for the implementation of relevant actions, consist the loss of valuable female employees when they are discouraged from continuing their careers as scientists, etc.

Strategy:

The main goal of the strategy is to increase awareness from a historical perspective. However, the social sphere in Slovakia is not yet prepared to work with this topic without prejudice, which is due to the low level of communication. On the other hand, younger generations are growing up with gender awareness and are erasing the differences between male and female worlds. They see their possibilities without bias. Our faculty is committed to continuing this trend and presenting ourselves as an organization that values

diversity, inclusion, and gender equality. STU BA established a responsible body for gender equality, which will strictly observe the conditions for implementing the new GEP and monitor and evaluate its progress.

3.4 Université libre de Bruxelles (RPO)

- Institutional vision for Gender Equality for the upcoming two years:

The CALIPER project targeted change in R&I fields with a strong underrepresentation of women, and the GEP in STEM that followed was thus devised to particularly make an impact in the STEM fields and faculties, but also included (both soft and structural) objectives and actions relevant at an institution wide level, that target gender inequalities that are common to all disciplines.

ULB continues to follow a strategy of linking and carrying forward goals, objectives, and results of the GEP in STEM in a long-term perspective to guarantee sustainable impact beyond the project period of CALIPER, by their integration into central G&D [Gender and Diversity] planning and policy objectives at institutional level.

It is important to remark that at the initial conceptualisation phase of the GEP in 2020, the successful strategy was pursued to embed the GEP in STEM into central ambitions in the area of gender and diversity, in order to ensure longevity, institutional legitimisation and support from the get-go. Indeed, ULB had already institutionalized the gender equality policy by entrusting this responsibility to a vice-rector back in 2012, extended to gender and diversity policy from 2016. ULB's participation in CALIPER was initiated by the previous Vice-rector in charge of the gender and diversity policy of the university. Of note, a diversity plan for working staff (2019-2022), supported by ACTIRIS, the employment agency for the Brussels Region, was ongoing at the time CALIPER was launched. Thus, a link to the central gender and diversity plan and policy in place during that period (2020), had been built into the design of the CALIPER GEP in STEM from the start of the project. Now a strategic process will be applied, where key objectives, goals and most successful approaches of the GEP in STEM can be transferred back into the new central strategic G&D plan, that is currently in development.

Thus, a set of key objectives in the CALIPER GEP in STEM will now be carried forward into the new central G&D plan in two ways. On the one hand, a select set of "STEM specific objectives" will be represented and, on the other hand, certain "transversal objectives" with institution wide relevance will be integrated.

Key priorities on the agenda will remain: soft actions to fight gender stereotypes in STEM; integrate the gender dimension in STEM research and teaching; structural actions to redress specifically gender inequalities in careers at university - building on the advocacy success achieved with Belgian decision makers that have in Nov 2023 approved legislation that now supports affirmative actions, and discussions on possible types of positive actions to be implemented can now commence at the central university level. Further, preventive measures will be strengthened on: sexual and/or discriminatory harassment and violence, as well as other types of discrimination; the combat against stereotypes and biases; fostering inclusive communications; promoting inclusive pedagogy and gender competences in teaching; advancing the gender dimension in research; all linked to reinforcing the key goal to bridge the leaky pipeline and help equal the scales for women in their career progression. For instance, efforts will be deployed to: more deeply evaluate the pilot project on gender-balance in advisory boards and possibly extending the measure to more boards; to implement new measures for work-life balance that draw on the feasibility studies carried out in CALIPER's GEP; disseminate widely the Toolkit for gender sensitive

recruitment practices; and organizing more trainings (on sexism, sexual harassment, inclusive communication...).

Sustainability strategy

Socialisation:

Activities at central level will continue to play a key role in securing continuous stakeholder support. This includes also the mobilization of, and regular meetings with, actors of the institution wide network of gender contact people – capable of diffusing information directly at their individual faculty level. The permanent Gender+ Commissions established in each STEM faculty will continue to act as an important conduit to diffuse ongoing activities and secure the needed support on the ground. Discussions will be held in the new year on how to shape the continued involvement of CALIPER's steering committee and the STEM deans – to continue their supporting role in diffusing high level information. The seat occupied by ULB's gender and diversity officer and two gender counsellors to the Rector, on the 'Comité femmes et science' – also will significantly strengthen the exchange of practices, advocacy work and actions around gender equality in the academic and scientific field at national level. This committee is made up of representatives from universities, the FRS-FNRS, the ARES, the Ministry of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation (the General Directorate of Higher Education, Lifelong Education and scientific research and the Directorate for Equal Opportunities), ministers responsible for higher education, research, women's rights and equal opportunities, as well as gender contact persons (PCG) of the universities and the FRS-FNRS. ULB's gender and diversity officer is also part of the 'Conference of Gender Contact Persons' of the Wallonia-Brussels Federation, a gender network with representatives of all the higher education institutions of the region (42 members).

In the future, discussions will also seek to explore how the institution's G&D (Gender & Diversity) policy can be shared/addressed within the framework of ULB's membership in CIVIS – European university alliance (funded by the EU).

Commitment:

For more detailed information please refer to the ULB's 'strategic note' on the continuation of the GEP (D3.3). Below a brief summary of key mechanisms in place. Both STEM specific as well as transversal objectives of the GEP will be transferred into the central G&D plan currently under development – to secure long term impact.

The central policy and planning headed by the Vice Rector for gender & diversity as well as the dedicated Officer for gender & diversity will secure high and middle level support for ongoing GE work. The extended collection of gender indicators and disaggregated data that is currently in process, will serve to underpin and legitimize initiatives. Also, the annual gender report will serve as a valuable tool to promote sensitization across the whole of the university community. Further, as mentioned, the permanent gender + commissions in the STEM faculties with support of the Deans, will continue to mobilize efforts at STEM faculty level, while the institutional network of gender contact people will support cross cutting priorities in GE across the whole of the institution. Close collaboration with the central communication department will be maintained to diffuse key milestones in GE with institution wide relevance, as well as exchanges with the communication departments at STEM faculty level will serve as a stable channel to maintain engagement. The dedicated webpages for GE in the STEM faculty's as well as the central webpage on Gender & diversity initiatives, plans and policy will serve as key dissemination channels.

Reward allocation:

In the assessment of researchers and academics (for recruitment and promotion) there is a point on “services à la communauté” i.e. acts of community engagement/service - that is taken into account in the assessment/evaluation procedures. This can be a soft incentive to enhance people’s engagement in G&D initiatives.

Diffusion:

Dedicated webpages for gender equality in each STEM faculty will continue to serve as a source of internal and external information for the university community. Also, the central webpage on Gender & Diversity is currently being remodelled and updated to be truly user friendly and better feature ongoing initiatives – and this will be a central source to raise awareness among all university staff. Moreover, the Gender + commissions in STEM faculties and Gender and diversity contact people network will function to raise awareness in newly onboarded staff. Ideas will also be explored on possibilities to potentially inform actors during the ‘welcome day for staff and students’.

Sensing and calibration/Monitoring and evaluation:

The institutional annual gender report taking stock of GE progress at all levels institution wide, will serve as a valuable tool to underpin evaluation efforts. This report is annually presented to Academic Council and the Administrative Council. Moreover, an inter-institutional report will also be elaborated by the Conference of Gender Contact People and will report on gender equality progress in all the higher education institutions of the region Wallonia-Brussels Federation.

Resistances

Main issue: One obstacle may be the securing of dedicated resources [human and financial] to carry forward GE efforts. With the funding period of the project coming to an end, new and further human resources have to be secured in order to ensure the long-term impact and continuation of actions kick started during the project period.

For the above it has to be noted - that ULB do not expect direct resistance to GE efforts - but that a lack of extended financial and human resources may lead to constraints when initiating actions e.g. in this case does not mean the actor might not want to contribute to GE and is resistant, but simply may not have the means to do so in terms of time and resources.

Strategy: as mentioned, Caliper from the get go has been embedded in a central gender and diversity policy and objectives of Caliper will now also be integrated into a new gender and diversity plan that is in development. The G&D officer and VR for G&D together with other actors, will continue to take impacts forward. However more resources are always in demand - thus the central team has started strategic discussions to see how and where more resources could be found to e.g. enlarge the team or solicit special expertise. This will require the buy-in of top management and the possibility for current budgets to give room to the allocation of more resources to G&D.

3.5 National Technical University of Athens – School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (RPO)

- **Institutional vision for Gender Equality for the upcoming two years:**

The School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (ECE) in the National Technical University of Greece (NTUA), is the first School of the NTUA that has implemented a Gender Equality Plan (GEP). The new version of the GEP is currently finalised and will be approved by the high-level management in the following months. The main objective of the School and its new GEP is to keep gender equality in its high priority areas, implement a series of actions and collaborations to securely transition to the consolidation of gender mainstreaming and achieve the following:

- Increase the female representation at all levels of the School (students, researchers, PhD candidates and Post Docs, and academics) and monitor the progress through the established indicators (i) Proportion of women grade A/B/C staff (academic) and ii) Undergraduate female students in Electrical and Computer Engineering (new enrolled average of 2 years).
- Establish an environment free of gender bias, sexism and harassment, through the application and continuous dissemination of formed procedures, “the Guide on Handling Gender Violence, Sexual Harassment, Bias and Sexist Behaviour”.
- Implementation of structural measures such as the establishment of a Gender Equality Committee, that will further support and coordinate gender equality and diversity actions at the School and work in conjunction with the Gender Equality Office of the School.
- Continue the data collection process on gender equality and intersectionality as part of the School’s decision making process and strategic management.
- Expand the use of inclusive language to all forms of the academic communication (administrative documents, teaching, website etc).
- Communicate and promote positive female role models, as identification with role models and representation has proven to be effective in countering stereotypes and stereotypical attitudes.
- Implement training workshops and information days on gender issues in STEM, to further increase awareness and engagement.
- Increase the number of research with the gender dimension integrated into its content and monitor it through the established indicator; Number and % of Undergraduate, MSc and PhD theses integrating a gender dimension in their subject matter. Important parameter for this integration is the degree to which gender issues and the gender dimension is introduced and analysed in the School’s syllabus. Therefore, it is also a priority to further introduce the gender dimension into under and postgraduate courses.
- Strong collaborations with other academic institutions, the industry and NGOs in order to implement common actions that will improve networking, provide mentoring opportunities for female students, professionals, and academics in STEM and will overall enhance the links between the external environment and the School to support its graduates

Sustainability strategy

Socialisation:

As regards the dissemination of the relevant information to the internal stakeholders, 2 online awareness sessions will be implemented, one every six months. These online awareness sessions will serve as the point for disseminating commitment and progress towards gender equality, future actions, possibilities for collaboration and for further engagement. Participants to these meetings will include members from the ECE NTUA high level management, academics, researchers, administrative personnel and technical personnel. Of course, bilateral meetings or meetings in smaller groups will be implemented if necessary.

The communication of the School's commitment, values, and activities to the external stakeholders, will take place during the various collaborative activities, that are foreseen in the 3rd ECE NTUA GEP. In particular:

- Implementation of at least 2 coffee talks, annually, with invited speakers from the R&I Hub. These "coffee talks" will be elaborated within the framework of courses and will focus on providing information and initiating discussion on gender issues in innovation, entrepreneurship, research etc.
- Organization of at least 1 information event/training workshop, annually, with the participation of the R&I Hub. Indicative topics include issues such as the application of gender sensitive language in communication, the integration of the gender dimension in research, Gender sensitive teaching, Gender violence and sexual harassment, Gender, and intersectionality etc. Experience from the past actions has shown that during these events external stakeholders as well as stakeholders from the R&I hub actively participate either as co-organisers and speakers, or as participants.
- Implementation of at least 1 webinar, annually, to integrate the gender dimension into the alumni network. In this activity, members of the alumni network, professionals in specific fields, will be asked to disseminate and present gender issues from the perspective of their own profession to other students, co-workers and other alumni.
- Cooperation with the G-WISE Network (Greece – Women in STEM & Entrepreneurship) and co-organization of meetings, webinars and/or in person events. The actions co-organised will assist in the improvement of networking for female students, professionals, and academics in STEM as well as in the improvement of mentoring opportunities. Additionally, these events will also highlight the School's commitment and values on gender equality.

The ECE School has a dedicated site for all the announcements implemented by the Gender Equality Office. These announcements include information on events, webinars, workshops, G.E. reports, guides etc. Whenever necessary these announcements are also included in the ECE Webpage latest news section, especially whenever the announcement relates to an event implementation. Additionally, up until now the G.E. Office has a strong presence in the ceremony of the 1st year students welcoming, when promotional material on the G.E. actions and measures undertaken by the School, are presented. The Office intends to create targeted social media (LinkedIn and Facebook) posts where all the events, cooperations, relevant announcements and material will be uploaded. This is planned to take place during the first months of 2024.

Commitment:

The G.E. Office plays a major role towards the continuous commitment of employees, middle and upper management, and students. The Office, which is part of the School's organisational structure, has the responsibility to collect and disseminate data on gender equality, to implement the respective G.E. reports, to organize workshops and events in order to inform, sensitize and engage all members of the School. Additionally, its close cooperation with the NTUA G.E. Committee, another institutional structure, further expands commitment beyond the School level.

The School also intends to establish a Gender Equality Committee (action included of the 3rd GEP), that will also support the continuous engagement of the School's members.

Finally, some of the actions implemented during the 1st and 2nd iteration, have been integrated into the School's strategy, such as the establishment of indicators and targets on the female representation, on the gender dimension integration into research, as well as the implementation and operation of a Guide on sexual harassment, gender bias, violence etc. Communication of the status and/or progress of the above further retains the School members commitment and interest on gender equality.

Visibility of the gender equality commitment to the entire organisation will be achieved through:

- Implementation of 2 online awareness sessions for the internal stakeholder,
- Implementation and dissemination of various collaborative activities (2 coffee talks, at least 1 information event/training workshop, at least 1 webinar, cooperation with the G-WISE Network)
- Continuous updates on the GEP progress, other respective actions and publication of respective material in the ECE NTUA official website.
- Creation of the G.E. Office social media pages and posts related to the GEP progress, other respective actions and publication of respective material.
- Engagement of volunteers for the implementation of the G.E. Office activities and dissemination of the organizational commitment through them.

Reward allocation:

The question of material rewards to the person involved has not yet been settled. ECE NTUA expects that the application of gender-related budget items in the future will help secure funds to, at minimum, reduce the required workload and improve efficiency.

As regards the rewards of the involved people in the effort towards change those include:

- The persons will be involved in a change process to address a critical social and, to a significant extent, scientific issue.
- Student and staff volunteers will be familiarised with gender equality issues, approaches, and methodologies.
- Student and staff volunteers will have additional networking opportunities with internal (to the institution) and external stakeholders due to the collaborative nature of the planned activities.
- Any student volunteers will gain experience during their participation in the plan's activities (as organisers, educators, public relations, etc.)

Diffusion:

The diffusion of change in other departments and the entire organisation will be achieved through the cooperation with the NTUA Gender Equality Committee and the implementation of collaborative actions. The G.E. Officer is also member of the NTUA G.E. Committee, while internal meetings are taking place monthly. Additionally, until now, one collaborative seminar has already taken place on the elimination of sexual harassment in the Higher Education Institutions, while two more are currently planned.

Sensing and calibration/Monitoring and evaluation:

Each action described within the 3rd ECE NTUA GEP, has specific outputs scheduled for implementation. Therefore, the monitoring and evaluation process will be based on the implementation (or not) of each action's specific outputs. The monitoring and evaluation process will be undertaken annually, at the end of each academic year. The person responsible for this process will be the G.E. Officer, with the cooperation of volunteers, the Secretary (whenever necessary), and the Deanery. The results of the monitoring and evaluation process will result in updates in the GEP and/or in specific actions.

Resistances

Main issue: A change in the top-level management (Dean & Deanery) might result in changes regarding the priority of G.E.

Strategy: Networking and collaboration to strengthen the position of the GEP and empower those committed to change is necessary. E.g. networking with members of the top and middle level management could assist in tackling the resistance. Additional measures include teamwork and a clear strategy and methodology to involve more people, create synergies and result in a positively influencing environment.

3.6 Institute for Research in Biomedicine (RPO)

- Institutional vision for Gender Equality for the upcoming two years:

The IRB Barcelona understands the importance of creating an environment in which diversity, equality and inclusion are valued and promoted. With this goal one of the main objective for the upcoming years is to achieve equality and diversity balance among IRB Barcelona personnel understanding that this contributes to excellence in research and the welfare of all those involved.

In addition, some of the main objectives to keep pursuing in the upcoming years are the following:

- Ensure equal, inclusive and non-sexist communication.
- Guarantee gender-neutral selection and promotion processes, working towards a balanced presence in the different professional categories.
- Guarantee equal opportunities to, training and career development for the entire workforce.
- Promote women to leadership position in science.
- Work towards an organisation of working time that favours a work-life balance.
- Ensure the application of effective policies to prevent harassment in the organisation.

Sustainability strategy

Socialisation:

In regards to the internal communication and meeting held to provide relevant information there are two mechanism in place and institutionalized at the IRB Barcelona

- Equality and Diversity Committee meetings: These meetings are held once every two month with the idea of discussing relevant topics and address current actions under development of the Gender Equality Plan or other initiatives outside the GEP. The members of the EDC represent different areas of the institute, assuring that both the actions and the feedback gather in these meetings have representation of various admin departments, laboratories, and core facilities.
- Induction sessions: Through the CALIPER framework, the IRB has developed and institutionalized the action of “Reinforce equality and diversity topics in on boarding sessions”. Through these sessions, every newcomer that arrives to the IRB receives a presentation with a brief explanation of the GEP, the Equality and Diversity Committee and its role, among other topics. These sessions are mandatory and up to this date are done at least twice a month (or more depending in the number of newcomers per month).
- Social Media, internal email campaigns, and internal activities: As done through the duration of the project the EDC will continue to disseminate new actions and efforts through social media platforms, email, campaigns, and institutional blog.

In regards to interactions with external stakeholders, the IRB Barcelona has shown interest in being part of an emerging CoP and it's in constant interaction with members of the research community at a regional level.

Commitment:

The IRB Barcelona is devoted in assuring and promoting equality and diversity. The existence of an institutionalized committee such as the EDC, provides overall commitment assuring that through this committee the institute is always developing a strategy through which promote and monitor equality and diversity issues and to provide support and guidance in the implementation of policies and action plans. To support this commitment, through a recent implemented action in the actual GEP, the IRB created an internal regulation to govern the EDC. This regulation provides a framework in which the institute commits to the existence and mission of the committee.

As mentioned before, the committee meets with a defined periodicity and its role and actions are disseminated when applicable. In addition the Committee has a dedicate section in the institutional website, including the members, explanation of the actions, and a direct link to the current GEP.

Reward allocation:

The IRB allocates a specific budget for the Equality and Diversity Committee, this budget is usually used for actions such as specific trainings, mentoring programmes, special events, roundtables, wellbeing activities, among others.

Sensing and calibration/Monitoring and evaluation:

Since some of the actions of the current GEP are still under development, the idea is to have the same structure of monitoring and development than the action that are already completed.

In addition, all the efforts in regard to equality and diversity are reported every 6 months through internal reporting tracked and sent to Directorate and External Board (“Patronato”). In addition, the minutes and reports of every EDC meeting are sent to directorate every two months after the committee meeting.

Resistances

Main issue: Since it's the third GEP of the IRB, it is not expected a major resistance moving forward, nevertheless, one of the obstacles that URB may face is the implementation of topics that are not yet fully implemented like the integration of gender dimensions into research and accomplishing gender balance on decision making bodies at the Institute. The obstacles mentioned, only involve a certain part of the GEP, meaning it will not fully impact on the progression and success of the GEP. It's a work in progress to be improved as the actions are implemented.

Strategy: Follow GEP Objectives. Participation in best practices groups, sharing information with key internal stakeholders, planning awareness sessions at the Institute.

3.7 Executive Unit for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania (RFO)

Institutional vision for Gender Equality for the upcoming two years:

In alignment with our dedication to pioneering gender equality in the research sector, UEFISCDI's vision is to catalyze a significant shift towards inclusive research practices across Romania. UEFISCDI aims to redefine the research paradigm by embedding gender equality as a core component of research excellence. Over the next two years, our goal is to see a substantial increase in the integration of gender dimensions within the content of funded research. By doing so, UEFISCDI expects to pave the way for more inclusive and comprehensive research outcomes that are reflective of our diverse society. Our focus will be on ensuring that gender considerations become an indispensable part of the research lifecycle, from design through to dissemination.

Sustainability strategy

Socialisation:

To effectively communicate our steadfast commitment to gender equality, UEFISCDI will engage in a multifaceted socialisation strategy. UEFISCDI will deploy our robust online presence, utilizing our website and social media platforms to broadcast our vision and the ongoing efforts to embed gender equality into our research culture. An annual 'Gender in Research' symposium will serve as a cornerstone for these efforts, providing a recurring platform for dialogue, knowledge exchange, and showcasing progress. This event, along with regular updates and features on digital platforms, will keep both internal and external stakeholders informed and engaged in our journey toward gender inclusivity in research.

Ensuring new staff members are immediately immersed in our culture of gender equality is crucial. From their first day, they will be introduced to our gender equality ethos through our induction programs. Our commitment to gender-responsive research will be visible through our actions, such as incorporating gender equality metrics into our research evaluation criteria. These measures will be disseminated through interactive onboarding sessions, internal newsletters, and featured stories on our intranet, fostering an environment where gender equality is recognized as a fundamental value of our institution.

Commitment:

Recommitment to gender equality will be fostered through both structural and cultural changes within the organization. Changes such as the incorporation of gender equality responsibilities in HR job descriptions will ensure that gender considerations are embedded in the fabric of our daily operations. Our Gender Equality Committee, bolstered by appointed Gender Equality Officers, will have clearly defined roles and

responsibilities, including the oversight of gender-related initiatives and monitoring of progress. These roles and the importance of their function will be communicated through regular institutional announcements and included in the strategic plan and budget, demonstrating to all stakeholders the depth of our commitment to gender equality.

Visibility of this commitment throughout the organization will be achieved by regular updates at staff meetings, articles in internal communication channels, and the celebration of milestones and successes. By making gender equality a prominent topic in these forums, UEFISCDI will ensure that the commitment is not only understood but is actively supported across all levels of the organization.

Reward allocation:

Our reward system will recognize and incentivize the efforts of those contributing to gender equality. Staff involved in gender equality measures will receive intrinsic rewards such as official acknowledgment in institutional publications and at public events, and potentially, reduced duties to allow them to focus more on these crucial tasks. Extrinsic rewards may include performance-based bonuses or additional professional development opportunities. This reward system is designed to acknowledge the importance of gender equality work and to encourage staff participation and initiative.

Diffusion:

The principles of gender equality will be disseminated across the organization through a series of planned interactions and engagements. This will include departmental meetings led by the Gender Equality Committee and Officers, where best practices will be shared and discussed. UEFISCDI will also establish a 'Gender Equality in Research' working group, with representatives from various departments, to ensure that the message is tailored and relevant across different organizational contexts. By leveraging internal networks and creating spaces for dialogue, UEFISCDI will promote a coherent and unified approach to gender equality across all departments

Sensing and calibration/Monitoring and evaluation:

Our dedicated monitoring and evaluation team will implement a gender-focused assessment tool, allowing us to gauge the effectiveness of our gender equality initiatives. UEFISCDI will conduct yearly reviews and adjust our strategies to ensure they remain aligned with our objectives and responsive to the needs of the research community.

Resistances

Main issue: One of the primary obstacles UEFISCDI anticipates, is the limited integration of gender perspectives in research proposals submitted for funding. Despite our efforts to promote gender equality through the GEP, there might be a persistent trend where researchers do not adequately address or incorporate gender dimensions in their research methodologies, objectives, or outcomes. This could be due to a lack of understanding or awareness of the importance of gender perspectives in research. For instance, a research proposal on urban development might overlook the different ways urban spaces impact men and women or fail to consider gender-specific needs and challenges. Cultural and Societal Norms: Deep-rooted cultural and societal norms might influence researchers' perspectives and approaches, leading to unconscious biases and a lack of gender sensitivity in research proposals and outcomes.

Strategy: UEFISCDI will deploy a combination of training workshops, awareness campaigns, and a gender-sensitive research proposal evaluation tool. For instance, UEFISCDI could introduce a tool that automatically scans research proposals for gender-specific keywords and suggests areas where gender perspectives can be integrated. By institutionalizing gender perspectives in research guidelines, continuously building capacity, and promoting awareness, UEFISCDI ensures that the importance of gender equality becomes ingrained in the research culture. Success factors include the active participation of researchers in training sessions, positive feedback from the research community, and an increase in research proposals that integrate gender perspectives. UEFISCDI Senior Management: Role: Their endorsement and support are vital for the successful implementation of any strategy. They have the authority to allocate resources, set organizational priorities, and influence the broader research community. Research Proposal Evaluation Committees: Role: These committees play a direct role in the selection of research projects for funding. Their understanding and appreciation of gender perspectives are crucial. They can ensure that proposals are evaluated not just on academic merit but also on their integration of gender perspectives. Communication and Public Relations Department: Role: This department can amplify the importance of gender perspectives through targeted communication campaigns, workshops, and publications. They can also highlight successful research projects that have effectively integrated gender perspectives. External Collaborators and Partner Institutions: Role: Collaborators can bring in diverse viewpoints and best practices from other institutions. Their support can enhance the quality of research and ensure that gender perspectives are considered from multiple angles.

3.8 Yasar University (RPO)

Institutional vision for Gender Equality for the upcoming two years:

The endeavors undertaken within the CALIPER project marked the initiation of Yasar University's inaugural generation of gender strategies. Over the next two years, our commitment extends to further institutionalizing these initiatives and fortifying the university's capacity. The specific objectives can be succinctly delineated as follows:

- **Boosting Female Enrolment in STEM Departments:** Concentrating efforts on enhancing female representation in STEM disciplines through the orchestration of high school outreach activities. By engaging with prospective students at this stage, YU aim to cultivate interest and encourage more women to pursue STEM education.
- **Dissemination of Gender Sensitivity and Sexual Harassment Regulations:** Widening the reach and awareness of the university's regulations pertaining to gender sensitivity and combating sexual harassment. Our aim is to foster a culture of understanding, respect, and intolerance for any form of harassment within the university community.
- **Augmenting Participation in CALIPER Training Programs:** Elevating the number of university staff who participate in the training initiatives developed within the CALIPER Project. By expanding the pool of trained individuals, YU seek to create a more informed and proactive community regarding gender-related issues.
- **Expanding National and International Networks:** Extending the university's networks in the realm of gender projects, both at the national and international levels. This expansion aims to facilitate collaboration, knowledge exchange, and participation in initiatives that promote gender equality on a broader scale.

- **Amplifying Gender-related Activities:** Increasing the frequency and diversity of activities dedicated to gender-related issues within the university. This encompasses seminars, workshops, and events that contribute to a richer discourse on gender equality and inclusivity.
- **Fostering Gender Research Hub Status:** Encouraging and supporting research endeavors on gender by leveraging both external and internal funding mechanisms. The goal is to position Yasar University as a prominent research hub at the national level, contributing significantly to the academic discourse on gender-related matters.

In aligning our efforts with these comprehensive objectives, Yasar University aspires not only to make substantial progress in gender equality but also to solidify its standing as a pioneering institution in fostering inclusivity, diversity, and cutting-edge research in this crucial domain.

Sustainability strategy

Socialisation:

The following strategies will be used to transmit the institution's vision, commitment, values and activities with respect gender equality to the internal stakeholders:

Yaşar University's internal communication channels such as internal mailing system and electronic document management system will be used. The information related to the institution's vision, commitment, values, and gender equality initiatives will be shared via these formal channels.

Furthermore; staff and student orientation and training programs will be used to transmit the information regarding the institution's commitment to gender equality.

Also, regular training sessions and workshops and seminars will be conducted to educate staff and faculty and to facilitate discussions and provide a deeper understanding of gender-related issues.

As for the External Stakeholders the following strategies will be used:

Publications and Reports: The institution's commitment to gender equality will be included in annual reports, promotional brochures, and other publications. Also, case studies and success stories will be published to highlight the positive impact of gender equality initiatives.

Institutional Websites and Social Media: The relevant sub-sections on the university's website that clearly outlines the institution's vision, values, and specific gender equality initiatives will be maintained and updated regularly. (<https://kalite.yasar.edu.tr/en/toplumsal-cinsiyet-esitligi-politikasi/> & <https://yugender.yasar.edu.tr/>)

The social media platforms of the University and YU Gender will be used to share updates, success stories, and events related to gender equality.

Collaborations and Partnerships: Yaşar University will continue to collaborate with external organizations and partners that share similar values regarding gender equality. Collaborative projects and activities will be conducted on gender-related issues.

Community Engagement activities such as outreach programs and events that focus on gender equality will be organized and external speakers and experts will be invited to share insights and best practices on gender-related issues.

By employing a combination of these strategies, Yaşar university will ensure the effective transmission of the information about its vision, commitment, values, and activities related to gender equality to both internal and external stakeholders, fostering a culture of inclusivity and transparency.

Transmitting information about the institution's vision, commitment, values, and activities related to gender equality to new staff is essential for fostering an inclusive environment. Yaşar University aims to effectively communicate its commitment to gender equality to new staff through a multi-faceted approach. This includes incorporating a dedicated session during the welcome day, featuring key speakers such as leaders of gender equality initiatives and university officials. Orientation materials, including welcome kits and employee handbooks, will integrate information on the institution's commitment to gender equality. Online platforms, such as the YU Gender website that features YU Gender Equality Plan (GEP) and social media, will also be used to engage and educate new staff. Training modules and workshops on gender equality topics will be integrated into the orientation program, and key personnel, including YU Gender Director will actively participate in these initiatives.

Commitment:

Ownership and engagement of employees and management were critical to the success of the CALIPER project at Yasar University. All GEP actions were carried out in close cooperation and with support from various departments at the institution. The general vision of the CALIPER project at Yasar University involved multi-level and multi-departmental collaboration. This aspect will be instrumental in gaining commitment to gender equality by employees and middle and upper management.

Towards the end of the project, the upper management changed. The current Rector and Vice-Rector for Academic Affairs are members of the Gender Equality Committee and Sustainability Committee. As members of the University Senate, they play a direct role in institutional decision-making. They will be the primary ambassadors for championing CALIPER values following the end of the project at the upper management level.

At the middle management level, the directors of the European Union Research Centre and the International Project Support Office are the coordinator and vice-coordinator of the CALIPER project. Together, they lead the university's international cooperation and research potential and will be instrumental in including gender dimension in funded projects and research. Other members of the Gender Equality Committee lead the Gender Equality Centre, Quality Coordinatorship, and Alumni Centre. They will lead communication and training activities and monitor and evaluate the institutional commitment to gender through gender-desegregated data collection.

The Human Resources Department has been a critical partner in CALIPER Project. In many activities in GEP, they provided research, data, and support for the project team. Throughout the run of the project, the Human Resources Policy has been revised to include gender equality as a priority. (<https://kalite.yasar.edu.tr/en/insan-kaynaklari-politikasi/>) As a part of the project, a gender research center was established. The center has a professor from the Faculty of Communications and a part-time gender

equality officer on staff, and it has been fully integrated into the organization's budget. The center oversees the implementation of the directive on gender-based discrimination, violence, and sexual harassment (<https://www.yasar.edu.tr/you-files/yonetmelik-yonerge/en/43793263208041071.pdf>) and the Discrimination, Gender Equality And Inclusion Policy (<https://kalite.yasar.edu.tr/en/toplumsal-cinsiyet-esitligi-politikasi/>).

Lastly, Yasar University has applied for the HRS4R award (The Human Resources Strategy for Researchers), a quality award given by the European Commission to institutions that implement the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers. The action plan created for the application includes various complementary activities already carried out in the CALIPER project and reinforces the institutional commitment to gender equality.

The visibility of institutional commitment to gender equality involves several departments. The leading department will be the Gender Equality Centre. As one of the many research centers at Yasar University, the Centre reports to the Vice-Rector for Research and Innovation. The heads of all research centers meet regularly to present research and impact activities. These meetings will align different research units regarding gender equality research and activities. In relation to this, the activities of the Centre for each academic year are planned before and reported to the upper management. The diversity of activities such as awareness raising, training in specific gender equality topics, and engagement with stakeholders will increase the variety of gender equality actions. Another factor that will increase the visibility of the institutional commitment is the regular gender equality awareness training sessions within the organization for administrative staff members. These sessions are now a regular part of the Human Resources Department's offerings and aim to increase staff members' awareness and knowledge of gender. Through the Mentorship Program created under the CALIPER Project framework, researchers who join the organization gain access to recordings of trainings on gender-sensitive human resources management, integrating gender dimension in teaching and research, and career management.

Reward allocation:

A range of intrinsic and extrinsic rewards is set to be implemented through the integration of gender strategies as a fundamental aspect of our university's operational structure. Concerning intrinsic rewards, acknowledgment and opportunities for skills enhancement and knowledge acquisition emerge as inherent motivators, leading to professional development. The introduction of training programs and workshops related to gender equality is positioned as a catalyst for personal and professional growth.

Participation in gender equality initiatives provides employees with an intrinsic reward, stemming from their contribution to a significant cause that goes beyond routine responsibilities, fostering a collective sense of purpose. Concurrently, this engagement enhances job satisfaction, correlating significantly with active contributions to a positive work environment and the promotion of inclusivity. The impact of this effect is emphasized when employees perceive tangible improvements resulting from their efforts. Ultimately, involvement in gender equality endeavours cultivates a sense of camaraderie and collaboration, generating an intrinsic motivational drive.

In the realm of extrinsic rewards, particular emphasis is given to the university's scientific research funding, underscoring its paramount importance. With gender prioritized in our university's strategic framework, projects related to gender will receive priority in funding allocations. In the upcoming strategic period,

discussions within the university administration contemplate the introduction of a distinguished "gender award" as part of the annual accolades conferred by the university. Additionally, the university's gender-focused centre is considering the establishment of a certification program referred to as the "gender sensitivity certificate." This certificate, bestowed upon staff actively involved in organizing events or developing initiatives related to gender issues, serves as a tangible extrinsic reward, symbolizing the institutional commitment to recognizing and incentivizing efforts that contribute to gender equity.

Diffusion:

Sustained involvement and leadership ownership, coupled with regular gender equality activities, will promote institutional change in the organization. By continuously implementing the Gender Equality Program (GEP), the organization will create a culture of gender equality, diversity, and inclusivity. This will be monitored through the review and revision of institutional policies such as HR Policy, and Gender Equality Policy. Human resources practices will also be assessed for inclusivity. Staff members will be regularly surveyed for additional and improved measures. Finally, collaborative projects and initiatives will be launched to engage other departments.

Sensing and calibration/Monitoring and evaluation:

Yaşar University has already established a monitoring and evaluation process by integrating gender-disaggregated data collection procedure into yearly reporting system. The data will be collected through involvement of various departments and relevant staff. The responsible departments include Women and Family Studies Application and Research Center, Directorate of Student Affairs, Human Resources Directorate, Vice Rectorate responsible for the Research and Innovation, Library and Information Center, Career and Alumni Center. All necessary human and financial resources will be provided by the relevant departments of the University.

The main department that will be responsible for ensuring the monitoring and evaluation of the implemented actions and their respective corrective measures will be Women and Family Studies Application and Research Center (YUGender). The Center team will analyse the data and propose respective corrective measures to the Rectorate.

Resistances

Main issue: YU might encounter some passive resistance towards achieving the long term target of "Gender balance in decision making processes". YU may encounter obstacle in the long-term target of "institutionalization of gender balance in decision making processes as a principle". Some of the members of the top management (e.g. members of board of trustees) might resist by not doing anything towards the achievement of this target or agreeing verbally but not following it through.

Strategy: The "networking and collaboration" approach within the institution to strengthen the position of the project and empower those who are committed to change will be deployed. Also, collaborative actions will be planned with other appropriate projects and Universities at national level. YU will also deploy networking approach at institutional level by establishing contacts with key persons and strategic units, and giving priority to reach people in different departments and those engaged in gender equality and building networks inside the organization. Ensuring the lasting change depends on the gaining support of the strategic actors such as members of top-level management and also engaging the relevant departments and staff members. Using the networking and collaboration strategy as well as creating the capacity for change through communication will ensure the engagement and lasting change in the end. The support of the gender equality office, senior or high management, human resources department and

middle managers and their engagement to the GEP activities are of great importance for the successful implementation of the GEP actions. Their role involves participation to the awareness raising activities and empowerment programme and also approval of the programmes & activities. **Error! Bookmark not defined.**

3.9 Salento University (RPO)

Institutional vision for Gender Equality for the upcoming two years:

The specific goals are the ones included in our GEP, which is valid till the 2025. UNILE list here in the following the main supported actions:

- Promotion of inclusive culture and practices in the academic community
- Promotion of gender diversity in the study of STEM disciplines
- Enhancement of gender diversity: actions to ensure the inclusion and well-being of male and female students
- Identification, development and implementation of actions aimed at work/life balance; valorisation of the individual worker's well-being also with regard to his/her care responsibilities
- Monitoring and coordination for gender equality assessment at institutional level
- Governance interventions to increase fair visibility and representativeness
- Actions for young female researchers to counter dispersion and career abandonment
- Support for equal opportunities in careers
- Enhancement of gender diversity in technical-administrative careers through seminars, training courses and reward systems
- Foster the integration of a gender dimension in research, teaching and third mission
- Relations with the territory and national and international actors; creation and strengthening of networks; funding, resources and planning
- Preventing and combating mobbing, harassment and discrimination, conflict phenomena and psychological distress that may arise in study and work relationships

Sustainability strategy

Socialisation:

- A) UNILE will strength all the activities with internal and external stakeholders, public engagement and social media supported dissemination of all the organized events, like for example University+ Gender Issues seminars, the Apulia Region-funded course against violence, and the "Protagonists" events in collaboration with the Provincial Superintendent of Studies of Lecce.
- B) The coordination group for GEP actions actuation and the monitoring and evaluation task force will be in place till the end of 2025. The group will support the revision of the actual GEP and the implementation of the new one.

Commitment:

- C) Structural changes and institutional awareness gained in the last few years are creating good foundation for continuity to the whole gender equality policy undertaken

Gender equality policies are included in the UniSalento strategic plan and in the sustainability plan of the whole university

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Reward allocation:

The staff involved in the process have no rewards due to the fact that they will be working on the implementation of the gender equality measures. Some funds are allocated for the implementation of the Gender Policy Vice-Rector activities.

Diffusion:

UNILE will continue in the organization of meeting and workshops, along with events like the ones reported above (see A) Meetings with key people might be beneficial to be described here.

Sensing and calibration/Monitoring and evaluation:

See point B) above

Resistances

Main issue: Change of University Governance could be a risk for the long term sustainability of GEP. Change of Regional and local administrations could also result in difference of support in GEP actuation.

Strategy: Networking and collaboration. Communication and dissemination at local, regional and national levels

4 Conclusion

The present deliverable aimed at developing a robust individual sustainability strategy for ensuring the continuity of the Gender Equality Plan (GEP)'s measures by the RPOs and RFOs involved in CALIPER. This document built upon the key policy insights on gender equality work at European level, the existing literature on the main success and hindering factors for sustaining the GE momentum within the institution and the institutionalisation of organisational changes, the *D5.1 Internal engagement and change management strategy guidelines*, the internal monitoring and evaluation reports of the partners' GEP measures and the workshops with internal and external stakeholders conducted by each CALIPER partners.

The present deliverable includes 9 individual sustainability strategies developed for each CALIPER partner ensuring the continuation of the gender equality work beyond the project lifecycle. From the strategies we can draw the conclusion that all the partners have an institutional vision for gender equality and are committed to continue the change effort towards gender equality. These visions indicatively span from providing equal opportunities for employees and students in achieving personal and professional development (see UZG FER) to the support of female researchers and the promotion of inclusive calls incorporating the gender dimension in research (see SNRSFG) and to the integration of the gender dimension in STEM research and teaching (see ULB). When it comes to the commitment, we see that the continuation of this effort is secured by the relevant gender equality bodies that have been created within the CALIPER project (see ECE NTUA and UZG FER) or when this is not the case this is secured by the amended job descriptions of the employees in order to perform relevant gender equality work within the institution (see SNRSFG). For the dissemination of the gender equality activities, relevant raising awareness sessions and other activities such as coffee talks are planned. Overall, most of the partners anticipate encountering some resistances however they have put in place a robust strategy for mitigating the impact of these resistances.

The promotion of gender equality is a long-term process and requires a careful analysis of the internal and external context of each organisation. Gender equality legislation, institutional procedures, starting points, internal support, existent gender equality structures and many other factors may differ between organisations. This is why a tailored approach has been followed in order each CALIPER partner to develop a context sensitive sustainability strategy ensuring the continuation of the gender equality work beyond the project duration.

Lastly, it should be noted that in most of the CALIPER partners the gender equality effort is sustained since:

- 2 inclusive GEPs (UNILE and UZG FER) continue their implementation because their overall duration exceeded the CALIPER project life cycle.
- 2 inclusive GEPs (by YU and IRB) have been updated after the 2nd iteration of the GEP implementation. Both GEPs are approved by their internal administration (for IRB it was not necessary for the updated GEP to undergo a new approval process).
- 4 new inclusive GEPs have been elaborated undergoing an internal approval process (ECE NTUA, SNRSFG, UEFISCDI, STU BA) since their duration ended within the project implementation. Three out of four GEPs have been approved. The last one is under the approval process.
- Parts of 1 inclusive GEP (ULB) that has been elaborated within the project implementation phase will be incorporated in the institutional overall Gender and Diversity Plan. The plan is under consultation.

This document is primarily addressed to the RPOs/RFOs involved in CALIPER to support the implementation and sustainability of the GEPs. It can also be used by other higher education and research institutions that desire to foster/sustain structural change for gender equality.

Apart from the individual sustainability strategy developed for each RPOs and RFOs involved in CALIPER ensuring the continuity of the project's outputs at partners level, it should be noted that the main outputs at project level namely the CALIPER [website](#), [the online repository of CALIPER partners GEP outputs](#), [the Policy briefs](#), [the CALIPER's role model videos](#) and the [CALIPER Charter](#) will be contributing to the envisaged pathway for expanding the project's impact after its completion.

In particular, the **CALIPER website** serving as a single entry point, to access all project outputs which have been used for the communication of the project's activities, and as it is easily identifiable by the target stakeholders, will remain active at least up to four years after the completion of the project.

With regards to the **online repository of CALIPER partners GEP outputs** will continue to be available on the project's website and be ready for uptake and use by the R&I community in Europe and beyond, as the legacy of the CALIPER. Parts of the available material are in partners native languages, enabling the material's uptake by non-English speakers, increasing the project's outreach. Partners with the help of VIL will keep updating/maintaining GEPs outputs at the project's website for further diffusion of knowledge on gender topics to R&I community.

The **three series of policy briefs (9 national and 1 EU)**, built on lessons learnt through the project, have been developed addressing policy makers at the European Union level and at the level of Member States and Associated Countries. These briefs offer specific recommendations supporting and further strengthening the capacity of the research, innovation and higher education community to work on setting up, implementing and monitoring a GEP. The briefs will be further communicated to relevant stakeholders upon the project's completion. They will be inserted in compelling templates and share via the project's social media accounts as well as partners' social media accounts.

The CALIPER's role model videos will be further disseminated by the project partners for greater engagement of girls and women in STEM fields and lastly the **CALIPER Charter** will be further promoted after the project's completion.

Lastly, through the project's various communication channels, visibility will be given to initiatives of other EU-funded projects working on gender equality in R&I. CALIPER has an already established wide network of [sister projects](#). It is necessary that this be updated after the project's completion. This will be achieved by the continuous update of the project's website based on the information received from additional sister projects. Additional activities will include the promotion of relevant events organised for the R&I community on relevant gender topics by the community of sister projects, made available via the project's social media accounts and website.

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Annex II: Sustainability strategy template

- Institutional vision for Gender Equality for the upcoming two years:

Please describe the specific goals you would like to achieve in the upcoming two year i.e. more women in managerial positions or attract more female students in STEM faculties or make your institutions an institution with zero tolerance to incidence of sexual harassment etc. Please be as concrete as possible. You can also describe the most pressing issues you would like to tackle in the future.

- Sustainability strategy

Socialisation:

- **How are you going to transmit relevant information such as your vision, the institution's commitment, values and activities with respect gender equality to the internal and external stakeholders in the upcoming two years?** You can describe upcoming meetings with internal and external stakeholders in the upcoming two years (for example the organisation of similar meetings like the online awareness sessions you organised under t5.3 to give more info to the internal stakeholders with regards to the GEPs implementation). The re-organisation of the win event can be also an option or similar events. You can mention also the collaborative actions you foresee with your r&I hub
- **How will you make sure that this information is going to be transmitted to new staff of your institution?** You can describe how you are going to manage info on your GEP website and social media. You can present a planning or the personnel to be involved. You can mention potentially at the welcome day of new staff/students there will be a dedicated topic.

Commitment:

- **How do you plan to gain recommitment to gender equality by employees and middle and upper management?** Here for example you can mention any change you have achieved ie in HR job description now there is relevant point on working with gender equality data. You can mention also your gender equality committee/gender equality officer that have been established/hired by mentioning their specific role within the organisation. In addition, you can mention if any of the activities became part of the overall strategic plan of the institutions or they have been integrated to the overall budget of the organisation
- **How it will be visible to the entire organisation this commitment?** Here you can mention any meetings or communication activities you plan to organise for making this visible.

Reward allocation:

- **Which are the intrinsic and extrinsic rewards that the involved employed will get for being involved in the change effort towards gender equality?** Here you can mention if the staff involved in the process have less duties from their other tasks due to the fact that they will be working on the implementation of the gender equality measures. You can mention any other financial rewards that might be linked to performing any gender equality work.

Diffusion:

- **How do you plan to diffuse the change in other departments or the entire organisations?** Meetings with key people might be beneficial to be described here.

Sensing and calibration/Monitoring and evaluation:

Have you established a monitoring and evaluation process for the upcoming years? Who is involved? What kind of resources are dedicated to this? Please describe how will you ensure the monitoring and evaluation of the implemented actions and their respective corrective measures.

Resistances

Main issue: Since its the third GEP of the IRB, we do not expect a mayor resistance moving forward, nevertheless, one of the obstacles that we may face is the implementation of topics that are not yet fully implemented like the integration of gender dimensions into research, and accomplishing gender balance on decision making bodies at the Institute. The obstacles mentioned, only involve a certain part of the GEP, meaning it will not fully impact on the progression and success of the GEP. Its a work in progress to be improved as the actions are implemented.

Strategy: Follow GEP Objectives. Participation in best practices groups, Sharing information with key internal stakeholders, planning awareness sessions at the Institute.

Annex III: Sustainability workshops with internal and external stakeholders

III.1 University of Zagreb – Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing (RPO)

Sustainability workshop with internal stakeholders:

The sustainability workshop was organized at the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing of University of Zagreb on December 2nd 2022 targeting internal stakeholders to reflect on results from the formative evaluation, and constitute a first step for the preparation of the GEP's sustainability plan. The relevant report can be found below. The relevant slides can be found here: <https://twk.pm/mowyecesxu>

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker
10:00 – 10:05	Introduction	Caliper project lead
Discussion		
10:05 – 10:25	Institutional governance	
10:25 – 10:45	Human resources	
10:45 – 11:05	Institutional communication	
11:05 – 11:25	Teaching & research	
11:25 – 11:45	Student services	
11:45 – 12:00	Conclusions and closing	

Participants' list

No	Type of stakeholder	Gender
1	Professor, Head of Department	M
2	Professors, Head of Committee	F
3	Head of Office, Secretary office	F
4	Professor, ex vice dean	M
5	Professor, Caliper project lead	F
6	Professor, ex dean	M
7	Head of Office, Student Services Office	F

Description the outcomes

The sustainability workshop was organized with the members of the Gender equality working group. The project lead of Caliper presented the implemented activities of the institutional Gender equality plan that were the subject of the formative evaluation. Actions were presented per thematic areas: institutional governance, human resources, institutional communication, teaching, research and student services. For each area, sustainable long-term activities were discussed. The following sustainable activities per thematic area were foreseen.

Institutional governance

Faculty will establish a permanent committee for gender equality by the end of 2023.

Basic guidelines:

- committee will act in accordance with the Gender Equality Plan
- attention should be given to inclusivity and representation of various groups in the membership (departments, professors, assistants, students, services, management)
- committee will prepare a report about GE activities and adopt a new GEP every two years
- secure formalized support/participation/management by one member of the faculty management
- secure formalized support/participation/consultation from one specially assigned member of the administration
- define budget and involvement of faculty offices in the implementation of activities

Human Resources

- Sustainable activities: based on collected data and analysis committee can make recommendations based (recommendations for supporting researchers after maternity leave, recommendations for attracting and retaining female researchers)
- Responsibility: Committee, Vice Dean for Research, Human Resources Office

Institutional Communication

- Sustainable activities: promotion of female researchers by organizing of one lecture per year together with the IEEE WIE / Alumni Club
- Time frame: December
- Responsibility: Committee, Vice Dean for Research

Teaching

- Sustainable activities: organization of two three-hour workshops where teachers would work on the development of their courses, the principle of exchange of experiences of FER teachers (mutual learning)
- Time frame: February, between two semesters, each year
- Responsibility: Committee, Vice Dean for Teaching, Committee for Undergraduate and Graduate Studies, Committee for Doctoral Studies

Research

- Sustainable activities: organization of one three-hour workshop to support the writing of project proposals, where researchers would integrate the dimension of gender in their project proposals
- Time frame: February every year
- Responsibility: Committee, Vice Dean for Research

Student Services

- Sustainable activities: promotional activities to attract future female students
- Time frame: November every year
- Responsibility: Committee, Vice Dean for Students

External stakeholders

- Include external stakeholders when possible: promotional activities, research, student services.

Intersectionality

- The committee should facilitate equal opportunity for everyone. Find members which can contribute to intersectionality.

Actions discussed:

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Gender equality committee	Institutional governance	Faculty will establish a permanent committee for gender equality by the end of 2023.	Time frame: Committee will be established by the end of 2023 and will work permanently Personnel: Faculty Management, Faculty Council	Establishment of the GEP, regular reporting, actions executed	Permanent	Faculty Management, Faculty Council	Permanent commitment and improvement of the institutional gender equality
2	Career support for female researcher	Human Resources	Based on collected data and analysis committee for gender equality can make recommendations based (recommendations for supporting researchers after maternity leave, recommendations for	Time frame: Each 2 years after the publication of GE report Personnel: Committee, Vice Dean for Research,	Published report on the state of GE at the institution Published new GEP with actions developed on	Biannually	Management: Vice Dean for Research Organization: Committee for gender equality,	Permanent commitment and improvement of the institutional gender equality

			attracting and retaining female researchers)	Human Resources Office	the basis of the analysis			
3	Promotion of female researchers	Institutional Communication	Promotion of female researchers by organizing of one lecture per year together with the IEEE WIE / Alumni Club	Time frame: December every year Personnel: Committee for gender equality, Vice Dean for Research	Number of participants / streams	Annually in December	Management: Vice Dean for Research Organization: Committee for gender equality, Public Relations office	Better visibility of female researchers
4	Workshops for gender mainstreaming in teaching	Teaching	Organization of two three-hour workshops where teachers would work on the development of their courses, the principle of exchange of experiences of FER teachers (mutual learning)	Time frame: February, between two semesters, each year Personnel: Committee for gender equality, Vice Dean for Teaching,	Number of participants in the workshops, number of courses with GE dimension	Annually in February	Management: Vice Dean for Teaching Organization: Committee for gender equality, Committee for Undergraduate and Graduate Studies, Committee for Doctoral Studies	More courses with gender dimension

5	Workshops for gender mainstreaming in research	Research	Organization of workshop to support the writing of project proposals, where researchers would integrate the dimension of gender in their project proposals	Personnel: Committee for gender equality, Vice Dean for Research, Workshop leader Timeline: February every year	Number of participants, number of research proposals	Annually in February	Management: Vice Dean for Research Organization: Committee for gender equality	More projects with a gender dimension
6	Promotional activities to attract future female students	Student Services	Workshops and events organized for female high school students	Personnel: Committee for gender equality, Vice Dean for Students Timeline: November every year for Open Day	Number of students who participated, number of employees involved	Annually in winter semester	Management: Vice Dean for Students Organization: Committee for gender equality	Regularly organized events to attract female students

Table 1 UZG – Actions discussed with internal stakeholders

Sustainability workshop with external stakeholders:

The GEP elaborated by the Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing of the University of Zagreb in Croatia (FER UZG) has been officially approved by the decision-making bodies of the Faculty for the period **2021 – 2025**. The procedure of approval of the Gender Equality Plan underwent two main steps:

1. approval from the Dean,
2. approval from the Faculty Council.

The Faculty Council of UZG-FER established Equal Opportunities Committee, a permanent body with the responsibility of implementation of GEP activities. After the implementation of the current GEP, Equal Opportunities Committee will design a new GEP, this process will start in the second half of 2024. After the end of the Caliper project, the Equal Opportunities Committee will continue with the implementation of all activities from the current GEP. Therefore, here we list only collaborative actions to be sustained.

No	Name of the action	The thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action.	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	External stakeholders involved	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Attracting new female students to the Faculty	Student Services	Production of podcast ŽensCast through which we introduce to the future students women who started their professional career at UZG-FER. Through their professional experiences, we want to invite and encourage female students to study at FER.	Personnel: 2 professors Budget: 200€ for the tool for registration of episodes Timeline: 2 episodes per year	1. Number of episodes 2. Number of views	Choice of guests of podcast and production of episode twice a year (annually in January and October)	Women in Engineering IEEE	Equal Opportunities Committee	2 episodes of the podcast annually

Table 2 UZG – Collaborative action to be sustained after the project completion

Agenda

- Overview of the GEP activities
- Overview on the jointly conducted activities (ŽensCast)
- Agreement of the possibilities for continuation of collaboration

No	Name of the organisation	Type of stakeholder	Gender
1	Women in Engineering IEEE	Civil society (excluding feminist NGOs)	F

Description the outcomes:

UZG-FER and Women in Engineering IEEE have been collaborating since 2020 on production of the podcast ŽensCast (https://www.fer.unizg.hr/equal_opportunities/students) through which we introduce to the future students women who started their professional career at UZG-FER. The aim is to give visibility to invite and encourage female students to study at FER. So far 7 episodes have been produced and we will continue this collaboration. The plan is to continue to produce two episodes annually.

We will continue to collaborate in the same pace, producing two episodes annually, in January (to mark the International Day of Women and Girls in Science on February 11) and November (to present to students visiting UZG-FER on the occasion of Open Day of UZG-FER held first Saturday after November 25).

Strenghts:

- The main strength is that this is an established collaboration and both institutions have benefited from it.
- Each video had over 200 views, so there is an audience for the podcast.

Weaknesses:

- Lack of resources and limited knowledge in video editing.

Opportunities:

- Opportunity to attract new female students at UZG-FER and new members of the professional organization Women in Engineering IEEE

Threats:

- Lack of time

In May 2023 we held 3rd awareness raising session at UZG-FER in which occasion we presented to the R&I Hub accomplishments in the implementation of GEP. In addition, options for collaborative actions were explored. Members of the HUB deeply support the efforts of UZG-FER in the implementation of GEP and are interested in the continuation of our collaboration. However, they are unable to plan dedicated human or financial resources for collaborative activities. They remain open to continuation of communication, exchange of experiences and best practices when the actions match both institutional goals.

In August 2023, follow up brief meetings with the following R&I Hub members were held where they confirmed openness for collaborative actions in the future, even though currently cannot bind themselves to provide financial and human resources.

No	Name of the organization	Type of stakeholder	Gender
2	University of Zagreb, Faculty of Science	Academic and research institutions	F
1	University of Zagreb, Center for Cultural Studies	Academic and research institutions	F

2	CROZ	Industry	F
1	ERICSSON NIKOLA TESLA	Industry	F
1	Gideon bros	Industry	F
2	Algebra	Academic and research institutions	F
1	Q Agency	Industry	F
1	V. Gymnasium, Zagreb	Public institution	F
1	Zagreb University of Applied Science	Academic and research institutions	F

At the meeting of Equal Opportunities Committee in October 2023, it was discussed about possible collaborative actions that do not require overwhelming financial and human resources from the R&I Hub, and that also benefit all partners. The discussion was focused on organization of new WIN event in 2024 in collaboration with R&I Hub, since their feedback was very positive in the occasion of FER WIN 2022. It was concluded that the Committee will have to make all the organizational efforts and invite R&I hubs as speakers and participants in the panels, as in 2022.

Strengths:

- Established collaboration
- Public events such as WIN benefit UZG-FER to raise awareness on its gender equality efforts and help industry players to attract new female employees

Weaknesses:

- Lack of time from the R&I hub for in depth planning of the event

Opportunities:

- Opportunity to promote professional women in ICT and electrical engineering

Threats:

- Small audience for the event

III.2 Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia (RFO)

Sustainability workshop with internal stakeholders:

The workshop was organized on 6th of December via zoom platform

Agenda: Agenda consisted of 2 parts. The first section included the presentation with review of GEP activities/ results of formative evaluation for the 1st implementation phase and the second section of the workshop included the round table with 2 discussions phases.

14:30 - 14:40 Welcome speech, introduction

All participants will have the opportunity to check their headphones and microphone

14:40 – 15:00 Presentation

Overview of the results of the first implementation phase and interim formative evaluation

15:00 – 16:15 Round table - 1 phase

Discussion on the GEP actions by area of intervention

16:15 – 16:45 Round table - 2 phase

Discussion on cross-cutting aspects to all areas

16:45 – 17:00 Summary

Participants' list

No	Type of stakeholder * (see table below)	Gender
1	CALIPER working group	F-7 M-1
2	Management	F-1
3	Public Relations / Communications office	F-2
4	Other	F-7 M-3

Description the outcomes:

During the workshop, in the first phase of the round-table all areas of intervention were discussed according to the framework-table with the dimensions (institutionalization/expansion/resources/gender knowledge and expertise) provided in the guidelines. Most of areas shared the similar responses and results according to the different dimensions. For example, for most of areas in case of resources dimension it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources will be required after the project conclusion. Also, similar suggestions were mentioned in case of gender knowledge dimension. After the project finalization there could be a necessity for additional gender expertise/knowledge.

During the second phase of the round-table cross-cutting issues were discussed. The participants of the workshop agreed that all discussed actions worth prioritizing for being sustainably continued. Besides that, some actions are already implemented on the structural level. Main concerns were related to the continuation of the monitoring of the GEP actions after the end of the project. Participants agreed that making GEP monitoring mechanism sustainable is not an easy and will require allocation of additional resources in the future. Regarding the R&I Hub's role in the sustainability plan and roadmap of the collaborative actions, participants of the workshop mentioned that external stakeholders were involved in different actions and also are interested in future collaborations. One of the ways for future sustainability can be systematic collaboration and communication on different issues and organization of joint workshops and conferences.

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Training for the staff involved in recruitment process	Human Resources	The action was finalized in the first iteration and there was no need to continue it in the second iteration, however, it could be still necessary to be reimplemented in the future.	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary in case of reimplementation of the action.	Number of training and staff participated in training	October 2021- March 2022	Office of International Relations and fundraising, Law and Administration Department	Organization of the training for staff
2	Informational brochure/guide to recruited staff about gender equality	Human Resources	The action was already implemented as structural one during the first iteration	No need for additional resources	Number of staff informed	November 2021	Office of International Relations and fundraising, Law and Administration Department, PR Office	Elaborated informational brochure/guide
3	Development of exit questionnaire for staff	Human Resources	The action was already implemented as structural one during the first iteration, however, is still ongoing in the second iteration since the additional data for	No need for additional resources	Number of questionnaires filled	December 2021 - August 2023	Office of International Relations and fundraising, Law and Administration Department	Creation and provision of exit questionnaire for staff

			monitoring should be gathered.					
4	Training and other activities improving professional skills of staff	Human Resources	The action was prolonged to the second iteration with the similar steps and activities.	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary	Number of training	October 2021-August 2023	Office of International Relations and fundraising, Law and Administration Department	Organization and provision of the training
5	Collecting gender disaggregated data on the organization institutional level	Institutional Governance	The action was already implemented as structural one during the first iteration	No need for additional resources	Comprehensive gender disaggregated data collected and regularly updated inside the organization	October 2021	Office of International Relations and fundraising, Law and Administration Department	Collected gender disaggregated data
6	Modifying existing job descriptions in the administration unit of SRNSFG, by adding targeted functions towards gender related issues in the organization	Institutional Governance	The action was already implemented as structural one during the first iteration	No need for additional resources	Number of targeted staff members of SRNSFG with modified job description towards gender issues in the organization	September, 2021	Office of International Relations and fundraising, Law and Administration Department	Amended job description/s and defined targeted functions

7	Gather disaggregated data by gender in conjunction with ethnicity, gender identity, age, disability, religion, etc.	Institutional Governance	The action was already implemented as structural one during the first iteration	No need for additional resources	Reporting system of disaggregated data collection is in place	December, 2021-June, 2022	Law and Administration Department, PR Office	Systematically gathered disaggregated data by gender in conjunction with ethnicity, gender identity, age, disability, religion, etc.
8	Elaborate a strategic plan encompassing measures/actions related to the institutional communication enhancement on the matter of gender equality	Institutional Communication	Systematic update of the strategic plan	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary	Elaborated special strategic plan document	September, 2021 – August, 2023	Office of International Relations and fundraising, PR Office	Elaborated and implemented strategic plan
9	Creation of a special section on the SRNSFG website revealing successful	Institutional Communication	The action was already implemented during the first iteration – the website section was created; however, the information should be systematically updated	No need for additional resources	Number of published information, interviews on webpage	September, 2021 – August, 2023	Office of International Relations and fundraising, PR Office	Refined SRNSFG website by creating a special section and systematically

	Georgian women in STEM/research and sharing the information related to women for their popularisation							published information
10	Organize with joint efforts special targeted events, conference, symposia, e.g. in the frame of “Science Fest”, one conference dedicated for Georgian Female Researchers	Institutional Communication	Organization of the special targeted events in the future	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary	Number of implemented activities	September, 2021 – August, 2023	Office of International Relations and fundraising, PR Office	Organized targeted events
11	Engagement in the creation of Gender mainstreaming platform	Institutional Communication	Participation in special targeted events - conferences, workshops, webinars	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget)	Number of events	September, 2022- August, 2023	Office of International Relations and fundraising, PR Office	Created Gender mainstreaming platform

				will be necessary				
12	Checking the existence of gender balance in research teams at the project registration stage	Research Funding	The implementation of the action was prolonged to the second iteration with the similar steps and activities.	No need for additional resources	Number of research projects where gender balance will be maintained	December, 2021 – August, 2023	Science Department, Law and Administration Department, Office of Science Popularization	Created gender balance control mechanism in scientific teams at the project registration stage
13	Establishing award for women scientists	Research Funding	The implementation of the action was prolonged to the second iteration with the similar steps and activities.	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary	Number of submitted proposals and winners' projects	January, 2022 – August, 2023	Science Department, Law and Administration Department, Office of Science Popularization	Established award for women scientists
14	Providing evaluators/committee members gender related guidelines	Research Funding	The implementation of the action was prolonged to the second iteration with the similar steps and activities.	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary	Number of guidelines and training	September, 2021 – August, 2023	Science Department, Law and Administration Department, Office of Science Popularization	Created specific guidelines and training materials
15	Adopt a Sexual Harassment Policy	Sexual Harassment	The action was already implemented as structural one during the first iteration, however the policy can be updated in the future in case of necessity	No need for additional resources	Number of elaborated policies	January, 2022 - March, 2022	Law and Administration Department	Developed a written policy prohibiting discrimination on any ground and harassment in

								any form including sexual harassment
16	Establish a mechanism for reporting	Sexual Harassment	The action was already implemented as structural one during the first iteration	No need for additional resources	Number of individuals to whom an employee of the foundation may make a complaint	January, 2022 - March, 2022	Law and Administration Department	Established reporting mechanism
17	WIN event	Transfer to Market	The implementation of the action was prolonged to the second iteration with the similar steps and activities.	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary	Number of organized workshops/conferences	October, 2021 - August, 2023	Office of International Relations and Fundraising, Science Department, Office of Science Popularization	Organized workshops/conferences

Table 3 SNRSFG – Actions discussed with internal stakeholders

Conclusions and next steps

During the workshop as potential resistances were identified resistances coming on individual level and related to concerns regarding the necessities of implementation of particular activities. As facilitating factors, the participants mentioned that the previous experience from first iteration in case of some actions can be useful.

First workshop was organized targeting internal stakeholders to reflect on results from the formative evaluation and as a first step for the preparation of the GEP’s sustainability plan.

During the workshop different actions were reviewed and sustainability of some GEP measures and procedures were discussed at this stage of the project for the further development and implementation of the sustainability plan. Besides that, participants overviewed the future necessities and potential upcoming efforts and activities.

As next step the organization of the second workshop focusing on gathering external stakeholders is planned in Spring 2023.

Photos:

Picture 1 SNRSFG Pictures from workshop with internal stakeholders

Sustainability workshop with external stakeholders:

Agenda

The workshop was organized on 5th of October at Shota Rustaveli National Science Foundation of Georgia. As the workshop was organized onsite it was decided to organize one workshop instead of multiple ones. The Agenda consisted of 3 main parts. The first section included the presentation with overview of CALIPER project/GEP activities/ main progress and results of the implementation. The second section of the workshop included SWOT analysis and the third section included discussion round table on the collaborative actions and proposal of the new actions for the new GEP version.

Participants list

No	Name of the organization	Type of stakeholder * (see table below)	Gender
1	Tbilisi State University	Academic and research institutions	Female

2	Tbilisi State University	Academic and research institutions	Female
3	Tbilisi State University	Academic and research institutions	Female
4	Tbilisi State University	Academic and research institutions	Female
5	Georgian Technical University	Academic and research institutions	Female
6	Georgian Technical University	Academic and research institutions	Female
7	Georgian Technical University	Academic and research institutions	Female
8	Georgian Technical University	Academic and research institutions	Female
9	Georgian Technical University	Academic and research institutions	Female
10	David Aghmashenebeli University of Georgia	Academic and research institutions	Female
11	Tbilisi State Medical University	Academic and research institutions	Female
12	National Centre of Manuscripts	Academic and research institutions	Female
13	Agricultural University	Academic and research institutions	Female
14	Agricultural University	Academic and research institutions	Female
15	UN Women	Civil society	Female
16	Ivane Beritashvili Center of Experimental Biomedicine	Academic and research institutions	Female
17	Alte University	Academic and research institutions	Female
18	SRNSFG	Public sector	Female
19	SRNSFG	Public sector	Female
20	SRNSFG	Public sector	Female
21	SRNSFG	Public sector	Female
22	SRNSFG	Public sector	Female
23	SRNSFG	Public sector	Female
24	SRNSFG	Public sector	Female
25	SRNSFG	Public sector	Female

Description the outcomes:

The first part of the workshop included a presentation regarding the CALIPER project and GEP activities. During the workshop, GEP actions were discussed according to instructions provided in the guidelines. Most of areas shared the similar responses and results according to the different dimensions.

During the second phase of the round-table cross-cutting issues were discussed. The participants of the workshop agreed that all discussed actions worth prioritizing for being sustainably continued. Besides that, some new actions were identified and also potential suggestions for future collaborations. During the

workshop participants emphasized that external stakeholders were involved in different actions and also are interested in future collaborations. One of the ways for future sustainability can be systematic collaboration and communication on different issues and organization of joint workshops and conferences.

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Indicate "YES" if it is a new emerged collaboration	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	External stakeholders involved	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Organize with joint efforts special targeted events, conference, symposia, e.g. in the frame of "Science Fest", one conference dedicated for Georgian Female Researchers	Institutional Communication		Organization of the special targeted events in the future	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary	Number of implemented activities	September, 2021 – New GEP	R&I hubs	Office of International Relations and fundraising, PR Office	Organized targeted events
2	Engagement in the creation of Gender mainstreaming platform	Institutional Communication		Participation in special targeted events - conferences, workshops, webinars	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation	Number of events	September, 2022- New GEP	Ministry, UN Women	Office of International Relations and fundraising, PR Office	Created Gender mainstreaming platform

					of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary					
3	Establishing award for women scientists	Research Funding		The implementation of the action was prolonged to the implementation period of the new GEP with the similar steps and activities.	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary	Number of submitted proposals and winners' projects	January, 2022 – New GEP	R&I hubs	Science Department, Law and Administration Department, Office of Science Popularization	Award for women scientists
4	WIN event	Transfer to Market		The implementation of the action was prolonged to the implementation period of the new GEP with the similar steps and activities.	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary	Number of organized workshops/conferences	October, 2021 - August, 2023	R&I hubs	Office of International Relations and Fundraising, Science Department, Office of Science Popularization	Organized workshops/conferences

5	Special target call on gender research	Research funding	Yes	The implementation of the action will include preparation of call documentation, internal and external discussions, call announcement.	Not exact figures were identified during the workshop, but it was mentioned that allocation of additional resources (personnel, budget) will be necessary	Number of announced calls	New GEP	R&I hubs	Office of International Relations and Fundraising, Science Department, Office of Science Popularization	Announced target call
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Table 4 SNRSFG – Actions discussed with external stakeholders

SWOT analysis:

<p>A. Strengths</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Raising awareness • Breaking the stereotypes • Financial support • Motivation of career development 	<p>B. Weaknesses</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of human resources • Lack of financial resources
<p>D. Opportunities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordination • Intersectionality • Integration • Call for women • Popularization of gender aspects in different fields 	<p>C. Threats</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low level of acceptance

Conclusions and next steps

Second workshop was targeting to gather external stakeholders to receive their feedback and to explore/define their potential role in the sustainability plan. During the workshop different actions were reviewed and sustainability of some GEP measures and procedures were discussed for the further development and implementation of the sustainability plan. Besides that, participants discussed the future necessities and overviewed potential upcoming activities and events.

Photos

Picture 2 SNRSFG Pictures from workshop with internal stakeholders

Actions to be sustained:

No	Name of the action	Thematic area
1	Organize with joint efforts special targeted events, conference, symposia, e.g. in the frame of “Science Fest”, one conference dedicated for Georgian Female Researchers	Institutional Communication
2	Engagement in the creation of Gender mainstreaming platform	Institutional Communication
3	Establishing award for women scientists	Research Funding

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

4	WIN event	Transfer to Market
5	Special target call on gender research	Research funding

Table 5 SNRSFG Collaborative actions to be sustained after the project's completion

III.3 Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava (RPO)

Sustainability workshop with internal stakeholders:

On November 30, 2022, a workshop focused on internal stakeholders was held at the Faculty of Material Science and Technology in Trnava, STU. The workshop was organized in a hybrid form (primarily onsite), where 2 participants were presented online.

Program:	1. Opening
	2. Current status of project activities
	3. Presentation of the results of GEP implementation
	4. STU Action Plan
	5. Round Table
	6. Summarization of inputs and conclusion

Audience:

4	Dean and vicedeans	F 2	M 2
5	Middle management positions	F 3	M 2
2	Researchers	F 1	M 1
5	Caliper team	F 5	M 0
1	PhD student	F 1	M 0
1	Technical staff	F 0	M 1

The workshop was organized in accordance with the sustainability requirements of the created GEP. The 1st goal was to present the success of the implementation of GEP activities within the 1st phase. The purpose of the meeting was to present the current status of project activities and at the same time to present information on the implementation of GEP activities. The composition of the participants was chosen in such a way that all levels of vertical management were included, as well as in terms of equal representation of the academic and administrative part of internal stakeholders. In the matter of institutionalization, we invited a representative for gender equality at STU, who presented the STU Action Plan. Based on this, meetings were arranged between the management of the STU MTF and the persons responsible for the implementation of the gender equality strategy at STU. The 2nd goal of the meeting was to set up the sustainability plan of GE at MT STU. The main step has been already done by establishing of the Council for GE as the implementation of GEP action. The meeting was also attended by members of this council. Its task will be to continue the sustainability of the issue of gender equality at the faculty after the end of the project implementation period.

A consistent output for the needs of sustainability was to focus on PR activities towards students in order to support the study of a technical studies, support researchers in the field of submitting project proposals containing a gender dimension, integrating gender issues into teaching and increasing the quality of internal

communication by integrating gender-sensitive language. Sustainability is supported by the commitment of the Council for Gender Equality to provide a methodical and control system that will ensure, by raising awareness, the natural acceptance of the gender dimension in the working environment of employees, students and the HUB environment.

Commitment of the Council of GE towards activities and competences:

- to manage the activities of the Council for Gender Equality (hereinafter referred to as "the Council")
- to ensure the coordinated implementation of the GEP
- to submit proposals for modification of the GEP in the form of amendments for approval to the management of the MTF STU and create documents related to its implementation
- be responsible for the monitoring and evaluation of the GEP
- to ensure communication and sustainability of GEP
- to ensure communication and counseling with other faculties, or by the rectorate of STU (university council)
- to communicate and integrate the policy of diversity, inclusion and gender equality across the entire faculty in teaching, research and employment
- to communicate and integrate the policy of diversity, inclusion and gender equality towards the external environment
- to identify and remove barriers to fulfilling the principles of equal opportunities and gender equality
- to present to the management of the faculty a report on the activity of the Council as of 31.12. of the given year
- Another commitment is reducing resistance to GEP implementation through communication skills.

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Council for Gender equality	Institutional Governance	The council is officially established under the auspices of the dean of the faculty with designated representatives of strategic management positions and faculty workplaces.	Personnel: representatives are appointed from the faculty's internal staff Budget: faculty Timeline: the time limit was not set, which means that the council is a regular executive body of the faculty regarding the application of gender issues	regular meetings to check the application of internal standards on gender issues	the council is already organized during the implementation of the project	all strategic positions of teaching, research, administration, student service and faculty management	active management and provision of assistance in the matter of gender issues at the level of management, internal communication, transfer of information to the market and in relation to students
2	The usage of personnel documentation using gender-sensitive language	Human Resources	As part of the implementation of the GEP, gender-sensitive documents were created, which will continue to be used and which are a model and an incentive for the creation of further documentation in	Personnel: Staff of HR department Budget: faculty Timeline: sustainability perspective	qualitative position of implementation	It has been already organized during the implementation of the project	HR department	raising awareness and sustainability of a gender-balanced working environment at a qualitative level

			the field of human resources management					
3	Programs for employees' reintegration	Human Resources	Use of these programs at the level of individual workplaces of the faculty.	Personnel: Staff of HR department Budget: faculty Timeline: sustainability perspective	Nr. of successful reintegrations.	09/2023	HR department	raising awareness and sustainability of a gender-balanced working environment at a qualitative level
4	PR actions	Institutional Communication	The gender issue is implemented in all PR activities of the faculty in order to reach potential students. Efforts are directed mainly at potential female students in order to increase their number in technical fields of study.	Personnel: PR department Budget: faculty Timeline: sustainability perspective	Increasing Nr. of girls studying the technical studies.	It has been already organized during the implementation of the project	PR department Faculty Management Institutes' Directors	raising awareness, increase in the number of students (female), increase in the number of researchers (female)
5	Implementation of the gender dimension in project proposals	Research	The Department for International Projects is an advisory body for monitoring the fulfillment of grant scheme criteria, which will provide advice on issues of implementing gender equality in the project proposal, including project staffing.	Personnel: Department for International Project Budget: faculty Timeline: sustainability perspective	Nr. of project proposals respecting gender equity	It has been already organized during the implementation of the project	Researchers	raising awareness and sustainability of a gender-balanced working research environment at a qualitative level
6	Integration of gender in the curriculum	Teaching	Raising awareness sustainability activities within the internal communication lead by the Council for Gender equality.	Personnel: Council for GE Budget: faculty Timeline: sustainability perspective	Nr. of curriculum respecting gender equality.	It has been already organized during the implementation of the project	Teachers, Researchers	raising awareness and sustainability of a gender-balanced working research environment at a qualitative level
7	Supporting all academics in technology transfer	Transfer to Market	Raising awareness sustainability activities within the internal communication lead by the Council for Gender equality.	Personnel: Council for GE Budget: faculty Timeline: sustainability perspective	qualitative position of implementation	It has been already organized during the implementation of the project	Researchers	raising awareness and sustainability of a gender-balanced working research environment at a qualitative level
8	Open days, information panels	Student Services	Raising awareness sustainability activities within the communication with students.	Personnel: Students Services department Budget: faculty Timeline: sustainability perspective	Nr. of actions	It has been already organized during the implementation of the project	Students Services department, Teachers, Researchers, Faculty management	raising awareness and sustainability of a gender-balanced working research environment at a qualitative level

Table 6 STUBA Actions discussed with internal stakeholders

Sustainability workshops with external stakeholders

1.st Report: Meeting held dated 27.09.2023

Agenda:

- 1) Introduction – information about completed GEP actions
- 2) Presentation of areas of cooperation
- 3) Brainstorming
- 4) Conclusions

Participants list

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

No	Name of the organization	Type of stakeholder * (see table below)	Gender
1.	Nemocnica Bory	Industry	M
2.	Technical University of Kosice	Academia	F
3.	Tomas Bata University of Zlin	Academia	M
4.	ZF a.s.	Industry	M
5.	MTF STU	Academia	M
6.	MTF STU	Academia	F
7.	MTF STU	Academia	F
8.	MTF STU	Academia	M

Description the outcomes:

The meeting was held online (Google Meet) on September 27, 2023, at 3:00 p.m., lasting approximately 90 minutes. The meeting was aimed at establishing new activities supporting the sustainability of GE in the sense of creating a new GEP. Cooperation was directed to those areas that can be supported by R&I HUB members. The activities are designed so that the benefits from their implementation are mutual and are not financially demanding. Investments represent expert input and the sharing of best practices. During brainstorming, no limits were set in relation to individual GEP areas. At the meeting, no limits were stated for all proposals that, on the one hand, followed from the original activities implemented by the original GEP. On the one hand, it was about new proposals that will contribute to increasing the quality of study, research, and presentation of the faculty as part of the sustainability of the GEP.

SWOT analysis

A.Strengths

Rising awareness
Support of science itself
Dissemination of knowledge of science
Inclusion
Intersection
Diversity
Equality of opportunity

B.Weaknesses

Financial
Lack of time

D. Opportunities

Approaching the younger generations
Sharing knowledge in the field of GE
Searching for cooperation opportunities

C.Threats

There seems to be a misunderstanding on the part of some employees.
Middle management control is being threatened.

Actions to be sustained:

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Indicate "YES" if it is a new emerged collaboration	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	External stakeholders involved	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Sustainability and Maintenance of R & I HUB.	Transfer to Market, Research	N (confirmation of original cooperation, or expanding the possibilities of cooperation)	Incorporation of the theme of gender equality into the agenda of the cooperating "Faculty Industrial Council", which will merge with the R&I HUB (project ecosystem)	Direct financial contribution is not needed. Personal contribution arises from the membership of the Council. Timeline: Agenda of GEP is drafted 4times per year during Council sessions.	Nr. of contributed actions and suggestions recorded in Agenda, successfully implemented and monitored.	January 2024 – New GEP	Each member of R&I HUB, Industrial Council	The Dean, Council for Gender Equity	R&I HUB Member-supported activities heading to students and employees
2.	Addition of statistical	HR	Y	Addition of statistical reporting and examination of the ratio	Personnel: HR	a balanced share, or at least a	January 2024 – New GEP	Academia	The Dean, HR	Balanced share of

	cal reporting and examination of the ratio of the variable component of remuneration for women.			of the variable remuneration component for women to the amount of compensation for men in the same job positions.	Timeline: quarterly Budget: N/A	growing share to balance				remuneration.
3.	A world of science and girls	Student Services	Y	An event devoted to attracting girls to study at the Faculty	Resources provided by the faculty. Timeline: once a year	Nr. of an activity	January 2024 – New GEP	R&I HUB, Management of the Faculty	Management of the Faculty (Responsible Vicedean)	The Activity
4.	Students contribute to	Research/ Teaching	Y	Presentation of gender equality by students based on the selection of the best-rated final thesis involved gender equity.	Resources provided by the faculty. Timeline: once a year	Nr. of presentations	January 2024 – New GEP	R&I HUB, Council for Gender Equality	Responsible Vicedean	Nr. of thesis

	science.									
5.	Rewarding women in science.	Research	y	Supporting women in science with an award for scientific contribution and their career growth.	Resources provided by the faculty. Timeline: once a year	Nr. of awards	January 2024 – New GEP	R&I HUB, Management of the Faculty	Academic Senate, Management of the Faculty	Nr. of Women awarded
6.	Evaluation of GEP implementation	Management	N (improving one)	Using evolving best practices and due diligence in academia.	Resources provided by the faculty. Timeline: once a year	Qualitative indicators	January 2024 – New GEP	Academia	Management of the Faculty	Nr. of proposals

Table 7 STUBA Actions discussed with external stakeholders 1

2. nd Report: Meeting held dated 3.11.2023

Agenda:

- 1) Best practices of Academia in GEP implementation
- 2) Best practices of Industry in Diversity and Inclusion
- 3) Brainstorming
- 4) Conclusions

Participants list

No	Name of the organization	Type of stakeholder * (see table below)	Gender
1.	Univerzita Sv. Cyrila a Metoda	Academia	F
2.	Univerzita Sv. Cyrila a Metoda	Academia	F
3.	ERASMUS s.r.o.	Industry	F
4.	Gender Expert	Gender Expert Industry	F
5.	STU	Academia	F
6.	STU	Academia	M
7.	MTF STU	Academia	M
8.	MTF STU	Academia	F
9.	MTF STU	Academia	F
10.	MTF STU	Academia	M
11.	MTF STU	Academia	F
12.	MTF STU	Academia	F
13.	MTF STU	Academia	F

Description the outcomes:

The meeting was held online via Google Meet on November 3, 2023 from 10:00 a.m. lasting approximately 90 minutes. The agenda mainly consisted of presenting best practices in the academic environment, how they implement activities within the adopted Action Plan, and how these activities are monitored and evaluated. Information was also shared about the structure of the Council for Gender Equality and the election of its representatives. Next, we focused on experiences in the business environment and how the issue is perceived in a multinational company, where different cultures, nationalities, and issues of gender equality collide. The supporting part was a discussion in the form of suggestions on how to improve access to the implementation of the activities of the new GEP.

SWOT analysis

A.Strengths Rising awareness Inclusion Intersection Diversity Equality of opportunity	B.Weaknesses Financial Lack of time
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D. Opportunities

Approaching the younger generations
 Sharing knowledge in the field of GE
 Searching for cooperation opportunities

C.Threats

There seems to be a misunderstanding on the part of some employees.

Picture 3 STU BA picture from the workshop with external stakeholders

Actions to be sustained:

N o	Name of the action	Them atic area	Indicate “YES” if it is a new emerged collaboration	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementati on	External stakeholder s involved	Departments involved in the action’s implementation and personnel’s role	Expected outcome of the action
1.	GBV preven tion	Sexual & Gender Harass ment	Y	Pointing out the importance of mandatory training of a selected group of internal stakeholders in the matter of GBV prevention.	Resources provided by the faculty. Timeline: at least semiannually	Nr. of participants	January 2024 – New GEP	Council for Gender Equality, External Experts	HR	Nr. of seminars
2.	Evalu ation of GEP imple menta tion	Manag ement	N (improving one)	Using evolving best practices and due diligence in academia.	Resources provided by the faculty. Timeline: once a year	Qualitative indicators	January 2024 – New GEP	Academia	Management of the Faculty	Nr. of proposals

Table 8 STUBA Actions discussed with external stakeholders 2

III.4 Université LIBRE de Bruxelles (RPO)

Sustainability workshop with internal stakeholders:

ULB's Caliper team conducted the workshop in two sessions for maximum efficiency and to secure the involvement of all key actors. The first sustainability meeting was held with the extended group of the steering committee and the second focused on aligning long term efforts of Caliper with the Vice-Rector of academic policy, in charge of gender and diversity, and the gender and diversity advisors to the rector, in order to secure targeted support in embedding GEP measures into ongoing and future institutional structures and policy. The below report presents and summarizes the combined outcomes of these discussions.

Agenda

- Introduction
- Presentation of actions, progress & results
[1st Iteration Phase & look ahead into 2nd iteration]
- Sustainability and long-term durability of GEP actions [Discussion]
- Reflection – priority measures for sustainability | continuous monitoring | Collaboration Potentials

Participants list

No	Type of stakeholder * (see table below)	Gender
1	Dean	M
2	Dean	M
3	Equality and diversity committee	W
4	Professors	M
5	Professors	M
6	Professors	W
7	Head of Department	M
8	Equality and diversity committee	M
9	Vice Rector gender and diversity	M
10	Equality and diversity committee	W
11	Equality and diversity committee	W
12	Equality and diversity committee	W

Description the outcomes:

Results, progress as well as challenges of the 1st iteration were presented and discussed and a look ahead at implementing measures in the 2nd iteration phase was considered. The discussions centered on the goal of identifying key measures in the GEP across all areas of intervention that may be sustained after the completion of the CALIPER project, ways to institutionalize actions and to clarify needed resources. The dedicated meeting conducted with the vice rector for gender and diversity and a set of gender and diversity advisors, centered around the setting of long-term strategic objectives and the identification of a working method to embed a relevant set of Caliper's actions into the established 'gender and diversity planning' at central level.

ULB's GEP in the frame of CALIPER has been designed from the start to work within the wider context of the institutional landscape and overarching policy objectives and will continue to pursue this central strategy to ensure long term durability, past the project's duration. The GEPs sustainability will be secured by continuing to embed and align gender efforts into ongoing and new institutional processes and goals.

Long term impact is and will be achieved by maintaining the GEPs position within the frame of larger strategic and central objectives, taking place across the institution – including the following structures:

- Euraxess HRS4R strategic plan - that includes strategic goals to ensure HR, career and recruitment practices embrace the gender+ dimension and foster research excellence.[This includes the Open, Transparent and Merit-based Recruitment checklist, taking gender dimensions into account - ULB has an active nondiscrimination policy and a proactive gender equality recruitment policy]
- Gender & diversity plan dedicated to implementing a university-wide policy in favor of gender equality.
- ULB's Sustainability Plan - dedicated to contributing to the Global SDGs, in its teaching and research missions
- Vice-rector in charge of gender equality and diversity policies
- Permanent Gender & Diversity officer

Measures in the area of 'Human Resources' will be embedded further in ongoing and long term strategic objectives within HR strategies and the HRS4R plan. Close cooperation with the HR department will be sought out, with the Gender and diversity officer acting as liaison and a working group will be formed to evaluate and engage in the practical implementation of measures across the institution. Further networks of support will be consulted such as the committee of women and science and The Gender Commission in Higher Education (CoGES), particularly for measure 2 targeting affirmative actions, as well as the ULB's internal Equality Law clinic.

Measures in the area of 'Institutional Governance' will be strengthened and sustained by a continued alignment with ULB's gender and diversity plan. The Vice Rector for gender and diversity, the deans of both STEM faculties and the gender+ commissions, as well as the network of gender contact persons will be mobilized. Measures will be geared to achieve wider institutional impact – like extending the measure of gender balance in advisory board to further bodies, discussing possibilities to give gender+ commissions a permanent status, the collection and monitoring of gender indicators will be centralized in the department of statistics and used transversally to enable better planning of actions and priorities and to evaluate progress and persisting barriers across the GEP as a whole.

The durability of interventions in 'Research' will be expanded and aligned with overarching strategic and policy goals for excellence in research. ULB central research department, the Vice rector for gender & diversity, Gender & diversity officer as well as ULB's European research cell, will be brought in to provide implementational and technical expertise. Possibilities to extend the impact of measures will be evaluated – such as the possibility of amending the central doctoral regulation of STEM faculties to feature a gender target in PhD juries, and to strengthen the application of the gender dimension in research by providing resources across the institution.

'Teaching' and 'Student Services' will be taken forward by enabling measures in these areas to reinforce one another. Goals such as the integration of the gender perspective in teaching will be tackled within the frame of the ongoing and long-term reform of the qualification program to teach at secondary schools. Here resources created in the framework of Caliper such as M11 the pedagogical guide on gender sensitive teaching will serve as a valuable tool and expertise to equip key actors involved in the reform, with the needed knowledge to integrate the gender dimension into the new teaching qualification program. The Education Support center, Service of science and education ULB, the Education Department will be brought in to align on a strategy. Efforts will also be continued around encouraging young women and girls to pursue future STEM studies and careers. Both STEM faculties will discuss the potential of co-organizing an event in the frame of the International Day of Women and Girls in Science.

In the area of 'Institutional Communication' the maintenance of current actions will be sought out. Dedicated STEM webpages for gender+ measures in both faculties, that have been created, will be updated regularly. The content created here will undergo continuous consideration for the application of inclusive language and imagery. Also, the objective of enhancing inclusive communications in the current GEP via training, will be evaluated for the possibility to be rolled out to more participants and further target groups across other departments at the university. An expert in inclusive communication, STEM faculty deans, Gender+ Commissions and the communications team may be brought in for support.

In the area of 'Sexual Harassment' awareness raising and training efforts will be carried forward. This will be framed by goals in the institution's gender and diversity plan as well as overarching HR initiatives. Further training on discrimination and harassment may be developed and also rolled out to further departments across the institution. Visual awareness raising campaigns (such as the poster exhibit) will be reviewed for the need of updated messaging also including intersectional dimensions.

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Toolkit to attract more female candidates to STEM positions	Human Resources	Continue promotion of toolkit Monitor application of toolkit	TBC	Collect indicators to measure increase of female applicants to STEM positions to measure impact Track application of toolkit – conduct user survey	2024-2026	Euraxess HRS4R Statistical Service ULB (STEP) HR Dep.	Permanently avoid unconscious bias, equip recruitment staff with tools and proactive training. Increase in number of female applicants to STEM positions
2	Action-oriented feasibility study 'Affirmative actions for academic recruitment'	Human Resources	Long term advocacy/lobbying strategy to progress the passing of an executive order needed to apply a pending legal framework for affirmative actions at the French speaking community level. Devised conjoint strategy with key actors and	ULB authorities in collaboration with ARES	Support to ULB authorities to advocate passing of the executive order Design & implementation of institutional framework at ULB for affirmative action	2023 onwards	ULB gender and diversity officer ULB Advisor to the authorities on gender policy Collaborate with: CoGES (Gender Commission in Higher Education)	Successful passing of the pending law supporting affirmative actions Internal Institutional framework for affirmative actions implemented

			networks to support the action		(in alignment with legal framework)		ELC (Equality Law Clinic) Comite Femmes et Science (ARES) HR Dep	
3	Action-oriented feasibility study 'Correction standard for career breaks due to childcare leaves'	Human Resources	If the studies outcome is positive: M3&4 will be interlinked – a working group could be formed with the HR team to push forward the practical implementation Draft proposal for application at institutional level Approval of the measure	3-month researcher	Track number of applications of correction standard (quantitative) Interviews with recruitment personnel (qualitative)	2024-2026	HR Department	Increase in the number of recruitment of female academics with childcare leaves
4	Action-oriented feasibility study 'Extension of post-doctoral contracts for the duration of childcare leaves'	Human Resources	See Measure 3		Track number of applications of extensions (quantitative) Interviews with key stakeholders in HR (qualitative)	2024-2026	HR Department	Decrease in the drop-off rate of female researchers
5	Gender+ commission in STEM faculties	Institutional governance	Officialize and make permanent the status of the newly created commissions	No budget needed	Commissions issue yearly impact report	2024 onwards	Deans Faculty of Sciences & of Faculty of engineering	An action-oriented group and network of advocates that sustain the institutionalization

			-Propose and receive approval for permanent status from relevant decision-making bodies at faculty level Discuss fixed membership of faculty gender contact person in the commissions				Gender & diversity officer	of gender+ policy at each faculty level
6	Gender indicators within different STEM disciplines	Institutional governance	Measure gender representation at faculty and disciplinary level (staff and students) Issue yearly report with indicators at STEM faculty level to track progress of gender representation	No budget	Yearly report with indicators across STEM disciplines at faculty level published	2024 onwards	Department for statistics (STEP) Deans of STEM faculties (Science faculty & faculty of engineering) Gender+ Commissions	Collect annually/consistently gender data across STEM disciplines in science and engineering faculty Long term/longitudinal tracking and evaluation of evolution of gender composition across STEM disciplines Take action to correct gender inequality in identified disciplines
7	Proposal for a gender-balanced participation in Advisory Boards	Institutional governance	If current pilot in 5 advisory boards is positively evaluated: Roll out measure across further boards at central level	No budget needed	Continued monitoring of application of measure across targeted boards – 1/3	2025-27	Presidents of selected advisory boards Vice rector for gender and diversity	Minimum of 1/3 female representation on selected boards.

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Identify further boards to target -Create proposal for roll out across more boards -Approval of proposal - Modification of the corresponding institutional document 		representation of women.			
8	Gender target in STEM PhD juries	Research	<p>To be confirmed if further actions need to be taken.</p> <p>The measure may already be fully sustainable if Caliper reaches the objective within the last year of implementation to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - amend doctoral regulation of each faculty to include a target or agreed norm in the special provisions of the regulation - With this the measure would be structural and permanent – being officialized in key institutional documents. 	No budget needed	Track representation of women in PhD juries	2024 -2026	<p>ULB central research department</p> <p>Vice rector for gender & diversity</p> <p>Gender & diversity officer</p>	Increased number of women participating in PhD juries across STEM faculties.

			If the process should last beyond the project period – the team will continue to work on progressing the measure.					
9	Dissemination of guideline on the inclusion of the sex/gender dimension in (STEM) research	Research	Enhance dissemination strategy at central level (beyond STEM faculties) Provide trainings and sustained support to enhance the inclusion of the gender dimension in research. Verify guidelines annually for potential updates in alignment with new EU funding and legal frameworks (update if needed)	No budget needed	Track annual number of downloads of guideline Track number of participants in trainings	2024 onwards	HR (Euraxess HRS4R) Cellule Europe (ULB EU research cell)	Increased awareness Increase in research proposals that consider the gender dimension
10	Exhibition 'Sex/gender+ in STEM research'	Research	One off action – N/A	/	/	/	/	/
11	Guide on gender-sensitive teaching	Teaching	Disseminate guide beyond STEM faculties To use this new resource in the existing training in	No budget	Number of participants in training User experience survey	2024-onwards	Team administering current training Euraxess HRS4R) Gender+ Commissions	Promote integration of gender perspective into teaching practices and content

			gender sensitive teaching.				Gender & Diversity officer	
1 2	Consultation for an explicit integration of a gender+ and diversity perspective into STEM curriculum competency frameworks	Teaching	Once a dedicated statement on gender is integrated in the competency frameworks of faculties – sustainability is already achieved without further action needed.	/	/	/	/	/
1 3	Consultation for a new ULB science and technology qualification program to teach at secondary schools	Student Services	<p>This measure must be done in the frame of an ongoing reform of the total qualification program. Objective: promote gender dimension in the reform</p> <p>The reform is anticipated to extend beyond Calipers period – thus, advocacy to integrate the gender+ dimension in teachers' curricula will continue to be pursued till completion of reform.</p>	No budget needed	??	Depends on timeline of reform	??	??

14	Gender technical support to mainstream the gender+ perspective in ULB science outreach activities	Student Services	<p>The creation of a roadmap featuring key questions to be considered when creating science outreach is planned currently.</p> <p>For sustainability this resource will undergo an update approx. every two years</p>	N/A		Every 2 years	In collaboration with Infor Science ULB	
15	Joint ULB-g4g WIN event	Student Services	<p>Consult STEM faculties on possibility to host periodic event to inspire a future generation of scientists</p> <p>Discuss if both STEM faculties can join forces on an event e.g. 11 Feb around the International Day of Women and girls in science.</p> <p>-Showcase innovations, researchers and role models across STEM faculties to challenge stereotypes in both gender and science.</p>	TBC	<p>Number of participants</p> <p>Participant survey</p>	2024-onwards	<p>R&I HUB</p> <p>Infor Science</p> <p>Gender+ Commissions</p>	Increased number of young women and girls interested in pursuing future STEM studies and careers

			Event targets internal and external stakeholders, including policy makers. It also invites secondary students to encourage them in their future study and career choices.					
1 6	Hands-on training on inclusive communication for STEM webpages administrators	Institutional communication	Roll out training for more staff also at central level (beyond STEM faculties) Revise training content in case of new/updated guidelines for inclusive communications	3h training per year Trainer pay	Number of participants Participant survey	2024 onwards	Counsellor for gender equality Expert in inclusive communication Deans Communication officers of faculties HR Dep. Gender+ Commissions	More gender+ aware institutional communication
1 7	Review and update of the communication of current STEM websites	Institutional communication	Measure is one off action with permanent impact	/	/	/	/	/

18	Dedicated webpage for the gender+ measures of STEM faculties	Institutional communication	Keep websites active, updated and fed with new and relevant content Any relevant initiatives and news items around gender equality measures in STEM will be featured	No budget needed		2024 onwards	Communication officers of faculties Gender+ Commissions	Increased visibility of gender+ policy in STEM faculties
19	Advertising of training on discrimination and harassment targeting STEM faculty authorities and departments/services leaders	Sexual harassment	Discuss possibility to extend training to further target groups – by collaborating with CASHe in charge of harassment towards students, and the service des conseillers en prévention in charge of harassment issues at staff level.	TBC	Number of participants Survey	2024 onwards	HR Department (Well-being unit) Gender & diversity officer CASHe	Better prevention and management of discrimination and harassment across faculties
20	Permanent poster campaign	Sexual harassment	N/A measure is permanent & long term	/	/	/	/	/

Table 9 ULB Actions discussed with internal stakeholders

Conclusions and next steps

The GEP will be sustained beyond the projects duration by further strengthening its already established links with ongoing larger strategic goals, policy objectives and actions plans at central level. The Caliper team will continue to work with relevant stakeholders to further develop plans for long term impact in the coming months.

Sustainability workshop with external stakeholders:

Agenda

Recap and learnings of the executed workshops – sharing experiences

What worked what did not work – what could be improved

A look ahead at future possibilities > How could potentially more trainings be rolled out.

Participants list

No	Name of the organisation	Type of stakeholder * (see table below)	Gender
1	JUMP	NGO [non feminist]	F

Description of outcomes:

The action discussed concerns the possibility to potentially roll out more trainings in the frame of the new central G&D plan that is under development. The meeting served to take stock and learnings from the prior cooperation and to have a first conversation on how a strategy for more trainings could look like. The outcomes now need to be brought back to the central intuitional level to discuss and evaluate the feasibility to move forward with the idea.

Recapping shared experiences of the action and discussing success factors as well as areas of improvement showed: that both parties evaluated very favorably the execution of the action. The quite mixed target group comprising actors from different staff [as well as generational] levels in the STEM faculties was seen a positive point - in the sense that it enabled the sharing of diverse experiences by the participants. However, one take away was also that mixing a very diverse group with different experiences could cause misunderstandings between participants – thus if pursuing a mixed and intergenerational group it is advisable to allocate more time to the workshop to allow space for more communication and to find solutions that can help converge viewpoints. This participant dynamic was identified as a potential advantage but also a potential weakness that requires attention. No further resistances or obstacles could be identified. Also, the need was discussed to equip participants with concrete tools that would allow them to better respond to diverse situations of harassment/sexism/ discrimination [based on participant feedback]. The workshops could also be extended in length to accommodate deeper learning experiences or possibly follow-up/advanced trainings could be held for certain target groups.

Factors that worked well included ‘the feeling that there was a lot of good will’ from participants that mitigated against any resistances, and helped the trainer easily work with the actors. In terms of future target groups, it is advisable to keep grouping people by faculty – as participants, in this logic, will be exposed to similar environments and situations, can easier share and relate to each other’s experiences and more importantly it will enable trainers to find collective solutions to context specific challenges of the target group.

On discussions for future possibilities: It was advised that before commencing any new trainings an evaluation of the unique situation at the institution could be conducted. This would entail the development and launch of a joint survey to better understand people’s needs, the situation at the institution and to surface any potential problems that should be addressed. From there on, custom made trainings could be developed. Such a situational analysis would also help to back up and justify the need for further trainings

and mitigate against any potential resistances. Jump's working approach is to build on unique institutional needs. Possibilities could include the launch of trainings that promote inclusive behaviors as well as tackle stereotypes that can affect work in male dominated environments and addresses inequalities. The communication approach would be to promote trainings on inclusive behaviors which is proven to yield less resistance and places participants in a position of learning, growth and the understanding of behaviors that help increase inclusivity.

As next steps discussions will need to be brought to the central level to evaluate how objectives align with central goals, and to better understand the needs of the institution in the coming 2-3 years. Then from these strategic discussions a methodology could be developed on how to achieve some key objectives as well as to define the target groups and faculties that could be beneficiaries of the action.

The type of financial and human recourses needed to host more trainings – can only be defined at a later point in time - once more detailed objectives have been crafted in cooperation with JUMP and the central level. Only then can the scope and the feasibility of such an investment be evaluated at central level. Either the institution would be able to define a scope of resources available for which JUMP could then create a value offer, or conversely Jump may also create an offer from scratch based on the defined objectives and the institution will evaluate if the needed resources are available. This is all to be rediscussed at a later stage.

Overall the experience on both sides was evaluated as very positive and both parties will continue to deliberate future possibilities for cooperation.

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Indicate "YES" if it is a new emerged collaboration	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	External stakeholders involved	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	M 19: Advertising of training on discrimination and harassment targeting STEM faculty authorities and departments/services leaders	Sexual Harassment	No	<p>It is being evaluated if the objectives of this action could be carried forward into the goals of the central G&D plan that is under development.</p> <p>The action could potentially be continued by rolling out more workshops on sexism/harassment and diversity training in the future</p> <p>This could potentially take place across a extended range of</p>	<p>Details can only be cleared later on TBC</p> <p>Personnel: 1 trainer and various internal staff to coordinate the action</p> <p>Budget: TBC</p> <p>Timeline: TBC</p> <p>Planning should start</p>	- Number of participants	Planning should start 2-3 month before launch of action	JUMP	<p>TBC...</p> <p>Gender & Diversity Project officer</p> <p>Target Faculties have to be defined [possibly network of gender contact persons}</p> <p>Other relevant actors. E.g, VR G&D , Deans etc.</p>	<p>Improvement of faculties' staff skills and knowledge to prevent and deal with cases of discrimination, to combat stereotypes, sexism and favor diversity.</p> <p>Better management and awareness of discrimination, stereotyping and sexism factors</p>

				<p>faculties [beyond STEM faculties]</p> <p>-First more in depth discussions need to take place on how the objectives of such workshops could best align with goals in the central G&D plan</p> <p>-The partnering NGO also suggests to create a survey and collect data from potential target groups to truly understand the situation at the institution and unique needs that exist – to be able to then design custom made trainings.</p> <p>-Also an evaluation needs to take place if the action is feasible based on the required budgetary resources that can be discussed at a later stage.</p>	<p>2-3 month before launch of action</p>					
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Table 10 ULB Actions discussed with external stakeholders

III.5 National Technical University of Athens – School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (RPO)

Sustainability workshop with internal stakeholders:

ECE NTUA's CALIPER team organized on the 12th of December an online combined workshop with internal stakeholders. Its main objective was to highlight the progress regarding the gender equality in the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, the initial results of the GEP's implemented actions, as well as the needs for further actions, information and awareness. The Working Group as well as the academic faculty were invited in order to discuss the sustainability plan of the GEP.

The following table provides the agenda of the workshop.

13.20 – 13.30		Registration
13.30 – 13.35	Welcome speech Dean Nektarios Kozyris	
13.35 – 14.00	Gender Equality in School of Electrical and Computer Engineering: Progress and Future Goals Dr Maria Flouri, Teaching & Research Lab Associate, Gender Equality Office	
14.00 – 14.10		Q&A
14.10– 14.45	Discussion	
14.45		End of workshop

Seventeen people attended the workshop (online) in total. The type and gender of participants are presented in the next table.

No	Type of stakeholder	Gender
1	Vice Dean, Professor	Male
2	Professor	Male
3	Other (Academia)	Male
4	Technical support	Male
5	Other (Academia)	Female
6	Professor	Male
7	Other (Academia)	Female
8	Professor	Male
9	Other (Research)	Male
10	Dean, Professor	Male
11	Professor	Female
12	Project Manager	Male
13	Professor	Male
14	Professor	Male
15	Professor	Male
16	Researcher	Female
17	Researcher	Female

Discussion and main Outcomes of the Workshop

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

At the beginning of the workshop, Professor Nektarios Kozyris (the Dean of the School) made a welcome speech mentioning that the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering is the first School in NTUA with its own GEP, while also highlighting the creation of School's Gender Equality Office.

Consequently, Dr. Maria Flouri, responsible for the Gender Equality Office and CALIPER team's member, presented the GEP actions that have been completed and evaluated, as well as the table with the suggested actions to be continued beyond the end of the project, in order to initiate the discussion with the attendees and fill in the table.

After the presentation and the completion of the table, there was a general discussion and further suggestions towards gender equality in School.

The professors had the impression that the number of female and male students were more equally distributed, in contrary with the statistics' results (which indicate an underrepresentation of female students). As such they highlighted that the GEP activities are of utmost importance in order to achieve equality and improve the academic community.

Prof. Nektarios Kozyris, focusing on the improvement of School's daily life through the enhancement of the interaction with the colleagues, administrative staff and students and through the adaptation of a mindset that does not allow discriminations (even unconscious expressions of speech or behavior), proposed the creation of a Gender Equality Committee in the School. The Committee would collaborate with the Gender Equality Office and deal with possible incidents/complaints. He also added that the aim is to give everyone the certainty that the School is "working" towards the direction of gender equality and the discriminations' elimination.

Prof. Konstantina Nikita, also suggested to create a lecture in English for the postgraduate students in order to develop the concept of synergy with foreign students and as such get in touch with other cultures (aiming to eliminate the discriminations). Additionally she mentioned that in view of a new postgraduate program initiating in the School "Translational Engineering in Health and Medicine", lectures could be developed for various courses such as AI in healthcare, healthcare robotics etc.

Afterwards, Prof. Giorgos Stamou highlighted the importance of providing to the students ongoing information on gender equality and added that the lectures could be a means of that. The professors and the academia faculty in general, have the responsibility to set the good example through their behaviors. He also pointed out how important it is for the students to know the operation of the Gender Equality Office so that they can turn to it for advice or to report possible problems.

Assistant Prof. Athanasios Voulodimos emphasized the importance of awareness raising regarding self-identification of gender identity among students, as this issue, he mentioned, seems to be recurring.

Subsequently, Prof. Dimitrios Askounis suggested the increase of information through the School's official website (visible material regarding the GEP and the Gender Equality Office). The development of a "code of ethics" for students ethics and behavior could be also supportive in the effort. It is essential for the students to be informed upon these as soon as they start their first year in the School. He also mentioned the importance of the collaboration between School's Gender Equality Office and NTUA's Gender Equality Committee.

After some questions by Prof. Iraklis Avramopoulos, regarding the progress of other project partners and generally of Europe, Dr. Maria Flouri, Dr. Manolis Ntanos and Prof. Konstantina Nikita initiated a relative discussion. They mentioned that even though some partners have faced barriers from their administration, there is more progress in Europe for years now (e.g.: universities with mechanisms for dealing with cases of gender violence, formal procedures to handle incidents of bias and sexist behaviour, lectures including the gender dimension, equal participation of women in panels, staff etc., dealing with unconscious stereotypes

in oral speech). In Greece there is more obstruction. However, nowadays, all the Greek universities have a Gender Equality Committee (National and Kapodistrian University of Athens has a Committee per each School too) and are developing guides and coping mechanisms.

Last but not least, all the participants agreed that it is essential to avoid unconscious comments and jokes in oral speech during lessons. As such, the maintenance of non-sexist language in both spoken and written language is of utmost importance. Dr. Maria Flouri also suggested to present relevant information material in the beginning of each academic year (probably during the presentation of course streams), while also she underlined the importance of using non sexist language in the written speech as well.

Table 11: ULB Main Outcomes

Thematic Area	Outcomes	Leverages & Obstacles
Human resources	Continued collection of data on the indicators	(+): Excellent cooperation with the School Secretary & the technical support that provide the respective data (-): None identified
Institutional Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a Gender Equality Committee in School level • Support and promote the Gender Equality Office 	(+): Engagement of the top management of the School (-): Possible difficulties in the allocation of the necessary resources
Institutional Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintain non-sexist language in written and oral speech through trainings to avoid unconscious stereotypes • Professors should set the good example through their behaviors • Strengthen the dissemination and increase the knowledge 	(+): High interest by the top level management (-): None identified
Research	Collection of data on the integration of the gender dimension in PhDs and in under & post graduate thesis	(+): Good cooperation with the Post and Under graduate Committees (-): Current low integration of the gender dimension into research
Teaching	Implementation of more lectures with gender dimension and also lectures in English to get in touch with other cultures (Erasmus students etc)	(+): Increased interest by various members of the teaching staff and students of the School (-): Scientific areas in which the integration is very difficult and/or not possible Scepticism by some Professors.
Transfer to market	As regards the Alumni Network and the Women in STEM network, there were no evaluation data, as these actions are implemented in the 2 nd iteration. The participants agreed that they are likely sustainable actions. However since they have not been implemented yet, their sustainability will be discussed in more detail, in a future meeting.	-

Thematic Area	Outcomes	Leverages & Obstacles
Sexual harassment and gender violence	Implementation of a mechanism at a School level and communication activities.	(+): Top level management endorsing the implementation of communication activities (-): None identified

Table 12 ECE NTUA Main outcomes from the workshop with internal stakeholders

The following table includes the nine actions that have been suggested to be continued beyond the project's end. The only fields that have been filled in advance, by the CALIPER team, were the number, the name and the thematic area of each action. The rest of them have been discussed and completed during the workshop in collaboration with the participants. No resistances or barriers have been identified during this procedure. All the participants were willing to share their opinion and ideas, and facilitate to the completion of the table.

No	Name	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Internal targets on the representation of women	Human resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicators record per year Indicators comparison with previous years Indicators inclusion in report every year 	Personnel: School technical support, Secretariat, Gender Equality Office Budget: 0 Timeline: -	Indicators	Annual implementation	Deanery Secretariat Gender Equality Office	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase the number of women Promotion of the gender dimension in the School's profile Decision support Motivation
2	Establishment of formal procedures to handle incidents of bias and sexist behaviour in the working environment.	Human resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of draft mechanism Adoption at School level Application Incidents' recording 	Personnel: Gender Equality Office, Others involved Budget: 0 Timeline: -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge of the process by all School members Incidents' recording 	Continuous	All school members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting a culture of zero tolerance Handling of incidents Safe working and teaching environment without incidents

No	Name	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
3	Gender Equality Office	Institutional Governance	Continuation of the Office after the end of the project	Personnel: Office manager, associates (if any), supervisors (if any) Budget: Timeline:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of organized actions Implementation of GEP actions 	Continuous	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Office manager Associates (if any) Supervisors (if any) 	Continuous operation of the Office
4	Collection of gender disaggregated data and collection of gender equality data on Intersectionality	Institutional Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Annual launch of the questionnaire Dissemination to all members of the School Data analysis and development of a relevant report Annual update of the questionnaire 	Personnel: Gender Equality Office Budget: Timeline:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Questionnaire launch Relevant reports 	Annual implementation	All School members	<p>Increase knowledge on gender data collection procedures</p> <p>Increase knowledge on the School's perspective on gender equality</p>

No	Name	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
5	Setting indicators and targets for the integration of the gender dimension in research	Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indicators record per year Indicators comparison with previous years Indicators inclusion in report every year 	Personnel: Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), Research Committee of NTUA, Postgraduate Studies Committee, Undergraduate Studies Committee, School Secretariat, Gender Equality Office Budget: 0 Timeline: -	Indicators	Annual implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> School Secretariat Gender Equality Office ICCS Research Committee of NTUA Postgraduate Studies Committee Undergraduate Studies Committee 	Increase the integration of gender dimension in research

No	Name	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
6	Integration of gender-related topics in selected courses and lectures	Teaching	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Continuation of lessons with the integrated material Addition of new courses Material evaluation and update 	Personnel: Academia Faculty members Budget: Timeline:	Number of courses/lectures	Continuous	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Academia faculty Gender Equality Office Students 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase the integration of gender dimension in lectured Increase the number of thesis and PhDs with an integrated gender dimension
7	Formal mechanism dealing with cases of sexual harassment and gender violence	Sexual harassment and gender violence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implementation of draft mechanism Adoption at a School level Application Incidents recording 	Personnel: Gender Equality Office, Others involved Budget: 0 Timeline: -	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge of the process by all School members Incidents recording 	Continuous	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> All school members 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promoting a culture of zero tolerance Handling of incidents Safe environment without incidents

No	Name	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
8	Information Days and Training Workshops on gender issues in STEM	Institutional Communication	Organization of 1-2 information days/workshops based on the School's needs	Personnel: Gender Equality Office, guest speakers/trainers, technical support Budget: Events' expenses (if needed) Timeline:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of information days/workshop Number of participants 	Continuous	All School members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased information on the gender related topics in seminars - trainings Increase the integration of gender dimension in research Support the environment without incidents of sexist behaviours, stereotypes and gender-based violence.

Table 13 ECE NTUA Actions discussed with internal stakeholders

Conclusions and next steps:

The participants congratulated the CALIPER team several times for their important effort and agreed that it is vital to apply the suggestions in everyday life, to boost the education and dissemination in a wider community so as for everyone to avoid any type of discrimination.

The discussion was fruitful and gave many insights to the team to further develop the GEP’s sustainability plan. To sum up, apart from the above mentioned activities, that are planned to be continued after the end of the project, the following ones are also considered to be implemented in the long term:

- Creation of a Gender Equality Committee at a School level
- Integration of gender related topics into more courses and/or creation of informative material for professors’ visits in high schools
- Inclusion of an informative session in the event of course streams’ presentation (February 2023)
- Highlight the progress of the GEP actions and the creation of Gender Equality Office in School’s General Assembly, by the Dean
- Implementation of more trainings and information workshops with the cooperation of the R&I Hub for knowledge transfer and exchange of expertise.

Photos:

Picture 4: ECE NTUA Picture from sustainability workshop with internal stakeholders

Slides:

Δράσεις ΣΙΦ		Δράσεις ΣΙΦ	
Αριθμ.	Τίτλος	Αριθμ.	Τίτλος
1.	Βήματα εστιασμένων στόχων για την προσαρμογή των εργασιών στο ΣΙΦ	10.	Διαμόρφωση δικτύου ασφαλών-οικιών
2.	Υλότερες διαδικασίες για τον αντιμετώπιση των απαιτήσεων και οφέλη της συμμετοχής στα εργασιακά περιβάλλοντα	11.	Εκδήλωση μεμονωμένο αντιμετώπισης αξιολογικής παρακολούθησης και διαβολής
3.	Υλοποίηση προγράμματος για το πλαίσιο εργασίας των ερευνητών	12.	Κατανομή προτίμων και δράσεων διαδρομής
4.	Μονον Γραφείου Ιερέων Φύλου	13.	Διαμορφωτική Δραστηριότητα στο ΣΙΦ
5.	Σύλλογος Δοκίμων εργατών με το φύλο και τον διαμετατόπιση	14.	Μάθημα επικοινωνίας και διαδρομής ("Open Day")
6.	Υποστήριξη της εφαρμογής του Οδηγού για τη «Χάρη» με επικοινωνιακές διαδικασίες	15.	«Ενημερωτική της διαδικασίας του φύλου στο έργο του Παιδαγωγικού Ινστιτούτου (Μεταπτυχιακό - 3 ^ο εξάμηνο), Σύστημα Διακοπής (Πρωτογενές - 6 ^ο εξάμηνο)
7.	Καθιέρωση εκπαιδευτικών στόχων για τον προσαρμογή της διαδικασίας του φύλου στην έρευνα	16.	Εκδήλωση για την Εξίσωση της Διαφορετικότητας στα ΑΕΙ - Δεκέμβριος 2022
8.	Εκπαίδευση της ομάδας του φύλου σε επικοινωνιακά εργαλεία και διαδικασίες	17.	Υλοποίηση εργασιών «Γνώσεις στην Κοινωνία»
9.	Υλοποίηση εργασιών σε θέματα φύλου για τους φοιτητές-τριες	18.	Ολοκλήρωση

Δράσεις ΣΙΦ
ΑΝΟΡΓΩΠΙΝΟ ΔΥΝΑΜΙΚΟ

Structural

#3. Ανάπτυξη και Εφαρμογή πλαισίου για τις συνθήκες εργασίας των ερευνητών στη Σχολή ΗΜΜΥ.

- ✓ Μίνι συνεντεύξεις με μη μόνιμους ερευνητές για τις συνθήκες εργασίας
- ✓ Ανάπτυξη προχεδίου του Πλαισίου

Εμπόδια:

- Ιούλιος 2022: Συζητήσεις με τη Διοίκηση της Σχολής > η Σχολή θα χρειαστεί περισσότερο χρόνο για να εξεταστεί και να εγκριθεί ένα τέτοιο πλαίσιο στο άμεσο μέλλον.
- Το περιβάλλον της Σχολής δεν φαίνεται έτοιμο για την εφαρμογή ενός πλαισίου για τις συνθήκες εργασίας των ερευνητών.
- Καθυστερήσεις στις επικοινωνίες

Παράγοντες επιτυχίας:

- Αποφασίστηκε να συνταχθεί μια πρόταση για το θέμα - θα μπορούσε να συμβάλει στην επίτευξη συναινετικής και ενός επίσημα εγκεκριμένου πλαισίου.

✓ monitored

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Δράσεις ΣΙΦ
ΔΙΟΙΚΗΣΗ

#15. Συλλογή δεδομένων με βάση το φύλο και τη διαθεσιμότητα

- ✓ 1^{ος} χρόνος υλοποίησης:
 - Ερωτηματολόγιο (100 συμμετέχοντες)
 - Ποιοτική και ποσοτική ανάλυση δεδομένων
 - Αξιολόγηση ερωτηματολογίου για μελλοντική βελτίωση
- ✓ Ετήσια ανανέωση και αναβάθμιση του ερωτηματολογίου
- ✓ Μηχανισμός συλλογής δεδομένων για το φύλο: συστηματική χάραξη στρατηγικής και σχεδιασμός κατάλληλων δράσεων

Δράσεις ΣΙΦ
ΕΠΙΚΟΙΝΩΝΙΑ

#16. Υποστήριξη της εφαρμογής του οδηγού για τη «Χρήση μη αξιωματικής γλώσσας στα διοικητικά έγγραφα»

- ✓ Εκπαίδευση για τη σωστή χρήση του Οδηγού (14 συμμετέχοντες)
- ✓ Follow up ερωτηματολόγιο για αξιολόγηση του training

Εμπόδια:

- Κανένα

Παράγοντες επιτυχίας:

- Η συνεργασία μεταξύ της Ομάδας CALIPER και της Γραμματείας ήταν καλή, επομένως είναι ένας παράγοντας που προώθησε την υλοποίηση αυτής της δράσης. (συζήτηση περιεχομένου, επιλογή ημερομηνιών, προώθηση εκδήλωσης)

Δράσεις ΣΙΦ
ΔΙΔΑΣΚΑΛΙΑ

#17. Ενωσιμότητα θεμάτων που σχετίζονται με το φύλο σε επιλεγμένα μαθήματα και διαλέξεις

- ✓ Αύξηση της ευαισθητοποίησης σε θέματα φύλου
- ✓ Follow up ερωτηματολόγιο για αξιολόγηση των διαλέξεων από τους φοιτητές /-τριες και μίνι συνεντεύξεις με τους καθηγητές
- ✓ Ανανέωση του υλικού σύμφωνα με τις αξιολογήσεις - επέκταση
- ✓ Αναζήτηση νέων μαθημάτων για περαιτέρω ενσωμάτωση σε προ- και μεταπτυχιακό επίπεδο

Δράσεις ΣΙΦ
ΣΥΝΕΡΓΑΤΙΚΕΣ ΔΡΑΣΕΙΣ

#12. Κινητοποίηση προτύπων και δράσεις διάχυσης

- ✓ 1 βίντεο και 1 coffee talk
- ✓ Πλήθος «ελικς» στα μέσα προώθησης, μίνι ερωτηματολόγιο, μίνι focus group

Εμπόδια:

- Κανένα

Παράγοντες επιτυχίας:

- Άφιξη συνεργασία όλων των εμπλεκόμενων

Δράσεις ΣΙΦ
ΣΥΝΕΡΓΑΤΙΚΕΣ ΔΡΑΣΕΙΣ

#16. Υλοποίηση ημερίδας «Γυναίκες στην Καινοτομία»

- ✓ Παρουσίαση εμπειριών γυναικών με έντονη παρουσία στην καινοτομία και την επιχειρηματικότητα
- ✓ Follow up ερωτηματολόγιο

Εμπόδια:

- Καθυστέρηση στην ημερομηνία υλοποίησης λόγω περιορισμών COVID
- Ίδια μέρα με Delphi Forum-άρνηση 2 πιθανών ομιλητών
- Δεν υπήρχε τρόπος εξασφάλισης της ενημέρωσης όλων των φοιτητών/Μικρότερη συμμετοχή από την αναμενόμενη παρά τις ανακοινώσεις στα μέσα κοινωνικής δικτύωσης και την ιστοσελίδα της Σχολής και τις αφίσες έξω από τις αίθουσες διαλέξεων

Picture 5: ECE NTUA Slides from sustainability workshop with internal stakeholders

Sustainability workshop with external stakeholders:

ECE NTUA's CALIPER team organized three sustainability workshops, dividing stakeholders according to their area of expertise. In particular, one sustainability workshop was organised with external stakeholders from the field of Academia and Research, one with external stakeholders from Industry and one with the external stakeholders representing NGOs and Civil Society. Additionally, two bilateral workshops were also organized to facilitate the participation of two external stakeholders, one from the industry area, and one NGO, who were not available on the scheduled dates.

The online workshops were held on the 22th, 25th and 28th of September respectively, while the bilateral workshops were implemented on the 25th and 26th of September 2023. The main objective was to highlight best practices from the implemented gender equality actions, to identify actions that can be sustained in the following GEP versions, and potential new actions. Upper goal is to continuously promote gender equality, through the implementation of updated GEPs, even after the end of the CALIPER project

The following table provides the agenda of the workshop.

10.50 – 11.00		Registration
11.00 – 11.05	Welcome speech Dr Emmanouil Ntanos, Project Manager	
11.05 – 11.15	Brief presentation of best practices & Sustainability of actions and ground for cooperation Dr Maria Flouri, Teaching & Research Lab Associate, Gender Equality Office	
11.15– 12.00	Discussion: Sustainability of the actions & collaboration	
12.00		End of workshop

Nineteen people attended the workshop (online) in total (18F/1M). The type and gender of participants are presented in the next table.

No	Name of the organization	Type of stakeholder	Gender
1	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki - AUTH	Academia and research institutions (Professor)	Female
2	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki - AUTH	Academia and research institutions (Professor)	Female
3	University of Crete	Academia and research institutions (Professor)	Female
4	Aristotle University of Thessaloniki - AUTH	Academia and research institutions (Researcher)	Female
5	Panteion Univeristy of Social and Political Sciences	Academia and research institutions (Permanent researcher)	Female
6	National Technical University of Athens - NTUA	Academia and research institutions (Career counselor, Liaison Office - Student and New Alumni Service)	Female
7	ATHENA – Research & Innovation Information Technologies	Academia and research institutions (Research Fellow)	Female
8	ELLAKTOR Group	Industry (Strategic advisor)	Female
9	SimpleApps	Industry (Lead Product & UI/UX Designer & Cofounder)	Female
10	Qualco	Industry (Development officer)	Female
11	Finclude	Industry (Co-Founder & Chief Risk Officer)	Female
12	Women Do Business	Feminist NGOs / gender experts (Project Manager & Cofounder)	Female
13	Mexoxo	Feminist NGOs / gender experts (Admin. Coordinator-)	Female

No	Name of the organization	Type of stakeholder	Gender
14	Mexoxo	Feminist NGOs / gender experts (Project Coordinator)	Female
15	Women On Top	Feminist NGOs (Co-founder/gender expert)	Female
16	National Technical University of Athens - NTUA	Academia and research institutions (Member of the CALIPER team - Researcher-NTUA)	Male
17	National Technical University of Athens - NTUA	Academia and research institutions (Member of the CALIPER team - Researcher-NTUA)	Female
18	National Technical University of Athens - NTUA	Academia and research institutions (Member of the CALIPER team - Researcher-NTUA)	Female
19	National Technical University of Athens - NTUA	Academia and research institutions (Member of the CALIPER team - Researcher-NTUA)	Female

Discussion and main Outcomes of the Workshop

At the beginning of the workshop, Dr. Emmanouil Ntanos (Project Manager) briefly welcomed the participants, mentioning that the CALIPER Project will soon be concluded, and highlighted the success of the actions implemented at the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering. Additionally, he described the scope of these workshops, i.e. to continue collaboration, through the elaboration of new and/or current actions, beyond the end of the project.

Afterwards, Dr. Maria Flouri, a member of the CALIPER team and responsible for the Gender Equality Office, presented the team's members and welcomed the stakeholders, asking them to introduce themselves.

After the short introductions, Dr Flouri presented the collaborative actions implemented within each stakeholder category. Dr Flouri focused on the actions that the G.E. Office intends to continue, after the end of the project and key parameters such as:

- What worked and didn't.
- How could the actions be further improved.
- What is necessary to be done to sustain these activities in the future.

During the presentation Dr Flouri also presented a SWOT analysis for each action, describing the actions strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. This led to a vivid roundtable discussion with all stakeholders, as they provided their feedback and respective suggestions, regarding actions that can be sustained and new ones.

In particular the main results per discussed action can be summarized as follows:

Collaborative Action 1: Role model engagement & dissemination activities

- Ideas were introduced on how to set up workshops that would be more oriented to young girls, e.g: promoting role models, sharing more technical information about how to build their own start-up.
- All stakeholders agreed that dissemination through social media is crucial (especially stakeholders from the feminist NGO Mexoxo highlighted the importance of taking advantage of these tools)
- Industry stakeholders suggested ways on how to build a mentor's database. These included asking members of GWISE network to dedicate one hour per week to meetings or calls with mentees.
- Regarding the obstacles that they have experienced, the NGO stakeholders noted that the participants are often more interested in personal stories of success and less in industry's line of work.

The SWOT analysis of the particular action can be found below (Table 1), while the

Table 1. SWOT Analysis - Role models' engagement & dissemination activities

<p>A. Strengths</p> <p>1. What is the expected outcome of the action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of positive role models • Communication of gendered issues • Creation of positive impact and empowerment <p>2. What resources (human and financial) do we have/need?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation with people with the right expertise (role models) is needed • Use of the School's resources • Identification of sponsors <p>3. Do we have the support of the top management?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes 	<p>B. Weaknesses</p> <p>1. How can the action be improved?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification and engagement of people from various fields • Enhancement of communication → attracting more students <p>2. Where are we lacking resources (human and financial)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weaknesses of financing allocation • Difficulties in attracting new people from various fields.
<p>Δ. Opportunities</p> <p>1. What policies we can leverage on to implement/sustain the action?</p> <p>2. What kind of issue this action intends to tackle?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintaining careers in STEM and entrepreneurship • Empowerment of women in the professional field • Communication on professional matters 	<p>Γ. Threats</p> <p>1. What issues can hold back our action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unavailability of potential role models • Unattendance and low engagement <p>2. Potential conflicts?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -

Table 2. Sustainability table on action: Role models' engagement & dissemination activities

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Indicate "YES" if it is a new emerged collaboration	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	External stakeholders involved	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Role models engagement and dissemination activities	Institutional Communication		Organisation of 1-2 coffee talks annually	Personnel: at least 2 role models, 1 person for technical assistance Budget: - Timeline: Annual	Nr of coffee talks implemented Nr of participants	1st Coffee talk: until December 2023 2nd Coffee talk: January 2024 – August 2024	Role models (Industry, Academia, NGOs) Other academia	ECE NTUA for the coordination and implementation of the action R&I Hub for the engagement of role models	Empowerment of female students Creation of positive female role models Encourage female students to pursue a career in STEM

Table 14 ECE NTUA Collaborative actions discussed with external stakeholders 1

Collaborative Action 2: Implementation of workshops & seminars on gender issues (STEM)

- An idea proposed to organize an event at a national level, with the co-organization and participation of all the Greek Universities. This will lead to shared skills, transfer of expertise and knowledge and attract funding opportunities (since the academia stakeholders have the same interests, they proposed the idea of making a request at the Ministry of Education).
- Implementation of a joint event, eg CALIPER and RESET Horizon Projects to presenting the outcomes of the sister projects.
- Stakeholders from AUTH shared an idea on the organization of workshops in the context of Walk | AUTH Innovation Accelerator <https://walk.auth.gr/>.
- The participants discussed the idea of using content from the Stanford Lab “Gendered Innovations” as a topic for the implementation of a discussion series on how to integrate the gender dimension into research content.
- The participants noted the importance of further dissemination through social media, and of gradually building engagement through the establishment of a small community that will develop incrementally.

Table 3. SWOT Analysis - Implementation of workshops & seminars on gender issues (STEM)

<p>A. Strengths</p> <p>1. What is the expected outcome of the action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge transfer • Strengthening women’s self confidence in the gender issues presented • Influence by positive role models <p>2. What resources (human and financial) do we have/need?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation with people from academia, industry and NGOs, is needed • Use of the School’s resources • Identification of sponsors <p>3. Do we have the support of the top management?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes 	<p>B. Weaknesses</p> <p>1. How can the action be improved?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expanding the topics to be covered • More emphasis on the dissemination of the events is necessary, to attract a greater number of participants. <p>2. Where are we lacking resources (human and financial)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weaknesses of financing allocation • Difficulties in attracting new people from various fields.
<p>Δ. Opportunities</p> <p>1. What policies we can leverage on to implement/sustain the action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of topics with greatest impact (implementation of polls in social media) • Annual programming of the covered topics and contact with the respective speakers • Continuous promotion • Design of posters for further dissemination <p>2. What kind of issue this action intends to tackle?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • - 	<p>Γ. Threats</p> <p>1. What issues can hold back our action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low participation • Ignorance of the public about the importance of the covered topics → low participation <p>2. Potential conflicts?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -

Table 4. Sustainability table on action: Implementation of workshops & seminars on gender issues (STEM)

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Indicate “YES” if it is a new emerged collaboration	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	External stakeholders involved	Departments involved in the action’s implementation and personnel’s role	Expected outcome of the action
2	Implementation of workshops & seminars on gender issues (STEM)	Institutional Communication		Implementation of questionnaires in order to identify the topics with the greatest impact to be covered. Identification and engagement of speakers Organization and implementation of 1-2 events/trainings annually	Personnel: Gender Equality Office, Invited speakers / trainers, technical support Budget: Event’s expenses (if necessary)	Number of trainings / events Number of participants	January 2024 – August 2024	Members of the R&I Hub	ECE NTUA for the coordination and implementation of the action R&I Hub for the identification and engagement of speakers	Communication of topics on gender issues Increased integration of the gender dimension into research Creation of an environment without incidents of sexism, stereotypes and gender based violence.

Table 15 ECE NTUA Collaborative actions discussed with external stakeholders 2

Collaborative Action 3: The Women in STEM & Entrepreneurship – Greece (G-WISE) network’s activity

- Proposals were made to help the CALIPER team to enlarge their network. For instance, the stakeholder from SimpleApps proposed to co-organize events with the Network, as well as QUALCO.
- Another idea was proposed by the participant from the “ELLAKTOR GROUP”, which has experience in “women entrepreneurship” and related to the development of synergies for scholarships, internships etc.
- All the stakeholders agreed to the importance of setting up a shared “mailing list” to support the organization of future collaborative activities.
- Approaches that would increase men’s participation in seminars, workshops etc were also proposed (eg. the stakeholders from NGO’s and the industry field shared the idea to use presentation titles at the events that are mostly gender neutral so to attract all the genders)

Table 5 SWOT Analysis – The G-WISE Network

<p>A. Strengths</p> <p>1. What is the expected outcome of the action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowerment of women that have (or want to have) a career in STEM • Creation of role models – positive influence • Opportunities for networking • Mentoring activities • Knowledge transfer <p>2. What resources (human and financial) do we have/need?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation with people from academia, industry and NGOs, is needed • Identification of sponsors • Identification of volunteers (from the School), to assist in the GWISE technical support <p>3. Do we have the support of the top management?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes 	<p>B. Weaknesses</p> <p>1. How can the action be improved?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attracting more members • Convincing more members to become mentors • Implementation of more events • Creation of more synergies • Attract sponsors <p>2. Where are we lacking resources (human and financial)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Weaknesses of financing allocation • Difficulty in engaging members into a more active role
<p>Δ. Opportunities</p> <p>1. What policies we can leverage on to implement/sustain the action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a document with the operating rules (what do we post, how often, how many events per year etc) • Implementation of a volunteering community to assist with the content management • Seek funding (EU resources, national resources) <p>2. What kind of issue this action intends to tackle?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The need for a STEM community for women in Greece 	<p>Γ. Threats</p> <p>1. What issues can hold back our action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low engagement • Lack of human resources and time availability leading to an inactive network <p>2. Potential conflicts?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of various other networks for gender equality

Table 6. Sustainability table on action: “the G-WISE Network”

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Indicate “YES” if it is a new emerged collaboration	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	External stakeholders involved	Departments involved in the action’s implementation and personnel’s role	Expected outcome of the action
3	The G-WISE Network	Transfer to market		<p>Attracting more members</p> <p>Organization of information activities for members</p> <p>Creation and dissemination of relevant content</p>	<p>G-WISE network: Operators and members</p> <p>R&I Hub</p> <p>Use of the ECE NTUA resources (when needed)</p> <p>Use of the AUTH resources (when needed)</p>	<p>Number of members</p> <p>Number of events implemented</p>	Constant implementation	<p>Members of the G-WISE network</p> <p>Members of the R&I Hub</p> <p>Members of the AUTH</p>	ECE NTUA & AUTH for the operation of the Network (new members invitations, organization of events, dissemination etc)	<p>Role models and positive impact</p> <p>Empowerment</p> <p>Networking</p> <p>Communication and knowledge transfer</p>

Table 16 ECE NTUA Collaborative actions discussed with external stakeholders 3

Collaborative Action 4: Including gender dimension at the Alumni network

- Industry stakeholders suggested the creation and establishment of an informal students' "community" and use of "UpToDate" tools to attract and engage them.
- Attracting volunteers among the students of the University, that would be assisting in the organization of meetings/infosessions . This will also achieve further engagement.
- All stakeholders agreed that dissemination through social media is also important.

Table 7 SWOT Analysis – Including gender dimension at the Alumni network

<p>A.Strengths</p> <p>1. What is the expected outcome of the action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowerment of women that have (or want to have) a career in STEM • Creation of role models – positive influence • Opportunities for networking • Mentoring activities • Knowledge transfer <p>2. What resources (human and financial) do we have/need?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large number of alumniees that are employed in major companies • ECE NTUA resources are available (if needed) <p>3. Do we have the support of the top management?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes 	<p>B. Weaknesses</p> <p>1. How can the action be improved?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Convincing more alumniees to become mentors • Implementation of more events • Creation of more synergies <p>2. Where are we lacking resources (human and financial)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in engaging alumniees into a more active role
<p>Δ. Opportunities</p> <p>1. What policies we can leverage on to implement/sustain the action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of list of alumniees interested in mentoring activities and the gender dimension • Implement questionnaires to identify topics of interest for webinars <p>2. What kind of issue this action intends to tackle?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Empowerment and mentoring for (young) women interested in a career in STEM • Communication of the importance of integrating the gender dimension in various employment issues • Communication of practical experience by ECE NTUA alumniees 	<p>Γ. Threats</p> <p>1. What issues can hold back our action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low engagement • Lack of interest both from the alumniees and the participants <p>2. Potential conflicts?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Existence of various other webinars by different organizations

Table 8. Sustainability table on action: Including gender dimension at the Alumni network

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Indicate "YES" if it is a new emerged collaboration	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	External stakeholders involved	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
4	Including gender dimension at the Alumni network	Transfer to market		Organization of mentoring activities focused on labor issues including the gender dimension	ECE NTUA Alumni network Gender Equality Office Communication Office	Number of alumnies in the network Number of events implemented Number of participants in the events	Continuous implementation	Members of the Alumni network	Gender Equality Office for the coordination and organization of the events Communication Office for the dissemination of the events	Empowering female students Creation of positive role models

Table 17 ECE NTUA Collaborative actions discussed with external stakeholders 4

In a nutshell, all the external stakeholders participating in the workshop, agreed to continue the collaboration on gender equality with ECE NTUA, and agreed to organize future actions. Dr Flouri also invited all stakeholders to participate at the next event which will be organized by the G-WISE Network in the framework of the “EU CODE WEEK”. In the end, Dr Flouri thanked all the participants and ended the workshop.

Conclusions and next steps

The external stakeholders congratulated the CALIPER team several times for their significant outcomes and all the participants welcomed the opportunity to continue the collaboration after the end of the project. They agreed that they are glad to enhance our cooperation and boost the effort towards gender equality.

In conclusion, the discussion was fruitful and provided the necessary support for the upcoming activities. The stakeholders emphasized the critical importance of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) and the need to secure funding.

The R&I Hub agreed to focus on the following ideas & proposals:

- Implementation and co-organization of more events (e.g trainings and information workshops),
- Creation of a community engagement so to achieve long-term and sustainable outcomes
- Encouragement for more speakers to participate at the “mentoring hub”; having as a main aim to foster the collaboration between the R&I Hub’s network

Photos

Picture 6: ECE NTUA Sustainability workshop with Academia & Research Institutions in progress

Picture 7: ECE NTUA Sustainability workshop with Industry in progress

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Picture 8 ECE NTUA Sustainability workshop with NGOs & Civil Society in progress

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Table 1: Overall actions to be sustained

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Indicate "YES" if it is a new emerged collaboration	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	External stakeholders involved	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Role models engagement and dissemination activities	Institutional Communication		Organization of 1-2 coffee talks annually	Personnel: at least 2 role models, 1 person for technical assistance Budget: - Timeline: Annual	Nr of coffee talks implemented Nr of participants	1st Coffee talk: until December 2023 2nd Coffee talk: January 2024 – August 2024	Role models (Industry, Academia, NGOs) Other academia	ECE NTUA for the coordination and implementation of the action R&I Hub for the engagement of role models	Empowerment of female students Creation of positive female role models Encourage female students to pursue a career in STEM

2	Implementation of workshops & seminars on gender issues (STEM)	Institutional Communication		Implementation of questionnaires in order to identify the topics with the greatest impact to be covered Identification and engagement of speakers Organization and implementation of 1-2 events/trainings annually	Personnel: Gender Equality Office, Invited speakers / trainers, technical support Budget: Event's expenses (if necessary)	Number of trainings / events Number of participants	January 2024 – August 2024	Members of the R&I Hub	ECE NTUA for the coordination and implementation of the action R&I Hub for the identification and engagement of speakers	Communication of topics on gender issues Increased integration of the gender dimension into research Creation of an environment without incidents of sexism, stereotypes and gender based violence.
3	The G-WISE Network	Transfer to market		Attracting more members Organization of information activities for members Creation and dissemination of relevant content	G-WISE network: Operators and members R&I Hub Use of the ECE NTUA resources (when needed) Use of the AUTH resources (when needed)	Number of members Number of events implemented	Constant implementation	Members of the G-WISE network Members of the R&I Hub Members of the AUTH	ECE NTUA & AUTH for the operation of the Network (new members invitations, organization of events, dissemination etc)	Role models and positive impact Empowerment Networking Communication and knowledge transfer

4	Including gender dimension at the Alumni network	Transfer to market		Organization of mentoring activities focused on labor issues including the gender dimension	ECE NTUA Alumni network Gender Equality Office Communication Office	Number of alumniees in the network Number of events implemented Number of participants in the events	Continuous implementation	Members of the Alumni network	Gender Equality Office for the coordination and organization of the events Communication Office for the dissemination of the events	Empowering female students Creation of positive role models
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Table 18 ECE NTUA Collaborative actions to be sustained after the project's completion

III.6 Institute for Research in Biomedicine (RPO)

Sustainability workshop with internal stakeholders:

Agenda:

Dia: 25 de setembre de 2022

Hora i Lloc: 11.30, PCB

- GEP Action overview. Status, reporting, development and sustainability
- EDC Members, sustainability and open space for new members
- Leadership for Women in Science training
- 25N Manifest

Participants' list:

No	Type of stakeholder	Gender
1	Academia-Equality and diversity committee (or similar (Gender) Equality/the Diversity bodies)	Female
2	Research- Project Manager	Female
3	Academia- Group Leader /Professor	Female
4	Administration- Research / Project Support Office	Female
5	Administration- Human Resources Office	Female
6	Research -Researchers (with PhD, not permanent)	Female
7	Research -Young researchers (no PhD)	Male
8	Management- Head pf Department	Female
9	Administration- Equality and diversity committee (or similar (Gender) Equality/the Diversity bodies)	Male

Description of outcomes:

The session was planned by providing a summary/overview of the actions. Starting with the six actions that were finalized during the first iteration of the project. At the end of the analysis of the first six actions, a quick guide of the reporting template was explained. This was done to provide a structural overview, that may result as helpful for the task/action leaders in the development of the remaining 18 actions.

The actions that are under development or yet to be developed were discussed following the structure provided for the session making emphasis on how they can be sustained overtime and the involvement of the acting stakeholders. This session also provided a good platform to provide an explanation for the changes in topics for the action that were initially categorized as "intersectionality" and "collaborative actions". Some potential resistances/barriers/facilitators were identified and will be explained below. These concrete points were not included in the table to avoid excess of information on the document:

Action 8 (HUMAN RESOURCES): Conduct a Salary Audit:

Possible barriers: This action was externalized to an external services provider with an expertise in this type of procedures. The final report for the initial audit had some delay, and the IRB is now on the process of translating and working on the final reporting of the action. This may cause a delay internally in regards to the activities plan for this action, especially in the communication process internally and also to completely finish the reporting and evaluating report.

Action 11 (HUMAN RESOURCES): Develop a Work-Life Balance Guide

Facilitators: Smart Venice. In one of the bilateral meetings to have an overview of the development of the GEP the IRB requested advice and guidance with the bibliography to better the developed the WLB guide . Smartvenice provided information and the guide is now under development.

Action 12(HUMAN RESOURCES/INTERSECTIONALITY): Develop awareness campaigns on Intersectionality.

Facilitators: IRB Barcelona has a very good relationship with PRISMA external stakeholder (member of R+I HUB) expert in intersectional topics, providing very important input in the realization of actions that have an intersectional approach. In addition, their participation may also be an impact to the rest of the consortium members of the CALIPER project since a workshop may be planned to explain the recent develop guide for LGBTQ+ members in research centers.

Action 14 (INSTITUTIONAL GOVERNANCE): Prepare an internal regulation to govern the Equality and Diversity Committee.

Possible barriers: The concrete barrier in this action was related to time and the deadline of the action. There was a brief delay on this action and it was caused because internally it was decided that it would be more clear/inclusive to have the document in three languages, so it was translated to Spanish, English and Catalan. The action is now completed and the final output in three languages can be found in the institutional intranet.

Action 19 (INSTITUTIONAL COMMUNICATION): Promote institutional engagement in equality and diversity topics (videos, institutional equality day, printed materials, among others).

Facilitators: Communication department and success of 8th of March video:

(https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nvjrRYCOYJQ&t=6s&ab_channel=IRBBarcelona). Having good feedback and engagement with this tool, the idea of creating more visual content is most likely to happen. This time the new topic will be the February 11 - The International Day of Women and Girls in Science

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
IMPLEMENTED IN FIRST ITERATION								
1	Review, update and disseminate existing recruitment policies and guidelines, assuring that the documentation has a gender sensitive approach.	Human Resources	Institutionalized procces: Policies will be reviewed every 2 years.	Personnel: HR Budget: N/A Timeline: Every 2 years.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # of reviewed documents Times the documentation is reviewed and updated 	M21-M24	HR	Revised and updated documentation
2	Give internal and external visibility to the new Gender Equality Plan.	Institutional Communication	Institutionalized procces: Efforts regarding equality and diversity will be constantly shared through instutional channels.	Personnel: WG+Communication Département Budget: N/A Timeline: Duration of plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> # attendees to presentation session(internal and external) 	M21-M24	WG+Communication+ HR	Ensure all that the IRB Barcelona community is aware of the new Gender Equality Plan

3	Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader selection protocol	Institutional Governance	Institutionalized procces: Policies will be reviewed every 2 years.	Personnel: HR+Directorate +WG Budget: N/A Timeline: Every 2 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Composition of selection panels aiming to achieve a target of at least 70%/30% men/women • Shortlisted candidates aiming for at least 75%/25 % men/women 	M21-M32	WG+Directorate+HR	Promote the participation of female scientists in Group Leader recruitment processes Increase awareness of the Protocol, its advantages and the results of its application
4	Review and update protocol on Sexual Harassment.	Sexual and Gender Harassment	Institutionalized procces: Policies will be reviewed every 2 years.	Personnel: HR+ H&S Budget: N/A Timeline: Every 2 years	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participants in the training sessions • Number of training sessions 	M21-M32	HR+ H&S+EDC	Prevent and eradicate behaviour related to sexual and gender harassment
5	Reinforce equality and diversity topics in onboarding sessions.	Student Services	Institutionalized procces: Sessions have been structure do be done continuously over time.	Personnel: HR+ H&S Budget: N/A Timeline: Once a month	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participants in the training sessions • Number of training sessions 	M22-M32	HR+ H&S+EDC	Give all newcomers a general overview of the efforts made by IRB Barcelona in matters pertaining to equality and diversity

6	WIN EVENT	Transfer to Market	At this moment. The event will only be done once.	Personnel: WG+Innovation +Directorate Budget: Caliper Project Timeline: Once a month	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of participants in event Satisfaction feedback sessions after the event 	M28	WG+Innovation+Directorate +External Stakeholders	Highlight and value women-led innovation, presenting startups and spin-offs and examples of gender-sensitive product development/design
<i>ACTIONS TO BE DEVELOPED IN SECOND ITERATION</i>								
7	Introduce measures to avoid bias in selection and evaluation processes.	Human Resources	Expected institutionalization By creating new documents and tools to ensure a non-bias recruitment process. To be implemented with an open timeline., Internal Resources human resources will be allocated to develop this action.	Personnel: HR+ WG Budget: N/A Timeline: over duration of project and expected to go beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Composition of panel members in recruitment processes <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of hired candidates who belong to the under-represented gender at the time of hiring 	M31-M43	HR+WG+external stakeholders (CERCA)	Promote the under-represented gender among applications of similar merit and skills

8	Conduct a Salary Audit	Human Resources	Institutionalized process: The audit as required by law will have to be done periodically.	Personnel: HR Budget: Internal budgeted if the process has to be externalized. Timeline: yearly process.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Document recording annual salaries according to the job classification system and the collective agreement • Long term: Number of salary audits • Long term: Number of job evaluations 	M22-M36	HR+Directorate	Ensure equal treatment and nondiscrimination among men and women with regard to pay
9	Plan and develop training actions to raise awareness of the importance of work-life balance and promote a pro-conciliation leadership management model	Human Resources	Institutionalized process: the idea is to making training actions recurrent and incorporate WLB measures to the institutional culture. Resources: Both internal budget and budget from EDC can be allocated to WLB actions.	Personnel: HR+WG+Directorate Budget: N/A Timeline: over during of project and expected to go beyond	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participants who attend the training and informative sessions broken down by gender • Number of participants broken down by category • Long term: Number of possible new measures to incorporate 	M25-M41	HR+WG+Directorate	Make work-life balance effective at IRB Barcelona, enhancing an institutional culture in which the promotion and support of conciliation are highly valued

10	Develop a Parental Leave Guide	Human Resources	<p>Institutionalization: This guide will become a recurrent document for parental procedures at the IRB. The document will be updated if required by law.</p> <p>Resources human resources will be allocated to develop this action.</p>	<p>Personnel: HR+ Budget: N/A Timeline: expected to go beyond the time line of project, updating in applicable.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of dissemination campaigns used for communicating this action • Number of parental leaves taken by year broken down by gender 	M32-M36	HR+WG	Provide support to parents-to-be and encourage men to take parental leave.
11	Develop a Work-Life Balance Guide	Human Resources	<p>Institutionalization : This guide will become new document in the efforts of WLB, incorporated on the institutional intranet and available for employees.</p> <p>Resources human resources will be allocated to develop this action.</p>	<p>Personnel: HR+WG+EDC Budget: N/A Timeline: expected to go beyond the time line of project, updating in applicable.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Published version of the Guide on the institutional intranet. • Number of Updated versions of the document if it applies 	M26-M32	HR+WG	Inform about the existing work-life balance measures at IRB Barcelona

12	Develop awareness campaigns on Intersectionality.	Human Resources	Expansion/Alignment: IRB will get advice in this topic from a external stakeholder (PRISMA) expert in intersectional topics. Resources human resources+communication partnrs will be allocated to develop this action.	Personnel: HR+WG+EDC+Communications dept. Budget: N/A Timeline: expected to go beyond the time line of project, updating in applicable.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of people who attend the training sessions • Number of measures and tools implemented in this action 	M25-onwards	HR+WG+EDC+Communications dept.	Construct a critical perspective on intersectional topics, providing the grounds to rethink everyday practices
13	Develop mentoring Programme: To promote career progression	Inst. Governance	Institutionalized process: The action will help to provide a mainframe to provide structural support for future mentoring programmes. Resources: EDC +HR Expansion/Alignment: some of the mentoring programmes involve other research centers and can be a reciprocal process	Personnel: HR+WG+EDC+Faculty. Budget: N/A Timeline: expected to go beyond the time line of project, updating in applicable.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participants in mentoring programmes broken down by gender • Number of training sessions • Number of role models involved • Number of peer coaching groups and type of participants 	M21-M36	HR+WG+EDC+Faculty	Provide a guidance method for career progression reflecting commitment to the career development of women

			in change of information and good practices.					
14	Prepare an internal regulation to govern the Equality and Diversity Committee.	Inst. Governance	<p>Institutionalized process: the action has created an internal regulation that will be part of the institutional documents going forward. As an institutional document, it will be updated and reviewed periodically</p> <p>Resources: As a document from the EDC the budget and workforce will be from this committee.</p>	<p>Personnel: EDC. Budget: N/A Timeline: expected to go beyond the time line of project, updating in applicable</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of document • Number of dissemination sessions • Number of approved versions of the document 	M25-M32	WG+EDC	Provide a document regulating the functioning of the Equality and Diversity Committee and the roles of its members

15	Organise an advance training session on gender and diversity topics for members of the Equality Commission.	Inst. Governance	Initially this action will only happen once. Nevertheless, the possibility to make it recurrent will be evaluated after the training session.	Personnel: EDC. Budget: EDC Timeline: happening once.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of people who attend the training session • Number of measures and tools implemented in this matter 	M29-M43	WG+EDC	Provide an advance perspective on the concept of equality and diversity
16	Creation and promotion of manual/guidelines on inclusive language (English, Spanish, and Catalan)	Inst. Communication	Institutionalized process: This document will provide a new guidelines on inclusive language for the communications department to be used going forward. Resources: Budget allocated to the EDC +including members of the committee. Expansion/Alignment: This measure can be shared and implement with members of the	Personnel: EDC. Budget: EDC Timeline: happening once.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of training sessions given • Manual/guidelines on inclusive language in English • Manual/guidelines on inclusive language in Spanish • Manual/guidelines on inclusive language in Catalan • Feedback sessions with participants 	M31-M37	WG+EDC+Communications department	Include gender sensitivity in internal/external communications.

			HUB. Gender Knowledge: Feedback from other institutions has been taken into account in previous meetings/workshops (AQUAS) member of hub.					
17	Develop a checklist/guidelines for posting and checking material on the Institute's social media channels	Inst. Communication	Institutionalized process: This document will provide a new guidelines on inclusive language for the communications department to be used going forward.	Personnel: WG+Communications department+HR. Budget: internal Timeline: happening once.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of employees using the guide per year • Number of social media posts for which the guidelines has been used 	M31-M36	WG+EDC+Communications department	Provide a guide to ensure the gender sensitivity of external communication on social media platforms.
18	Organise and participate in advanced training on inclusive language.	Inst. Communication	Initially this action will only happen once. Nevertheless, the possibility to make it recurrent will be evaluated after the training session	Personnel: WG+Communications department+HR. Budget: internal Timeline: happening once	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participants in training sessions 	M30-M38	WG+EDC+Communications department	Integrate an inclusive (gender, diversity, intersectional) approach into oral and written communications and apply the recommendations for diverse and

								inclusive communication
19	Promote institutional engagement in equality and diversity topics (videos, institutional equality day, printed materials, among others).	Inst. Communication	This action will continue moving forward. Outputs are to be engaging and promote institutional engagement. Expansion and institutionalization may happen depending on the output.	<p>Personnel: WG+Communications department+HR .</p> <p>Budget: internal and may include others depending on the activity</p> <p>Timeline: project and moving forward</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of blog posts, news, articles, activities, etc., posted on the institutional website relating to equality and diversity 	M21-Onwards	WG+EDC+Communications department	Give greater visibility to the efforts made by IRB Barcelona with respect to equality and diversity topics.
20	Offer training sessions on the integration of the gender dimension into research.	Research	Initially this action will only happen once. Nevertheless, the possibility to make it recurrent will be evaluated after the training session	<p>Personnel: WG.</p> <p>Budget: internal and may include others depending on the activity</p> <p>Timeline: happening once</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participants in training sessions • Number of training sessions • Number of projects/research proposals taking gender into account 	M31-M37	WG+EDC+HR+Academic unit	Understand the importance of gender dimension in research and innovation.

21	Create and consolidate a protocol for planning and developing internal seminars, promoting and assuring the participation of female speakers.	Research	<p>Institutionalized process: The action will provide a new institutional protocol to be used starting with the elaboration of the action going forward</p> <p>Resources: internal</p>	<p>Personnel: WG. Budget: N/A Timeline: project and moving forward</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of seminars per scientific programme Number of yearly seminars Number of female speakers Number of non-binary speakers 	M25-onwards	WG+EDC	Create and consolidate a protocol for planning and developing internal seminars, promoting and assuring the participation of female speakers.
22	Integrate gender perspective training in transversal PhD programme	Student Services	<p>Institutionalized process: The idea of this training session is to integrate it to the regular mandatory training to all PhD Students.</p> <p>Resources: Internal budget+ HR +Academic Personnel</p> <p>Gender Knowledge: Feedback from other institutions and experts will be taken into consideration.</p>	<p>Personnel: WG+HR+Academic . Budget: internal and may include others depending on the activity Timeline: once a year</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of participants in training sessions Number of training sessions Number of projects/research proposals taking gender into account 	M31-onwards	WG+EDC+HR+Academic unit	Include a mandatory course to inform about existing initiatives addressing equality and diversity.

23	Develop internal training on Sexual & Gender Harassment.	S&G Harassment	<p>Institutionalized process: The idea of this training session is to provide it periodically.</p> <p>Gender Knowledge: Feedback from other institutions and experts will be taken into consideration.</p>	<p>Personnel: WG+HR+EDC</p> <p>Budget: internal and may include others depending on the activity</p> <p>Timeline: once a year</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of participants in the training sessions • Number of training sessions 	M27-M35(onwards)	WG+HR+EDC	Increase awareness and capacity to prevent and recognise sexual harassment.
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Table 19 IRB Actions discussed with internal stakeholders

Conclusions/next steps:

- The working group will continue meeting once a week and the EDC will be meeting once every two months. Both meeting to overview the development of actions and sustainability of them.
- The EDC has a new member and will be joining and supporting the development of the GEP
- The inclusive communication guidelines will be the next action to prioritize under institutional communication actions
- The training on Sexual & Gender Harassment is now being planned and will take place In march/april pending confirmation of the provider.
- A new seminar is being planned with Carmen Valls (one of the suggested scientist for role model video that due to calendar complications wasn't able to participate) . Dates are being studied to develop this seminar on 2023.
- Work life balance activities will continue to be organized for 2023, continuing with languages classes, yoga and football league during working hours.
- Induction sessions will continue to be done every month for all the newcomers of the institute. The rotation of members of the EDC will continue and an agenda has been drawn up to assigned a month to the members participation
- The results of the Salary audit are expected to arrive by the end of the month and this will be translated by HR to compliment the report for the Caliper Project.
- Once the report is completed will have to be attached to the GEP and signed as a V2 in order to upload to the national repository and comply with legal requirements. The signature process will be done by the Equality Commission .
- A “ refreshing” approach should be done with members of the hub to keep engagement on the working group and specially with members in which collaborative actions are in place.

Slides:

Version 2 Plan : 3 main changes

1) Caliper Framework: Intersectionality – Collaborative Actions

1 Human Resources	5	1 Human Resources	7
2 Institutional Governance	3	2 Institutional Governance	4
3 Institutional Communication	5	3 Institutional Communication	3
4 Research	2	4 Research	2
5 Young Scientists	2	5 Young Scientists	2
6 Addressing Gender and Sexual Harassment	2	6 Addressing Gender and Sexual Harassment	2
7 Transfer to Market	0	7 Transfer to Market	2
8 Intersectionality	2	8 Intersectionality	2
9 Collaborative Actions	3	9 Collaborative Actions	2
TOTAL	28	TOTAL	28

INTERSECTIONALITY
Develop awareness campaigns on Intersectionality (Human Resources)
Organise an advance training session on gender and diversity topics for members of the Equality Commission, (Institutional Governance)

COLLABORATIVE:
Introduce measures to avoid bias in selection and evaluation processes. (Human Resources)
Develop a system to monitor the evolution of women in transfer to market (Transfer to Market)
WIN Event (Transfer to Market)

GEP Update- Version 2

DECEMBER 2023

- ### Completed actions
- Review, update and disseminate existing recruitment policies and guidelines, assuring that the documentation has a gender sensitive approach.
 - Consolidate and disseminate Group Leader selection protocol.
 - Give internal and external visibility to the new Gender Equality Plan
 - Reinforce equality and diversity topics in onboarding sessions.
 - Review and update protocol on Sexual Harassment.
 - WIN EVENT

Sustainability workshop with external stakeholders:**Workshop 1: Agenda**

- GEP Overview /summary
- Create context on summative evaluation survey
- Focus on actions collaborative actions
- Scheduling next meetings

Participants list

No	Name of the organisation	Type of stakeholder * (see table below)	Gender
2	CERCA	Academic and research institutions	Female

Description the outcomes:

As stated in the agenda, the first thing in the session was to create a context of the evolution of the plan, taking into consideration the evolution of the implementation of the plan and the actions focused on 2024. The main idea of this interaction with CERCA was to regain the collaboration and re-start the brainstorming session to develop the action “Introduce measures to avoid bias in selection and evaluation processes”.

The main outcome was to define two future dates for meeting to start working together towards de evolvment of the action.

In addition, over the session a context was created of the overall evolution of the caliper project towards a better participation and understandment of the summative evaluation survey.

Strenghts:

The main strength is the fact the CERCA is also involved in the scientific scope and same methods in regards to recruitment are set in place.

The action can be used for the benefit of both institutions

Weaknesses:

Lack of expertise

Time constraints

Opportunities:

The current method is obsolete.

Threats:

Both IRB and CERCA have been in working groups together before.The amount of working groups, communities of practices may be timing consuming.

Workshop 2: Agenda

- GEP Overview /summary
- Create context on summative evaluation survey
- Focus on actions collaborative actions

- PRISMA conference
- Intersectionality context for IRB

No	Name of the organisation	Type of stakeholder * (see table below)	Gender
2	PRISMA	Civil society (excluding feminist NGOs)	male

Description the outcomes:

Prisma has been one of the closest members of R+I HUB during the evolution of the CALIPER Project. Through their collaboration, the IRB has planned and hosted activities such as round tables and engagement sessions to promote awareness in intersectionality. Because of good working interactions, the idea is to keep working together towards the EDI initiatives in the IRB. Specifically, towards the end of the GEP two main objectives were set. Initially to count with PRISMA collaboration in the planning and development of the action: “Develop awareness campaigns on Intersectionality” and to include the IRB Barcelona in the agenda of their annual conference to present the results of the Caliper Project.

The event will be celebrated the third week of November, in Madrid Spain.

Event program: [PRISMA ANNUAL EVENT](#)

Strenghts:

- Prisma has extensive expertise in intersectionality topics in the scientific world.
- Close collaboration had led to a great working interaction

Weaknesses:

- NA

Opportunities:

- Possibility to create awareness in intersectionality through the framework of GEP actions in the IRB
- Possibility to promote IRB EDC initiatives through events and conferences
- Have first-hand information and access to events that could lead to more engagement and more community of practices.

Threads

- N/A

In addition to the meeting mentioned above, brief meetings were held with members of the HUB without a specific action to be developed but as to create a context and explain the development of the GEP and the CALIPER project.

It is worth mentioning that with the following stakeholders, the communication and interaction has not been as strong and constant as with other members of the HUB especially since the interaction have not been required or simple because as time evolved during the duration of the project, the relationship did not manage to be so closed and/or productive.

Workshop 3: Agenda

- GEP Overview /summary

-Create context on summative evaluation survey

No	Name of the organisation	Type of stakeholder * (see table below)	Gender
1	ACCC (asociacion catalana de comunicacion cientifica)	Civil society (excluding feminist NGOs)	Female
1	UPF	Academic and research institutions	Female
1	UAB	Academic and research institutions	Female
1	ONA Therapeutics	Industry	Female
1	AQUAS	Civil society (excluding feminist NGOs)	Female

The brief meetings with these partners were focused in presenting a summary of the project, the duration of the GEP and expected actions to be developed in the upcoming period.

In terms of sustainability, the idea was to keep communication open and sharing good practices when actions match the objectives of both institutes.

Through AQUAS the opportunity came up to join a new community of practices In which the IRB has decide to participate to continue the momentum of the Caliper Project and the constant interaction with a working group. The community of practices will be focused in the topic of intersectionality and change management. This working group is set to be set in motion during the course of 2024.

Strenghts:

- Most of the partners in academia have to follow same legal national procedures and topics, so there is a common ground.
- Common grounds also of the industry under development, Most of the members of these meeting have a scientific scope in their day-to-day operations, and common grounds on the development of topics such as the integration of gender dimension into research.

Weaknesses:

- Overall lack of knowledge in certain topics.
- Lack of time for meetings/events leading to lack of attracting members to certain activities and actions.

Opportunities:

- Through the development of the CALIPER project and the high involvement through the development of the actions , the IRB has been perceive as institutional role model towards EDI topics. This has open the communication channels and open doors such as the invitation to join the AQUAS CoP.

Threads

- N/A

Actions discussed:

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Indicate “YES” if it is a new emerged collaboration	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	External stakeholders involved	Departments involved in the action’s implementation and personnel’s role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Introduce measures to avoid bias in selection and evaluation processes	Human Resources	Yes. Collaborative. This action has been collaborative since the design of the plan.	<p>This action is set to start on January 2024. The main idea is to prepare information on recruitment bias and send it to all the members involved in selection panels before the selection process starts`.</p> <p>This action is set to “renew” an existing measure done by CERCA (member of hub) that created a video on gender bias.</p>	<p>Personnel: EDC members With the collaboration of CERCA.</p> <p>Budget : EDC</p> <p>Timeline: Developed during the course of 2024.</p>	Open Calls in which the new information is used.	<p>Timeline: Developed during the course of 2024. Meetings have been organized and brainstorming was started.</p>	YES	EDC and with involvement of CERCA management.	<p>Printed updated material for GL selection protocols to be shared both in the IRB, and all of the members of CERCA.</p> <p>Main goal is to avoid any sort of bias in selection protocols.</p>

2	Develop awareness campaigns on Intersectionality.	Human Resources	NO	<p>The idea with this action is to work closely with one of the members of the HUB (PRISMA) to plan a series of campaigns on intersectionaity to generate awareness and involvement within the IRB Barcelona.</p> <p>The idea is to endorse all kinds of activities moving forward such as training sessions, open tables, and collaboration with events.</p>	<p>Personnel: EDC</p> <p>Budget : EDC or intennral if applicable</p> <p>Timeline: Developed during the course of 2024.</p>	<p>- Numb er of campa igns</p> <p>- Numb er of activiti es organi zed with an inters ection al scope</p>	<p>Timeline: Developed during the course of 2024. Meetings have been organized and brainstorming was started.</p>	YES	EDC and with involvement of Prisma	<p>Generate awareness on intersectionality.</p> <p>Participate in collaboration with Prisma to include intersectionality as an important topic in EDC activities.</p>
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Table 20 IRB Actions discussed with external stakeholders

III.7 Salento University (RPO)

Sustainability workshop with internal stakeholders:

The sustainability round table for UniSalento GEP activities was organized onsite at the Rectorate building and at the same time online by Meet on 8 February 2023. The people attending the meeting was internal stakeholders involved on the implementation of GEP actions and several member of CALIPER's project. This meeting was important for summarising the just concluded activities and the GEP actions to be implemented by identifying the strategies for their sustainability.

The annual report of the OmbudsPerson was a starting point for a fruitful discussion concerning the implementation of awareness-raising initiatives especially in some critical Departments. It was suggested to promote periodic training and information paths for various members of the academic community.

1. Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker
14:00 – 14:10	Introduction	A. M. Cherubini
14:10 – 15:00	Annual report of the OmbudsPerson	S. Manco
15:00 – 15:45	Report on the concluded activities and on the actions to be implemented	A. M. Cherubini, D. Di Benedetto
15:45 – 16:20	Discussion and Conclusion	All the participants

2. Participants list

No	Type of stakeholder	Gender
1	Management: Vice-Rector	F
2	Management: Rector's Delegates	F
2	Management: Rector's Delegates	M
1	Management: General Director	M
2	Academia: CUG	F
1	OmbudsPerson	F
7	Academia: Professor, Researcher	F
2	Administration: Rectorate	F

3. Outcomes

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved of the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Ensure the inclusion and well-	Human Resources	Establishment of an alias career for	CUG, Delegate for Gender	Regular reporting	Annually	Staff of the Disability Integration	Activation of alias career for

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

	being of male and female students		transgender students, which can also be used by victims of stalking, witnesses of justice.	Policies, Delegate for Privacy, Delegate for Education, Delegate for Orientation, Student Council, Coordination Table. Budget: Budgetary resources			Office of the Education Department.	transgender students.
2	Monitoring and coordination for gender equality assessment at institutional level	Gender budget in top positions and decision-making bodies	Annual updating of the Gender Balance Sheet as a key tool for evaluating GEP implementation	Personnel: CUG, Gender Delegate, Budget Delegate, Personnel Delegate, EOS Team, Coordination Table. Budget: Budgetary resources Timeline: Annual	Diffusion of Gender balance at the institutions and departments	Biannually	Technical-administration staff, teaching staff, students and PhD students.	Updating the Gender Balance.
3	Actions for young female researchers to counter dispersion and career abandonment	Gender equality in recruitment and career advancement	Establishment of a prize for the best PhD thesis written by a young female researcher from the University	CUG, Delegate for Gender Policies, Delegate for Orientation, EOS Team, Coordination Table. Budget: Budgetary resources	Regular reporting	Biannually	Students and PhD students.	Increasing the visibility of female PhD students and young researchers at UniSalento
4	Relations with the territory and national and	Gender dimension in research and teaching and	Cooperation with surgery local health center (ASL) for creation of a health including	CUG, Gender Policy Delegate, EOS Team, Coordination Table	Regular reporting, number of persons attending the center	Permanent	Regulations and Institutional Relations Office, Technical and Technological Department.	Activation of the center

	international actors;	third mission	not only basic services, but also a gynaecological service. The possibility of offering a psychological support service is also being evaluated.					
5	Creation and strengthening of networks; funding, resources and planning	Gender dimension in research and teaching and third mission	Update of the University guidelines for granting patronage to events related to gender and diversity.	CUG, Delegate for Gender Policies, Delegate for Patronage, Delegate for Research, EOS Team, Coordination Table	Regular reporting,	Annually	Staff of the Communication and OPR Office, Staff of the Rector's Private Secretary.	Drafting of Guidelines.
6	Preventing and combating bullying, harassment, discrimination and conflict in work and study relationships	Gender prejudices and stereotypes, sexism and sexual harassment	Annual monitoring of the implementation of the Code of Conduct for the Prevention of and Fight against Harassment and Sexual Harassment to be submitted to the Academic Senate.	CUG, Gender Policy Delegate, Coordination Table.	Publication of the annual reports of the Ombudsman and subsequent preparation of an analysis and planning document for interventions	Annually	Staff of the Anti-Corruption and Transparency Office.	Reduction in the number of detected situations of harassment, bullying, mobbing and discrimination and increase in those that are avoided and/or positively resolved with the help

Table 21 UNILE Actions discussed with internal stakeholders

4. Photos:

Picture 9 UNILE pictures from workshop with internal stakeholders

Sustainability workshop with external stakeholders

The GEP sustainability workshop was organized at the medical center of the University of Salento on 16 May 2023 by inviting external stakeholders for promoting the new medical center and to discuss the GEP's sustainability plan.

1 Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker
10:00 – 10:30	Welcome and Introduction	Rector
10:30-11:00	Caliper Project	A. M. Cherubini
Discussion		
11:00 – 12:30	GEP sustainability	All the participants

1 Participants list

No	Type of stakeholder	Gender
1	Management: Rector	M
2	Management: Vice Rector for Gender Policy	F
3	CUG president	F
4	Caliper Project member	F
5	Management: General Director of UniSalento	M
6	Academic staff: Professor	M
7	Academic staff: Professor	F
8	External Management: General Director of Lecce's ASL	M
9	Mayor of Lecce	M
10	Mayor of Monteroni	M
11	Medical team: healthcare assistant	F
12	Medical team: doctor	M
13	Medical Team: psychologist	

14	Councillor for welfare of the city of Lecce	F
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Main outcomes

This meeting was important to promote the medical center which is important for the health of students and University staff with actions on medicine, primary prevention and specialist services. The Medical Center was established on the basis of a memorandum of understanding between the University of Salento, the Mayor of Lecce, the Mayor of Monteroni and the ASL of Lecce.

The external stakeholders attending the workshop were involved on the activation of medical center including survey staff and Policy makers .

The internal stakeholders were academic staff involved on the implementation of GEP actions and members of CALIPER's project.

The meeting opened with a Rector's talk concerning the medical center, after that a talk of A. M. Cherubini concerning the *CALIPER Project* and the UniSalento GEP ongoing activities Then, after that a discussion concerning the *Integration of Gender and Diversity Dimensions into Institutional Policies and Strategies* was held.

Picture 10 UNILE picture from the workshop with external stakeholders

III.8 Yasar University (RPO)

Sustainability workshop with internal stakeholders

Agenda

Time	Activity	Speaker(s) / Moderator (s)
10:00-10:15	Opening and welcome speech	Assoc.Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator
	Summary of the GEP activities and status of implementation	Güldan KALEM, CALIPER institutional assistant coordinator
10:15-10:45	Discussion	GEP Working Group Members, Top Level Managers, Middle Level Managers
10:45-11:00	Conclusion & Remarks	Assoc.Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator Güldan KALEM, CALIPER institutional assistant coordinator
11:00-11:15	Preparation for the round table discussion: Information on the sustainability plan for YU GEP, formation of small working	Assoc.Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator Güldan KALEM, CALIPER institutional assistant coordinator
11:15-12:30	Round table discussion	Assoc.Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator Güldan KALEM, CALIPER institutional assistant coordinator Burcu KİPER, CALIPER Expert Efsa SABİT, CALIPER Expert Nisan GÖKDEMİREL, EU Centre Expert
12:30-12:45	Summary of round table discussion and debrief	Assoc.Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator Güldan KALEM, CALIPER institutional assistant coordinator

Participants list

No	Type of stakeholder * (see table below)	Gender
1	Management; Vice rector	M
2	Management; Vice rector	M
3	Management; Dean	F
4	Management; Vice Dean / Director of Gender Research Center	F
5	Academia & Management; Professor / Head of Department	F
6	Academia; Professor	F

7	Academia & Management Professor / Director of EU Research Center	M
8	Academia & Management Professor / Director of Academic Planning and Quality	M
9	Academia & Management Professor / Director of Open and Distance Education Center	M
10	Academia; Professor	M
11	Management; Deputy Secretary General / Director of Human Resources	F
12	Administration; Director of Competition Relations Analysis and Central Planning	M
13	Administration; Human Resources Chief	F
14	Administration; Research / Project Support Office Chief	F
15	Administration; Research / Project Support Office Chief	F
16	Administration; Research / Project Support Office Expert	F
17	Administration; Research / Project Support Office Expert	F
18	Administration; Research / Project Support Office Assistant	F

Description the outcomes:

The Sustainability Workshop brought together representatives of top management, academia and administration who are responsible for the GEP implementation of Yasar University to prepare the ground for developing the sustainability plan of the institutional GEP actions. A balanced distribution of internal target groups and genders were achieved as shown in the graphics below.

Participants were divided into smaller round tables according to the GEP actions areas and the expertise of the internal stakeholders. Each round table had a moderator from CALIPER project team to facilitate dialogue and discussion. Moderators shared the completed, ongoing and planned GEP actions with their group members and initiated a discussion on possible actions from GEP that can be sustained over time and become institutional practice and implementation.

The composition of the round table was as follows:

- **Human Resources & Institutional Governance:** Moderated by Assoc.Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER Institutional Coordinator, the round table included Vice Rector for Research and Innovation, Deputy Secretary General and Director of Human Resources, Director of Academic Planning and Quality, and the Chief of Human Resources.
- **Research:** Moderated by Burcu KİPER, CALIPER Expert, the round table included the Dean Faculty of Human and Social Sciences and the director for Competition Relations Analysis and Central Planning
- **Teaching:** Moderated by Güldan KALEM, CALIPER institutional assistant coordinator, the round table included the Vice Rector for Academic Affairs and the Director of Open and Distance Education Center
- **Institutional Communication:** Moderated by Efsa SABİT, CALIPER Expert, the round table included the Head of Radio, Television and Cinema Department at the Faculty of Communication and Head of Art and Design at Graduate School
- **Sexual Harassment:** Moderated by Nisan GÖKDEMİREL, EU Centre Expert, the round table included Vice Dean, Faculty of Communication / Women Family Studies Application and Research Center Director and professor at vocational school.

The following actions were identified for the institutional sustainability plan:

Human Resources:

Addition of gender equality as a principle to the human resources policy for sustainability of GEP results

Inclusion of the recording and materials of trainings organized within the project in the orientation programme of new staff with certification

Strengthening gender dimension of human resources through the institutional HRS4R award application and implementation process to be completed in 2023.

Institutional Governance:

Introduction of an internal newsletter or bulletin on gender equality to increase the visibility of gender equality

Presentation of gender disaggregated data as a report to the Board of Trustees by gender research center (YUKAM) annually for increasing the representation of women in top management.

Research:

Integration of gender equality as a stand-alone category with all GEP actions as KPIs in the next strategic plan. (At the moment gender equality is integrated in the institutional strategic plan under two categories: social sustainability and societal impact.)

Recruitment of researchers and academics who are exclusively working on gender to support gender research and capacity of the organization

Teaching:

Inclusion of a statement of adherence to gender equality in each syllabus prepared by academics at Yasar University. CALIPER team will prepare the statement and share it with the vice rectorate for academic affairs. (How gender equal is your syllabus?)

Promoting GEP at student orientation programme

Institutional Communication:

Training of trainers and creation of “gender equality representatives” pool that will promote and train staff members on gender sensitive institutional communication

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Sexual Harassment

In addition to the prevention of sexual harassment through the unit, materials such as podcasts, videos, animations that will capture the attention of the viewer and create a transformation in terms of mentality should be created for sustainability.

Addition of ***a new training on preventing sexual harassment*** for heads of departments, directors, managers and deputies (including those internally promoted), heads of student associations and the student council president

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved of the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action	Is the action supported by any national/European law? If yes, please mention the law
1	Gender-sensitive recruitment procedures	Human Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adding gender dimension in human resources policy document⁷ HRS4R award application and the application of OTM-R (open, transparent, merit-based recruitment principles) 	Personnel: Human Resources Budget: Institutional Timeline:2024 - 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of staff members trained on gender sensitive recruitment procedure Number of female applicants in all areas, especially STEM 	2024 - 2026	Human Resources Department and HRS4R steering committee and work committee	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased gender awareness for human resources staff as well as managers, heads of departments, offices and centers Increased number of female applicants in all areas, especially STEM 	European Charter for Researchers and a Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers
2	Empowerment programme for underrepresented gender at the institutional level	Human Resources	Inclusion of the recording and materials of empowerment programme for new staff with certification	Personnel: Human Resources Budget: Institutional Timeline:2024 – onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of new staff members trained within the empowerment programme 	2024 – onwards	Human Resources Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Skills and competencies created for underrepresented gender at the institutional level 	N/A

⁷ GEP Working group already followed up on this measure and as of December 9, 2022 institutional human resources policy includes gender equality as a principle. The policy document is published in English on <https://kalite.yasar.edu.tr/en/insan-kaynaklari-politikasi/>

3	Gender disaggregated data to be reported to the Board of Trustees	Institutional Governance	Reporting of gender disaggregated data annually to the Board of Trustees	Personnel: Gender research center Budget: Institutional Timeline: 2024-onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of meetings and reports on gender disaggregated budget 	2024 – onwards	Gender Research Center	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased awareness of top management on the current gender analysis at the institutional level Increased number of female top managers 	N/A
4	Integration of gender into institutional strategic plan	Research	Integration of gender equality as a stand-alone category with all GEP actions as KPIs in the next strategic plan	Personnel: Top management Budget: Institutional Timeline: 2023- 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Decision of top management to integrate gender as a stand-alone category in the institutional strategic plan 	2023-2025	Top management Strategic Planning and Excellence Office	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Further institutionalization of gender in policy and strategy 	N/A
5	Gender Researchers Group	Research	Recruitment of researchers and academics who are exclusively working on gender to support gender research and capacity of the organization	Personnel: Human Resources Department Budget: Institutional Timeline:2024 – onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of researchers and academics recruited 	2024 – onwards	Top management Human Resources Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased gender research capacity of the organization 	N/A
6	Training and pilot implementation	Teaching	Inclusion of a statement of adherence to gender equality in each syllabus	Personnel: Vice Rector for academic affairs Budget: Institutional Timeline: 2024	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of course syllabi with gender equality adherence included 	2024	Vice rector for academic affairs Departments and Faculties	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased awareness to integration of gender dimension in teaching 	N/A

7	Gender-sensitive institutional communication guidelines	Institutional Communication	Creation of an internal newsletter to promote gender equality in communication	Personnel: Deputy Secretary General for Corporate Communications Gender research center	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of newsletters prepared and disseminated 	2024-onwards	Deputy Secretary General for Corporate Communications Gender research center	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased gender sensitive communication awareness among staff members 	N/A
8	Gender sensitive communication trainings	Institutional Communication	Training of trainers and creation of “gender equality representatives” pool that will promote and train staff members on gender sensitive institutional communication	Personnel: Deputy Secretary General for Corporate Communications Human Resources Department Budget: Institutional Timeline: 2024 - onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of staff members trained in training of trainers Number of gender equality representatives 	2024 – onwards	Deputy Secretary General for Corporate Communications Human Resources Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased gender sensitive communication awareness among staff members Increased gender sensitive communication practices at the institutional level Increased number of staff members who are working for gender sensitive communication 	
9	Gender sensitive communication trainings	Institutional Communication	Promoting GEP at student orientation programme	Personnel: Central Academic Planning Department (responsible for student orientation programme) Gender research center	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of orientation programmes implemented 	2024-onwards	Central Academic Planning Department Gender research center HeforShe student association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased gender sensitive communication awareness among students 	N/A

				HeforShe student association Budget: Institutional Timeline: 2024-onwards					
10	Gender Based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual Harassment Prevention Unit	Sexual harassment	New training on preventing sexual harassment	Personnel: Human Resources Department Gender research center Budget: Institutional Timeline: 2024 - onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of staff heads of departments, directors, managers and deputies (including those internally promoted), heads of student associations and the student council president trained, Number of trainings 	2024-onwards	Gender research center Human Resources Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increased awareness on prevention of sexual harassment 	N/A

11	Gender Based Discrimination, Violence and Sexual Harassment Prevention Unit	Sexual harassment	Awareness raising materials such as podcasts, videos, animations	Personnel: Gender research center Budget: Institutional Timeline: 2024 - onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of awareness raising materials • Number of posts on institutional social media accounts 	2024-onwards	Gender research center HeforShe student association	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased awareness towards sexual harassment among staff and students 	N/A
12	Awareness raising trainings	Human Resources, Research, Teaching, Institutional Communication	Inclusion of the recording and materials of trainings organized within the project as permanent trainings in Moodle LMS of the university	Personnel: Human Resources Department Budget: Institutional Timeline: 2024-onwards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of staff members trained 	2024-onwards	Human Resources Department	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased awareness towards gender equality in CALIPER GEP action areas • Institutionalization of the CALIPER GEP 	N/A

Table 22 YU Actions discussed with internal stakeholders

Conclusions and next steps

The sustainability workshop was highly successful as it produced many measures for the institutionalization of GEP at Yasar University. CALIPER Project team will closely follow and monitor the sustainability measures identified in the workshop in the design of the GEP following the end of the project.

Photos

Picture 11 YU Pictures from workshop with internal stakeholders

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Sustainability workshop with external stakeholders**Agenda**

Time	Activity	Speaker(s) / Moderator (s)
14:00-14:10	<i>Opening and welcome speech</i>	<i>Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator</i>
14:10-14:45	<i>Integration of Gender and Diversity Dimensions into Institutional Policies and Strategies</i>	<i>Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator</i>
14:45-15:20	<i>CALIPER Project</i>	<i>Güldan KALEM, CALIPER institutional assistant coordinator</i>
15:20-15:55	<i>EU Funds for Gender Equality and Diversity</i>	<i>Burcu KİPER, Impact Acceleration Manager, Crowdhelix</i>
15:55-16:30	<i>Discussion on Sustainability of CALIPER Actions</i>	<i>Facilitator: Prof.Dr. Gökay ÖZERİM, CALIPER institutional coordinator</i> <i>Participants: Representatives from stakeholders</i>
16:30-16:45	<i>Q&A</i>	

Participants list

No	Name-Surname	Gender	Type of stakeholder
1	Ayla Çelik	Female	Feminist NGOs / gender experts
2	Başak Ovacık	Female	Academic and research institutions
3	Burcu Kiper	Female	Industry
4	Burkay Pasin	Male	Academic and research institutions
5	Destina Berfin Sever	Female	Academic and research institutions
6	Dilekcan Denizci	Female	Industry
7	Elçin Doruk	Female	Academic and research institutions
8	Elif Reis	Female	Academic and research institutions
9	Emre İşeri	Male	Academic and research institutions
10	Eren Jale	Female	Industry
11	Ezgi Özey	Female	Academic and research institutions
12	Fatma Kılıç	Female	Civil society (excluding feminist NGOs)
13	Fatma Türüç	Female	Academic and research institutions
14	Fatoş Dayıoğlu	Female	Feminist NGOs / gender experts
15	Filiz Sargın	Female	Industry
16	Funda Üvek	Female	Feminist NGOs / gender experts
17	Gökay Özerim	Male	Academic and research institutions
18	Gulsum Akarsu	Female	Academic and research institutions
19	Güldan Kalem	Female	Academic and research institutions
20	Gülşa Baykuş	Female	Industry
21	Hatice Demir	Female	Civil society (excluding feminist NGOs)
22	Huriye Toker	Female	Academic and research institutions
23	İlgın Öztürk	Female	Academic and research institutions
24	Irem Ozgoren Kınlı	Female	Academic and research institutions

25	Kevser Çimenli	Female	Academic and research institutions
26	Lütfiye Kader	Female	Public sector (excluding academia/public research institutions)
27	Mehmet Emin Bakay	Male	Academic and research institutions
28	Mehmet Kahyaoglu	Male	Academic and research institutions
29	Nisan Gökdemirel	Female	Academic and research institutions
30	Oğuz Can Ok	Male	Academic and research institutions
31	Onur Kınlı	Male	Academic and research institutions
32	Sami Kaan Şen	Male	Academic and research institutions
33	Seda Banu Yuşan	Female	Public sector (excluding academia/public research institutions)
34	Seha Şahin	Female	Civil society (excluding feminist NGOs)
35	Seher Ergüney	Female	Academic and research institutions
36	Selin Atış	Female	Academic and research institutions
37	Sena Ortakışlalı	Female	Academic and research institutions
38	Sevtap Şirin	Female	Feminist NGOs / gender experts
39	Süheyla Üçışık Erbilen	Female	Academic and research institutions
40	Yonca Odabaş	Female	Academic and research institutions

Description the outcomes:

On November 16th, 2023, the CALIPER project team at Yasar University hosted its second sustainability workshop, which was conducted online. The workshop saw representatives from various stakeholders, such as academic and research institutions, the public sector, industry, and civil society, in attendance. Most of the participants were from academic and research institutions, but there was also a significant interest from the industry. Managers of businesses and industry partners attended the session, along with participants from civil society, including feminist NGOs. The majority of participants were female.

Figure 1 YU Type of stakeholders participated at the workshop with external stakeholders

Figure 2 YU Gender distribution of people participated at the workshop with external stakeholders

The first part of the workshop focused on CALIPER project, how to integrate gender and diversity in institutional policies, and various EU funds on gender equality and diversity to provide participants with background information and refresh their knowledge on the different aspects of the CALIPER project.

During the workshop, two main actions were discussed with the participants. Prof.Dr.Gökay Özerim, the institutional coordinator of the CALIPER project at Yasar University facilitated the discussion. It was decided that **awareness-raising activities** targeting external stakeholders and **collaborative projects** (national and international) will be continued with external stakeholders. The Gender Research Centre at Yasar University will be primarily responsible for the continuation of the involvement of different stakeholders in sustained actions.

SWOT analysis

<p>A.Strengths</p> <p>1. What is the expected outcome of the action?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased number of awareness-raising and empowerment activities targeting external stakeholders • Increased number of collaborative actions/project proposals with external stakeholders <p>1. What resources (human and financial) do we have/need?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Researchers/Research Support Office/Gender Research Centre <p>2. Do we have the support of the top management?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes 	<p>B.Weaknesses</p> <p>1. How can the action be improved?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • By strategically designing awareness-raising and empowerment activities targeting external stakeholders through focus groups and surveys • Providing tailor-made and impactful activities in collaboration with external stakeholders • Including external stakeholders & R&I Hub in the design and development of project proposals / co-creation <p>2. Where are we lacking resources (human and financial)?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NGOs lack human and financial resources
<p>D. Opportunities</p> <p>1. What policies we can leverage on to implement/sustain the action?</p>	<p>C.Threats</p> <p>1. What issues can hold back our action?</p>

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrating gender dimension in research Cross-cutting issues such as diversity and inclusion, open and responsible science Attracting female students into STEM field <p>1. What kind of issue this action intends to tackle?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Breaking the stereotypes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conflicting schedules between different stakeholders Lack of follow-up and monitoring <p>2. Potential conflicts?</p> <p>None</p>
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Conclusions and next steps

The workshop aimed at external stakeholders proved to be a valuable step in ensuring the sustainability of the gender equality actions of CALIPER with the involvement of external stakeholders. The engagement of external stakeholders through a quadruple helix innovation ecosystem approach has allowed for a more comprehensive and collaborative approach to gender equality, and the planned actions for future collaboration will play a critical role in the sustainability of the CALIPER project.

Photos

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 873134.

Actions to be sustained

No	Name of the action	The thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	External stakeholders involved	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Awareness raising and empowerment action	HR	<p>Inviting external stakeholders to awareness-raising and empowerment activities</p> <p>Organizing joint awareness-raising and empowerment activities</p> <p>Continuous communication and engagement with external stakeholders on gender issues</p>	During the workshop, it was mentioned that additional resources such as personnel and budget allocation would be required, but no exact figures were identified.	<p>Number of activities/trainings organized.</p> <p>Number of external stakeholders participating in the awareness-raising and empowerment activities</p> <p>Number of surveys and questionnaires to measure the impact of the activities</p>	2024-2026	R&I hub	<p>Gender Research Centre</p> <p>Human Resources Department</p>	<p>Increased number of collaborations with R&I Hub</p> <p>Increased awareness level among R&I Hub members on gender</p>
2	Collaborative Projects	Research	<p>Preparation of joint projects (local, national, international and EU) with external stakeholders on gender equality and diversity</p> <p>Implementation of funded projects</p> <p>Possibility of developing "social responsibility" projects with industry partners</p>	During the workshop, it was mentioned that additional resources such as personnel and budget allocation would be required, but no exact figures were identified.	<p>Number of project proposals submitted to various funding programmes</p> <p>Number of internally funded project applications</p> <p>Number of social responsibility collaborations with industry partners</p>	2024-2026	R&I hub	<p>Vice-rectorate for research and development (all related project support offices included)</p> <p>Social Entrepreneurship and Social Impact Unit</p> <p>Gender Research Centre</p>	<p>Increased number of collaborations with R&I Hub</p> <p>Increased awareness level among R&I Hub members on gender</p>

Table 23 YU Actions discussed with external stakeholders

III.9 Executive Unit for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding in Romania (RFO)

UEFISCDI organized a sustainability workshop on GEP activities on 30th January 2023. The aim of the meeting was to develop tools and establish ways in which the actions already implemented, or course of implementing are to be sustain by future actions.

The workshop lasted for 2 hours.

Main results of the meeting were a set of actions to be taken in the future to increase the impact of the GEP. The below report presents and summarizes the combined outcomes of these discussions.

Agenda

- Introduction
- Presentation of actions, progress & results
[1st Iteration Phase & look ahead into 2nd iteration]
- Sustainability and long-term durability of GEP actions [Discussion]
- Actions to be taken and timeline

Participants list

1. Luciana Bratu (F), Deputy Manager UEFISCDI, member of GEB
2. Cosmin Cioranu (M), Head of IT department, member of GEB
3. Marius Mitroi (M), Head of Innovation department, member of GEB
4. Alex Dinu (M), GEP coordinator, member of GEB
5. Elena Simion (F), International projects Coordinator, member of GEB
6. Irina Geanta (F), Higher Education Department, member of GEB
7. Oana Ionescu (F), CALIPER working group

Description the outcomes:

During the 2 hours meeting were presented the results of the 1st year of implementation, the resistances encountered, ways in which they were dealt with and plans for the second iteration. The main goal of the discussion were to secure ways and tool in which action already taken will be transformed in sustainable action that will impact the organization after the second iteration of GEPs ends

Main decisions taken following the discussions:

- GEB mandate lasts until end of 2024 and new elections will be made on fall of 2024.
- After the second iterations ends (December 2023), GEB will create a working group to develop a Diversity and Inclusivity Plan. The Diversity and Inclusivity plan will be developed by mid 2024 and after its development will start the implementation.
- In case actions in the actual GEP are not finalized by end of 2023, the GEP will be prolonged according to the needs.
- A position for Gender Equality Officer will be created in UEFISCDI in 2024

Measures on the area of Human Resources will be embedded in the various guidelines created: recruitment guidelines, back-to-work guidelines etc. The actual UEFISCDI's Code of Conduct will be updated with suggestion from these guidelines.

Measures on the area of Institutional Communication are also embedded in the Inclusive communication guidelines created. A measure to create specific communication guidelines targeting specific communicational situations is needed.

Measures on the area of Gender Based Violence: The guidelines for preventing sexual and moral harassment will be included in UEFISCDI's Code of Ethics

Measures on Research Funding will be sustained and further developed on the basis of a policy brief that will be developed using the results from internal analysis on research funding. Regarding the evaluation process, training for evaluators will be developed accompanied by guidelines.

Measures on Institutional Governance: elections for a new GEB component will take place on Q3 of 2024. A position for Gender Equality Officer will be created.

All guidelines and trainings that are to be developed in the GEP will be video recorded and uploaded in a repository of results of GEP – www.gep.uefiscdi.ro . In this way the video materials will be available longer with greater impact.

No	Name of the action	Thematic area	Brief description on how you plan to continue the action. It should be an action list including the necessary steps	Resources needed (personnel, budget, timeline)	Suggested KPIs for monitoring	Draft timeline of its implementation	Departments involved in the action's implementation and personnel's role	Expected outcome of the action
1	Recruitment guidelines	Human Resources	Continue promotion of guidelines Monitor application of guidelines	No budget needed	Collect indicators to measure changes in the recruitment process Track application of guidelines – conduct survey on applicants	2024-2026	GEB Caliper Working group HR Dep.	Permanently avoid unconscious bias, equip recruitment staff with tools and proactive training.
2	Training for recognizing unconscious bias	Career progression	Create online video resources based on the offline training Organize annual training for all employees	TBC	Conduct surveys on employees after training Collect feedback from them	2023 onwards	GEB Caliper Working group	More and more employees become aware of their bias and the ways it interfere with their day to day work
3	Back-to-work guidelines	Human Resources	Continue promotion of guidelines Monitor application of guidelines	No budget needed	Interviews with personnel returning from parental leave (qualitative)	2024-2026	GEB Caliper Working group	Update the guidelines in according to the feedback received

4	Sexual Harrasment Guidelines	Sexual Harrasment	Continue promotion of guidelines Monitor application of guidelines Integrate the measures from the guideline in the Code of Ethics	No budget needed	Interviews with employees (qualitative)	2024-2026	GEB Caliper Working group	Update the guidelines according to the feedback
5	Inclusive communication guidelines	Institu tional comm unciati on	Continue promotion of guidelines Monitor application of guidelines Working together with communication department to develop specific templates for inclusive communication	No budget needed	Interviews with employees (qualitative)	2024-2026	GEB Caliper Working group Communication department	Update the guidelines according to the feedback
6	Gender Equality Body	Institu tional govern ance	Organize new election for GEB in q3 of 2024 Creating a new position for a Gender Equality Officer	No budget	Yearly report with indicators after the year 1 and year 2 of mandate	2024 onwards	Top management CALIPER working group	More employees interested in being part of GEB or supporting groups
7	Analysis of research funding from gender perspective	Resear ch Fundin g	After the analysis of research funding instrument from a gender perspective si finalized, a policy brief will be developed based on its results.	No budget needed	A new analysis should be conducted after the implementation of GEP	2025-27	Top management GEB CALIPER working group	Changes in the call text for funding instruments and evaluation guidelines coming from the Ministry

			The policy brief will be published on a conference and will serve as a basis for further with the Ministry					
8	Training for evaluators	Research Funding	Implement a section in the evaluation sheet where evaluators should leave comments whether the application targets GD, in which way or why it should not	No budget needed	Number of comments left	2024 -2026	Top management	A better integration of GD in research content

Table 24 UEFISCDI Actions discussed with internal stakeholders

Conclusions and next steps

The GEP will be sustained beyond the projects duration by creating institutional structures that will continue the actions from the GEP. Also the CALIPER working group will continue to develop a new Diversity and Inclusion Plan starting from 2024. UEFISCDI is also partner in other projects dedicated to GE – Genderaction+ and will continue to promote GE as a crucial value in Romanian RI community.

Sustainability workshop with external stakeholders

All materials used in the workshop are gathered here -

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1ei7TJY40q0oNWN5CbLdW_r_XuZsNsna3?usp=sharing

Agenda

- 16.00 - 16.10: Welcome note ANES, UEFISCDI
 - Mr. Adrian Curaj, General Director UEFISCDI
 - Mrs. Liliana Popescu, Secretary of State/Other representative ANES
- 16.10 - 16.20: Importance of GEP in the context of Horizon Europe eligibility conditions – NCP UEFISCDI
- 16.20 - 16.35: Tools, measures, and actions from GEP. Next steps in evaluation.- UEFISCDI
- 16.35 - 17.00: Evaluation of a GEP – process, importance, Q&A - UEFISCDI
- 17.00 - 17.05: Break
- 17.05 - 17.20: Importance of gender dimension in research – University of Bucharest
- 17.20 - 17.40: Intersectionality and gender equality – Presentation & Q&A – University of Bucharest
- 17.40 - 18.00: Gender violence in Romanian public organizations - ANES
- 18.00 - 18.10: Q&A and conclusions - UEFISCDI

Participants list

No	Name of the organisation
1	TAMARA ANASTASIU
2	Olteanu Laura
3	Alex Dinu# UEFISCDI (Elena Simion)
4	Gilda Niculescu
5	Mariana Ardeleanu-INCEMC Timisoara
6	Tatiana Adriana Oprea
7	Eduard-Laurențiu Maciu
8	Oana Cătălina TACHE
9	Sbarcea Gabriela
10	Georgia Sima (IMNR-Romania)
11	Anamaria Ravar (UEFISCDI)
12	Cristina Teculescu- INCEMC Timisoara (Cristina Teculescu)
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24	Lucia Pintilie _ICCF Bucuresti (Lucia Pintilie)
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29	Roxana Marinescu
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45	Mihaela Alina Dragan
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47	Brânză Grațiela (Universitatea Maritima Constanța)
48	Alexandra Dimofte
49	Sorina (Simona Socoleanu - Synesis Partners)
50	Andreea Radu - Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara (Andreea Radu - WUT# SupportTM Center)

51	Daniela Draghici
52	Mihaela Frincu
53	ADRSM-Maria NUTU-
54	Andreea Nita ADRSM
55	Andreea Potinteu
56	violeta postole#comoti
57	ACZ Consulting Romania
58	Anela Pleşcan-ACZ Consulting Romania
59	Iris Alexe
60	Ramona Mihaila's iPhone
61	Liviu Oprea - UMF Grigore T. Popa din Iasi (Liviu)
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75	Andra Jakab
76	Centruldeformaremara12356
77	Ramona Mihaila
78	Cristina Dragomir
79	Galaxy S10

Description the outcomes:

During the workshop, several pivotal issues were addressed, each corresponding to a specific collaborative action:

Collaborative Action 1: Implementation and Evaluation of Gender Equality Plans (GEP)**Issues Discussed:**

- The significance of GEPs in the context of Horizon Europe eligibility conditions.
- The process of evaluating a GEP, its importance, and the challenges faced during evaluation.

Outcomes:

- A consensus was reached on the need for a standardized evaluation process for GEPs.
- Participants recognized the importance of GEPs in securing Horizon Europe funding and committed to ensuring their institutions meet the required standards.

Collaborative Action 2: Gender Dimension in Research

Issues Discussed:

- The role of gender in shaping research outcomes.
- The benefits of integrating a gender perspective into research methodologies.

Outcomes:

- Participants acknowledged the value of incorporating the gender dimension in research and pledged to advocate for its inclusion in future projects.

Collaborative Action 3: Intersectionality and Gender Equality**Issues Discussed:**

- Definitions and concepts related to intersectionality.
- The correlation between intersectionality and gender equality concepts.

Outcomes:

- A shared understanding of intersectionality was established, emphasizing its importance in addressing gender equality comprehensively.

Collaborative Action 4: Addressing Gender Violence in Romanian Public Organizations**Issues Discussed:**

- The prevalence and forms of gender violence in Romanian public organizations.
- Strategies and measures to combat gender violence.

Outcomes:

- Participants agreed on the urgency of addressing gender violence and committed to implementing preventive measures in their respective organizations.

i. Actions Discussed and Agreements

Out of the collaborative actions discussed, the following were agreed upon for continuation:

To Continue:

- **Collaborative Action 1:** A task force will be set up to standardize the GEP evaluation process.
- **Collaborative Action 2:** Workshops and training sessions will be organized to educate researchers on the importance of the gender dimension in research.
- **Collaborative Action 4:** A zero-tolerance policy towards gender violence will be adopted across all participating organizations.

To Re-evaluate:

- **Collaborative Action 3:** While the importance of intersectionality was acknowledged, participants felt the need for further discussions to determine actionable steps.

SWOT Analysis for Collaborative Action: Implementation and Evaluation of Gender Equality Plans (GEP)**Strengths**

1. **Expected Outcome:** The expected outcome of this action is to have a standardized and effective GEP in place that meets the Horizon Europe eligibility conditions.
2. **Resources:**
 - **Human:** Dedicated team of gender equality experts and researchers.
 - **Financial:** Allocated budget for training, workshops, and evaluation processes.
3. **Top Management Support:** Yes, the top management is fully supportive and recognizes the importance of GEPs.

Weaknesses

1. **Improvements:** The action requires more frequent feedback loops to ensure that the GEPs are up-to-date and relevant.

2. Lacking Resources:

- **Human:** Need for more trainers and evaluators.
- **Financial:** Additional funds for outreach and awareness campaigns

Opportunities

1. **Policies:** The Horizon Europe funding guidelines can be leveraged to emphasize the importance of GEPs.
2. **Issue Addressed:** This action aims to ensure gender equality in research institutions and to secure Horizon Europe funding.

Threats

1. **Issues Holding Back:** Resistance from certain departments or faculties that do not see the immediate relevance of GEPs.
2. **Potential Conflicts:** Differences in understanding and interpretation of gender equality measures among different departments.

Potential Resistances/Barriers/Facilitators Identified:

Resistances:

- Skepticism about the effectiveness of GEPs.
- Concerns about the additional workload and bureaucracy involved in implementing and evaluating GEPs.

Barriers:

- Lack of awareness and understanding of the importance of gender equality in some departments.
- Limited financial resources for extensive training and workshops.

Facilitators:

- Strong support from top management.
- Availability of a dedicated team of gender equality experts.
- The incentive of securing Horizon Europe funding.

Conclusions:

1. **Significance of GEPs:** The workshop emphasized the critical importance of Gender Equality Plans (GEPs) not only for meeting Horizon Europe eligibility conditions but also for fostering a more inclusive and equitable research environment.
2. **Challenges Identified:** While there is strong support from top management and a dedicated team in place, there are challenges in terms of resource allocation, both human and financial. Additionally, resistance from certain departments and potential conflicts in understanding gender equality measures need to be addressed.
3. **Opportunities Ahead:** The Horizon Europe guidelines present a significant opportunity to emphasize the importance of GEPs and to secure funding. Moreover, the action aims to address the broader issue of gender equality in research institutions.
4. **Collaborative Effort:** The workshop highlighted the need for a collaborative effort involving all departments and stakeholders. Feedback loops and regular evaluations are essential to ensure the effectiveness and relevance of GEPs.

Next Steps:

1. **Awareness Campaign:** Launch an awareness campaign to educate all departments about the importance of GEPs and address any skepticism or concerns.
2. **Resource Allocation:** Seek additional funding sources for training and workshops. Consider hiring more trainers and evaluators to ensure the effective implementation and evaluation of GEPs.

3. **Feedback Mechanism:** Establish a regular feedback mechanism where departments can share their experiences, challenges, and suggestions related to GEPs.
4. **Collaboration with External Stakeholders:** Engage with external stakeholders, including gender equality experts and Horizon Europe representatives, to gain insights and recommendations for improving GEPs.
5. **Review and Update:** Schedule a follow-up workshop in six months to review the progress made, address any new challenges, and update the GEPs as necessary.
6. **Roadmap for Sustainability:** Develop a roadmap outlining the steps to ensure the sustainability of collaborative actions beyond the project's end. This will include identifying stakeholders' interests, influence, and capacities.

Picture 12 UEFISCDI Pictures from workshop with external stakeholders